

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D2.9

Data on regulatory and socio-economic conditions and impacts (a)

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D2.9
Deliverable title	Data on regulatory and socio-economic conditions and impacts (a)
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	P
Due date	31.12.2023 (Month 12)
Pages	154
Document version	4.0
Lead author(s)	Monika Bucha (KIE), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)
Contributors	Sam Klap (UU), Sarah Lonscher (KIE), Jasper Lueke (KIE), Jens Lowitzsch (KIE)

The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	24.10.2023	Monika Bucha (KIE), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Creation
0.2	04.12.2023	Monika Bucha (KIE), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU), Sam Klap (UU), Sarah Lonscher (KIE), Jasper Lueke (KIE), Jens Lowitzsch (KIE)	Consolidation of input from contributors
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	11.12.2023	Muhammad Andy Pu-tratama (VUB); Shary Heuinckx (VUB)	Proofreading and peer review
SECOND PEER REVIEW			
2.0	12.12.2023	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich; Alena Lohrmann, ETH Zurich	Second peer review
2.1	20.12.2023	Jens Lowitzsch (KIE), Monika Bucha (KIE), Sarah Lonscher (KIE), Jasper Lueke (KIE), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
3.0	21.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator review
3.1	21.12.2023	Jens Lowitzsch (KIE), Monika Bucha (KIE), Sarah Lonscher (KIE), Jasper Lueke (KIE), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Consolidation of input from coordinator
3.2	21.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator approval

FINAL VERSION

4.0	22.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission
-----	------------	--------------------	---

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract This deliverable presents the methodologies and the first version of the data sets or models related to regulations, governance configurations, financing sources and job creation in the wind power industry in Europe.

Concerning regulations relevant for wind power deployment we offer a descriptive analysis of the 'lege lata' involving legal interpretation and legal fact finding. Regarding governance configurations for wind power deployment, we provide empirical studies on various forms of participatory mechanisms to potentially increase wind power acceptance. Considering financing sources, we offer an in-depth analysis of funding mechanism of the European Union.

Concerning job creation, we provide a model that estimates the employment factor in job-years per installed capacity (job-years/MW) for individual wind farms. This requires as input the turbine capacities in MW, the country where the farm is located and whether it is onshore or offshore. Outputs are disaggregated into job types and life cycle stages.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	16
1.1	Regulatory Framework for Wind Power.....	16
1.2	Governance Models for Wind Power Projects.....	17
1.3	Financing Resources.....	18
1.4	Job creation relevance and definitions	18
1.4.1	Job types in the wind power industry	19
1.4.2	Jobs sectors in the wind power industry.....	20
1.4.3	Quantification approach: Employment factor.....	20
2.	METHODOLOGY	22
2.1	Gathering data on regulations to wind energy development	22
2.2	Evaluation of Wind Energy Governance and Financing Sources.....	24
2.3	Determining job creation estimates	24
2.3.1	Job creation literature review	24
2.3.2	Semi-structured interviews about job creation.....	25
2.3.3	Data analysis of job creation data from literature.....	26
2.3.4	Job creation model development	27
3.	REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR WIND POWER	28
3.1	Austria.....	28
3.1.1	Wind Energy Zones.....	28
3.1.2	Environmental Impact Assessment	32
3.1.3	Electricity Law Permit.....	32
3.1.4	Building Law	33
3.1.5	Nature and Cultural Heritage Law.....	34
3.1.6	Measures to Raise Acceptance	35
3.2	Italy.....	35

- 3.2.1 Wind Energy Zones 36
- 3.2.2 Environmental Impact Assessment 39
- 3.2.3 Electricity Law Permit..... 40
- 3.2.4 Building Law 41
- 3.2.5 Nature and Cultural Heritage 42
- 3.2.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance 43
- 3.3 Portugal..... 43
 - 3.3.1 Wind Energy Zones 43
 - 3.3.2 Environmental Impact Assessment 47
 - 3.3.3 Electricity Law Permit..... 47
 - 3.3.4 Building Law 48
 - 3.3.5 Nature and Culture Heritage 49
 - 3.3.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance 49
- 3.4 Norway 50
 - 3.4.1 Wind Energy Zones 51
 - 3.4.2 Environmental Impact Assessment 53
 - 3.4.3 Electricity Law Permit..... 54
 - 3.4.4 Building Law 55
 - 3.4.5 Nature and Cultural Heritage..... 56
 - 3.4.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance 57
- 3.5 Synthesis of Regulatory Framework 58
- 4. GOVERNANCE MODELS..... 60
 - 4.1 Overview of the EU Governance Framework for Wind Energy..... 60
 - 4.1.1 Europeanization versus Member State Sovereignty..... 60
 - 4.1.2 The Energy Union and the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package 60
 - 4.1.3 Fit for 55 Package..... 63
 - 4.1.4 REPowerEU Plan..... 64
 - 4.1.5 European Wind Power Action Plan (COM/2023/669) 64
 - 4.2 Co-Investments and Financial Participation in Wind Energy 64

4.2.1	Renewable and Citizen Energy Communities	64
4.2.2	RE Auctions – a determinant for community actors?	67
4.3	Possible Constellations of Wind Energy Projects Enhancing acceptance	69
4.3.1	100% Citizen Projects	70
4.3.2	Commercial Wind Project Developer and Majority Citizen Shareholding.....	71
4.3.3	Commercial Wind Project Developer and Minority Citizen Shareholding.....	72
4.3.4	Commercial Actors and Citizen Project.....	72
4.3.5	Commercial Actor and Municipality.....	73
4.3.6	Municipal Project	73
4.3.7	Citizen and Municipality Project	73
4.3.8	SME, Citizen and Municipality	74
4.4	Synthesis of Governance Models	74
5.	FINANCING RESOURCES	76
5.1	Institutional & Financial Framework.....	76
5.1.1	Institutional Embeddedness	76
5.1.2	Financial Volumes.....	77
5.2	Eligibility of Wind Energy by Financing Resources	80
5.2.1	European Structural and Investment Funds	80
5.2.2	Just Transition Mechanism	82
5.2.2.1	Just Transition Fund	82
5.2.2.2	Just Transition Scheme under InvestEU	83
5.2.2.3	Public Sector Loan Facility (PSLF)	83
5.2.3	Innovation Fund & Modernisation Fund (2021 – 2030)	84
5.2.4	LIFE Clean Energy Transition Sub-Programme.....	85
5.3	Conclusions.....	86
6	Job Creation In The Wind Power Industry – Results	87
6.2	Results of the literature review.....	87

6.3	Results from the statistic and regression analysis	88
6.3.2	Statistics of the wind park development stage	89
6.3.3	Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage	89
6.3.4	Statistics and regressions of the wind park manufacturing stage	90
6.3.5	Statistics and regressions of the wind park operation and maintenance stage	91
6.3.6	Statistics and regressions of the wind park decommissioning stage	92
6.3.7	Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage	93
6.3.8	Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage	94
6.4	A model to estimate job creation	95
6.4.2	Job creation model input	95
6.4.3	Model based estimations	96
6.4.4	Model validation based on interviews	98
6.4.5	Job creation model limitations	99
7	CONCLUSIONS	101
	REFERENCES	104
	ANNEX	118
	Annex A: Collected data on regulations	118
	Annex B: Collected data on job creation	134
	B1: development data	134
	B2: construction data	135
	B3: manufacturing data	140
	B4: operation and maintenance data	142
	B5: decommissioning data	149
	B6: construction phase data	150
	B7: other data	152
	B8: local share data	153

LIST OF PARTNERS

No	Logo	Name	Short Name	Country
1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU	Denmark
3		INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	IIASA	Austria
4		UNIVERSITÄT FÜR BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	Austria
5		UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
6		NAZKA MAPPS BVBA	NAZKA	Belgium
7		KELSO INSTITUTE EUROPE gGMBH	KIE	Germany
8		DEEP BLUE SRL	DEEP BLUE	Italy
9		UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU	Netherlands
10		POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	Italy
11		UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO	UNIPA	Italy
12		APREN-ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE ENERGIAS RENOVAVEIS	APREN	Portugal
13		MULTICONSULT NORGE AS	MCN	Norway
14		EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH	ETH Zürich	Switzerland
15		PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	PSI	Switzerland

16		UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UCL	United Kingdom
----	---	---------------------------	-----	----------------

ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AIA	Environmental Impact Assessment (Avaliação de Impacte Ambiental)
APA	
BGBI	Bundesgesetzblatt (Federal Law Gazette)
CCDR	Regional Coordination and Development Commission
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CEP	Clean Energy for All Europeans Package
CF	Cohesion Fund
DL	Decreto Legge (Decree Law)
DGEG	Directorate General for Energy and Geology (Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia)
DM	Decreto Ministeriale (Ministerial Decree)
DRA	Direccao Regional do Ambiente (Regional Environmental Directorate)
DRAOT	Direccao Regional do Ambiente e do Ordenamento do Territorio (Regional Directorate for the Enviroment and Spatial Planning)
EF	Emloyment factor
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EincA	Procedimento de Avaliacao de Incidencias Ambientais
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EU	European Union
FF55	Fit for 55 Package
FOR	Forskrift (Regulations)
ICN	Instituto de Conservacao de Natureza (Institute of Nature Conserva- tion)
IEMD	Internal Electricity Market Directive
IEMR	Internal Electricity Market Regulation
INCF	Instituto da Conservacao da Natureza e das Florestas (Institute for Na- ture Conservation and Forests)
JTF	Just Transition Fund
JTM	Just Transition Mechanism
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KIE	Kelso Institute Europe Berlin
kW	Kilowatt
L	Legge (Law)
LGBI	Landesgesetzblatt (Provincial Law Gazette)
LIH	Low-income Households
LOV	Lov (Law)
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
MS	Member States
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan

NGEU	NextGenerationEU
NIJOS	Norwegian Institute of Land Inventory
NUTSO	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics level 0
O&M	Operation and maintenance
OPEX	Operating expenses
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PEOT	Planes de Ordenamento do Território (Special Territory Planning Plans)
POAP	Planos de Ordenamento de Areas Protegidas (Protected Area Management Plans)
POOC	Planos de Ordenamento da Orla Costeira (Coastal Management Plans)
PSLF	Public Sector Loan Facility
RE	Renewable Energy
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RESP	Public Service Electricity Network (Rede Elétrica de Serviço Público)
STEP	Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform
TJTP	Territorial Just Transition Plan
TRC	Grid Capacity Reservation Certificate (Titulus de Reserve de Capacidade de rede)
UPAC	Unidade de Producao para Autoconsumo (Production Unit for Self-Consumption)
UU	University Utrecht
WT	Wind turbine(s)

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Typology of wind projects.....	68
Figure 2: Overview of the EU funding instruments relevant to the deployment of wind power across Europe	79
Figure 3: Job sectors and their duration range	88
Figure 4: Direct, indirect and induced EFs (job-years/MW) for a 5 MW offshore wind turbine in the EU.....	97
Figure 5: Total job sector shares for 2, 8 & 12 MW onshore wind turbines in the EU.....	98
Figure 6: Total job sector shares for 2, 8 & 12 MW offshore wind turbines in the EU.....	98

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Federal states' regulation on wind energy zoning in Austria as of November 2023..... 28

Table 2: Wind turbine deployment in Austria as of December 2022 29

Table 3: Limitations of municipal competencies in the Federal EIA-Act since March 2023..... 29

Table 4: Construction requirements for wind turbines in Austria within dedicated wind energy zones as of November 2023 30

Table 5: Construction requirements for wind turbines in Austria outside dedicated wind energy zones as of November 2023 31

Table 6: Distance rules for the construction of wind turbines outside wind energy zones in Austria as of November 2023..... 31

Table 7: Electricity law permit thresholds for wind parks in Austria as of November 2023..... 33

Table 8: Compulsory noise thresholds in Italy as of November 2023 39

Table 9: Electricity Permit Thresholds in Italy as of November 2023 41

Table 10: Rules on Wind Energy Construction Within Protected Areas 44

Table 11: Three modalities of distributing grid capacity reserves certificated to energy producers in Portugal as of November 2023 48

Table 12: Summary of Regulatory Framework..... 58

Table 13: Governance models under RED II and IEMD 66

Table 14: Legal Structures of Energy Communities..... 70

Table 15: Cohesion Data regarding Wind Energy Projects, 2014 to 2020; Refresh Date: 14.09.2023; in EUR mil; Source: European Commission (Cohesion Data)..... 80

Table 16: Significant EF regressions for the construction stage 89

Table 17: Indirect, induced and total EFs for the construction stage. Values provided in job-years/MW..... 90

Table 18: Significant EF regressions for the manufacturing stage 91

Table 19: Indirect, induced & total EFs for the manufacturing stage. Values provided in job-years/MW..... 91

Table 20: Significant EF regression for the O&M stage 92

Table 21: Direct, indirect, induced and total EFs for the O&M stage. Values provided in job-years/MW..... 92

Table 22: Significant EF regression for the decommissioning stage 93

Table 23: Indirect, induced & total EFs for the decommissioning stage. Values provided in job-years/MW..... 93

Table 24: Direct, indirect, induced & total EFs construction phase. Values provided in job-years/MW..... 94

Table 25: Location of the job creation per job sector	95
Table 26: EF model input (range) values (job-years/MW).....	95
Table 27: Total EFs range (job-years/MW) for a 5 MW wind turbine at different locations	97

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document was compiled by the Kelso Institute Europe Berlin (KIE) and the University Utrecht (UU) with the aim to understand the potential impact of local regulations, governance models and financing sources on wind power deployment and the jobs generation potential of the wind power industry for individual regions.

With respect to the regulatory framework of wind power deployment, we analysed the respective laws and regulations of the four pilot countries Austria, Italy, Portugal, and Norway. We organised our results in six chapters: (i) wind energy zones, (ii) environmental impact assessment, (iii) electricity law permit, (iv) building law, (v) natural and cultural heritage and (vi) measures to raise acceptance. Annex A on page 118 provides a table of the analysed laws and regulations for each country.

Regarding the governance framework for wind energy, we map out possible actor constellations focusing on cases from ten EU Member States (MS) and Switzerland. In doing so, we differentiate between (i) 100% citizen-owned projects, (ii) commercial wind project developer with majority citizen shareholding, (iii) commercial wind project developer and minority citizen participation, (iv) commercial (non-energy) actor/SME and citizen project, (v) municipality projects, (vi) municipality and commercial actor projects and (vii) citizen and municipality projects.

Most of the existing financing instruments at EU level were established in 2021 and there is almost no data about their impact in general and their financial support for wind energy in particular. The existing programmes are intended to support economic development or decarbonisation in general and do not refer specifically to wind power deployment. The only exception providing information on the period from 2014 to 2020 are the European Structural and Investment Funds (ERDF & CF). However, this data is (i) incomplete and (ii) concerning regulations were amended for 2021 to 2027, thus not allowing us to draw conclusions on the impact of the existing funding programs. We, therefore, examine the new instruments in terms of their institutional embedding, their financial scope and the eligibility of wind energy projects for funding; only those programs that promote wind energy are considered. In summary, while wind energy projects are eligible for EU funding, the impact

of these funding instruments on wind power deployment in practice remains unclear until said data is available.

Concerning job creation, we conducted a systematic quantitative literature review of 162 unique sources of which 70 contained useful data on job creation. We extracted from these sources job creation quantities for different job creation stages and locations. We followed an employment factor approach to quantify job creation in job-years per installed capacity (job-years/MW). We use the retrieved data to create a model that estimates job creation disaggregated into (i) job types: direct, indirect, and induced and (ii) life cycle stages: development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning. Model outputs were validated using expert knowledge obtained via semi-structured interviews. The developed model comprises the best possible estimation that could be done with publicly available data. The main limitation for achieving a level of detail beyond NUTS0 regions is the general lack of data. More data, especially for decommissioning, could increase model accuracy and enable using smaller locational scales. However, we do not expect that such data will be made available by developers, deployers and manufacturers in the near future.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the objective to contribute to a thorough understanding of factors that influence the acceptance of wind power deployment this report reviews and systematises (i) current regulations governing wind power deployment, (ii) governance models that affect the acceptance towards wind power installations, (iii) financing sources for new projects (both public and private) and their implications for business models, and (iv) the potential for expected job creation of wind energy project.

The focus of our analysis is on WIMBYs partner countries. Following the present first version of this deliverable D2.9 in M12 (four pilot project countries) an updated and extended final deliverable D2.10 will be provided after feedback loops with the pilots in M24 (six remaining WIMBY partner countries).

1.1 Regulatory Framework for Wind Power

The regulatory framework for wind power development is very diverse across Europe: While some regions have introduced strict distance rules governing the construction of wind turbines on land (e.g. Burgenland, Lower Austria, Carinthia, Upper Austria), others rely on more general criteria such as noise regulations that determine minimum distances wind turbines must respect to residential areas (e.g. Italy, Portugal, Norway). Further, differing levels of regulatory density can be perceived in the analysed countries: Austria, due to its federal system, by far poses the highest density of regulations of the analysed countries while the Norwegian doctrine, in general, is dominated by guidelines rather than rules (Eckhoff, 1953), thus offering a rather low density of hard law governing the wind energy sector.

The arguably most outstanding characteristic with regard to acceptance are the competence of municipalities. In Austria (§ 4a para 2, BGBl Nr 697/1993) and Portugal (Art. 4-A Decree Law no. 30-A/2022), a general trend towards weakening the competence of municipalities deciding over where a wind park should be constructed, can be perceived. In Norway the constitutional court in its judgement of 11 October 2021 (*HR-2021-1975-S*, 2021) decided that the construction of a wind park was illegal, taking up another trend. Following the decision, municipalities have regained their veto power

and may prevent the construction of a wind park in their vicinity (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2023). In Italy, municipalities do have the competence to declare and suitable non-suitable zones for wind energy development, however, a government plan is expected to be published soon, defining suitable areas on a national level (Ressa, 2023).

With respect to raising acceptance of wind energy among population, compensation measures between MS vary as well. In Austria, the federal state of Burgenland is the only state charging wind park developers a windfall levy (formulated as a levy for destroying the beauty of the landscape), offering part of the levy revenue to municipalities (LGBI Nr 47/2023). The Italian government recommends that monetary compensation measures by wind park developers should not exceed three percent of the earnings made (DM. 2010). In Portugal, big wind park operators must offer municipalities a monetary (1,500 EUR per MVA of allocated grid connection power; Art. 49 para. 2 of Decree Law no. 15/2022) or qualitative compensation (e.g., the installation of electric vehicle charging stations in the affected municipality; Art. 6 of Decree-Law no. 30-A/2022). In Norway, only recently a resource rent tax which will be automatically adjusted to the profits of the wind park developer has been proposed, to share the monetary benefits with society and raise acceptance (Norwegian Ministry of Finance, 2023).

1.2 Governance Models for Wind Power Projects

Wind energy plays a pivotal role in achieving the EU's decarbonization objectives and ensuring the provision of secure, sustainable, and affordable electricity. To fairly distribute ills and benefits of the decentralized energy production it is crucial to question the dominance of governance models inherited from a predominantly centralised system (Krug et al., 2022). As important as this observation is – as complex its implementation. The democratization of energy governance structures gives rise to a complex mosaic of stakeholder relationships, legal entities, and diverse actors (Heldeweg & Saintier, 2020). Through the implementation of the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package¹, the EU has established a comprehensive framework com-

¹ Eight legislative acts of over 1,000 pages covering governance, renewable energy, energy efficiency, energy performance of buildings, internal electricity market, cooperation of regulators, innovation, etc.

prising of interconnected directives and regulations, shaping both the technical and societal aspects of the transformation. Subject to regular updates to align with the evolving strategy towards a net-zero future, the realization of the targets depends on the effective implementation within the Member States. For the implementation at national and regional level, acceptance of the local population poses a pivotal element.²

Chapter 4 provides an overview of the EU's governance rules for renewable energy sources (RES), laying the foundation for the European green transition at the supranational level. Given the substantial potential for expansion of wind power throughout Europe, we investigate specific forms of implementation that could characterize the future utilization of wind energy in the region. As has been argued by Lowitzsch et al. (2020) factors like demand flexibility, storage solutions, peer-to-peer trading and market interactions between heterogeneous partners on equal footing play a vital role in the socio-technical regime of decentralized energy production. Therefore, we then examine decentralized governance models for (wind) energy projects to provide insights in existing stakeholder combinations. Concluding this chapter is a synthesis that summarizes the potentials and limitations of decentralized governance in the deployment of wind power.

1.3 Financing Resources

Chapter 5 provides an overview of the available EU funding for wind energy projects. An impact analysis is not part of the Chapter due to lack of available data. We anticipate the amount of available data to increase by the time we review, update and extend this deliverable in M24. The chapter on financing resources, therefore, provides an examination of the eligibility of wind projects for funding through the new EU financing instruments. In addition, the chapter describes the institutional embeddedness of the instruments and their financial volumes.

1.4 Job creation relevance and definitions

One of the clear positive impacts of wind power deployment is the job creation. However, there are multiple conceptual ways to understand job creation, different indicators to describe it, and no common model to make an

² Already in 2010, 40% of wind energy projects in Europe were cancelled due to resistance of local populations filing lawsuits (EWEA, 2010)

estimation at the wind park level taking into consideration geographical differences. In this deliverable we provide a common ground of terminology in the introduction, the description of how we constructed a job creation estimation model in section 2.3 and the model and some example estimations in section 6.³

1.4.1 Job types in the wind power industry

In the wind power industry, three distinct job categories are generally recognized: direct, indirect, and induced jobs (IRENA, 2011). Direct jobs pertain to the core activities within the sector, indirect jobs involve roles in the supply chain supporting the wind power industry, and induced jobs arise from increased spending and wealth. Direct jobs in the wind energy sector are directly associated with the previously mentioned job sectors. Indirect jobs, for example, could encompass roles necessary for the production of steel for wind turbines. Notably, existing literature predominantly focuses on direct job creation, with less emphasis on indirect and induced jobs (Bowen, 2016). Solely considering direct job creation may underestimate the actual job creation impact of wind energy (Ram et al., 2022). To provide the most accurate assessment of jobs generated by wind energy, in our model and in this deliverable we incorporate all three job types.

Estimating values for indirect and induced jobs involves utilizing a local job multiplier, which considers additional jobs generated by new job creation (Bartik & Sotherland, 2019). As outlined by Bartik & Sotherland (2019), supplier linkages contribute to additional jobs created on the supplier side, reflecting indirect jobs. This phenomenon occurs due to an increase in employees in the industry. Worker demand refers to the extra expenditure by new employees, resulting in further job creation, and can be regarded as induced jobs (e.g. jobs created at the company offering temporary housing to the builders of a wind park). Inclusion of all job types provides a more comprehensive and accurate representation of the overall job creation impact of wind energy.

³ The full methodological and results detail can be found in the master thesis of Sam Klap (UU) which is a document that can be only accessed through the UU library. The objective is to derive an open access journal paper from that master thesis until M18, which would allow to disclose the full detail of the performed research.

1.4.2 Jobs sectors in the wind power industry

According to Llera et al. (2013), the lifecycle of renewable energy technologies typically comprises five stages. The initial stage involves research, project design, and development. The second stage refers to the manufacturing of the renewable energy technology, specifically wind turbines in this context. The third stage encompasses the transport, installation, and commissioning of the wind farm, while the fourth stage pertains to the operation and maintenance of wind parks. The final stage involves the renovation or decommissioning of the wind turbines. IRENA (2011) aligns with this perspective, highlighting processing of raw materials, manufacturing, project design and management, installation and/or construction, operation and maintenance, and eventual decommissioning as distinct jobs related to wind energy. WIMBY adopts these five stages as job sectors, namely: development, manufacturing, construction, operation, and maintenance (O&M), and decommissioning.

Understanding the duration of each job sector is crucial for accurately quantifying job creation. Construction and decommissioning are typically viewed as temporary jobs, while planning, manufacturing, and O&M are considered permanent jobs (Llera et al., 2013). This distinction is supported by Hanna et al., (2022), who also categorize O&M as a permanent job. While manufacturing a single turbine may be seen as temporary, the expected growth in the number of wind turbines needed suggests a more long term perspective (Hanna et al., 2022).

Another aspect of job creation is its locality—whether jobs are created locally, nationally, or internationally. Hanna et al., (2022) note that manufacturing jobs can emerge at all three levels, depending on the presence of wind turbine manufacturing organizations. Other jobs, such as those in development, construction, O&M, and decommissioning, are more likely to be created locally or nationally.

1.4.3 Quantification approach: Employment factor

There are two primary methods for assessing job creation in renewable energy: the Input-Output model (IO) and the Employment Factor approach (EF) (Breitschopf et al., 2013). The IO model calculates job creation based on a sector's output and employment, encompassing both direct and indirect

job effects (Fragkos & Paroussos, 2018). However, it doesn't explicitly distinguish the proportion of direct and indirect jobs in the total job creation (direct, indirect, and induced). On the other hand, the EF approach evaluates job creation by the number of jobs associated with installed capacity (Fragkos and Paroussos, 2018). It estimates the employees required per job sector for a wind park with a specific capacity, often focusing on direct job creation. Literature also shows that the EF approach can incorporate indirect and induced jobs, as seen in Simas & Pacca (2014). Considering that EF is also recognized by its simplicity and transparency (Fragkos and Paroussos, 2018) we have decided to use EF for job quantification in WIMBY.

Typically, the EF approach expresses job creation as jobs/MW (jobs per MW total installed capacity) or job-years/MW (job years per MW installed capacity). However, literature occasionally presents values per Gigawatt hour (GWh), leading to quantifications in jobs/GWh or job-years/GWh, where GWh represents produced energy. The last approach requires additional assumptions about operations hours, additional information on local wind conditions and is easier to perform ex post. Therefore, the indicator chosen for WIMBY is jobs/MW.

2. METHODOLOGY

Nota bene: The legal assessment of this first version of Deliverable 2.9 focuses on the WIMBY partner countries with pilot projects (Austria, Portugal, Norway, and Italy) and will be extended to all partner countries in the final version of Deliverable 2.9 to be submitted in month 24.

2.1 Gathering data on regulations to wind energy development

Based on a document analysis of all types of regulations relevant for wind power deployment with a focus on those issues that impact acceptance, our approach comprises of three steps: (i) To determine EU/EU-MS state of legal affairs on wind power deployment: What does the existing law say? (ii) To gather empirical data about how share-/stakeholder constellations reflect the regulatory framework in practice: What kind of participatory mechanisms occur that potentially can increase acceptance? (iii) To enhance acceptance for wind power deployment: What should the law say? In terms of methodology this approach entails

- (i) Descriptive analysis of ‘lege lata’ involving legal interpretation (grammatical, teleological, systematic, historical), legal qualification (e.g., legal sources/legal traditions) and legal fact finding.
- (ii) Empirical legal studies applying methods of socio-empirical studies (esp. qualitative) and analysing real life cases.
- (iii) Prescriptive analysis of ‘lege ferenda’ involving legal comparison, normative analysis (leading values/principles) to develop recommendations.

With respect to legal information on renewable energy (RE) including wind energy policy in the respective WIMBY partner countries, we found several databases that served our desk-based research: Polizero (Panos et al., 2021) offers an overview of RE policies for 11 EU Member States (AT, DK, FI, FR, DE, GR, IR, IT, PT, ES, SE) and 3 Non-EU MS (CH, and the UK); RES Legal (2018), a project finalised at end of 2018, compared RE policy for the EU27 (incl. CH, NO, UK and TR); RES Simplify (2023), an EU-funded research project, published its final study in 2023, providing a comprehensive overview of barriers and good practices with respect to RE permitting procedures identified in the EU27 (incl. NO and IC).

To retrieve the most recent information on wind energy related policies and regulations, we use the legal databases of the respective countries and the plain regulatory text. Screening through the regulations, we focussed on consolidated versions (final version of a legal text, including all previous amendments) which were in force at the time of our search request. In addition, we retrieved information from official government websites of the respective countries, peer-reviewed journals, reports, and books.

The Legal Information System of the Republic of Austria (www.ris.gv.at) is a legal database providing information on Austrian law on federal and state level. Screening through the legal database using the key term *windkraft** (wind power), we retrieved 51 results with respect to federal law and 70 results with respect to state law (last search conducted on 10 November 2023). Drawing on the results, we identified 21 laws and regulations which were the basis for the research conducted in section 3.1.

The Italian government website Normattiva (www.normattiva.it) contains laws and regulations of Italian state, regional and provincial law. Screening through the legal database using the key term *energia eolica* (wind energy), we retrieved 34 results with respect to federal law and 26 results with respect to state law (last search conducted on 15 November 2023). Screening through the results, we identified 11 federal laws and regulations which were the basis for the research conducted in section 3.2.

The Legal Information System of Portugal, the Diário de República (www.diariodarepublica.pt), is a legal database providing information on Portuguese law, including the autonomous regions (Azores and Madeira). Screening through the legal databases using the key term *energia eólica** (wind energy), we retrieved 29 results with respect to federal law and four results with respect to the law of the autonomous regions (last search conducted on 28 November 2023). Screening through the results, we identified eight federal laws and regulations which were the basis for the research conducted in section 3.3.

The Legal Information System of Norway, Lovdata (www.lovdata.no), established by the Ministry of Justice and the Faculty of Law in Oslo, aims to create, maintain and operate systems for legal information. Screening through the legal database using the key term *vindkraft** (wind power), we retrieved 55 results with respect to federal law (last search conducted on 1 December

2023). Screening through results, we identified 12 laws and regulations which were the basis for the research conducted in section 3.4.

2.2 Evaluation of Wind Energy Governance and Financing Sources

To investigate wind energy governance in the EU, we conducted a multi-level governance analysis. The following questions guided the three layers of analysis: (i) What is the EU framework outlining wind power deployment? Concentrating on the emphasis of an inclusive energy transition for all Europeans, layer (ii) examines citizen co-investment and financial participation – How can EU citizens actively engage in wind energy? In layer (iii) an exploration of stakeholder constellations concludes the chapter, examining the question what the practical implications of the legal frameworks are and how they are implemented by European citizens.

Regarding both governance and financing, we conducted a document analysis at EU level providing the framework in which MS policies navigate. This involved scrutinizing EU legal documents and open-access information provided by official EU bodies, specifically focusing on their impact on the deployment of wind power.

Building on insights gained from the EU governance, a screening of scientific literature on the impacts of financial participation in wind energy production was carried out. As a third part, a systematic collection of case studies was conducted to offer empirical evidence and insights into the practical implementation of participatory wind energy projects. Given the lack of a comprehensive database on community energy projects, we opted to choose representative cases and organize them into stakeholder clusters. We considered the current status of the EU Repository on Energy Communities as of December 2023, encompassing 64 energy communities ((European Commission, 2023e) as well as the case study collection provided in the book *Energy Transitions – Financing Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewables* (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

2.3 Determining job creation estimates

2.3.1 Job creation literature review

A systematic quantitative literature review, following the methodology outlined by Pickering and Byrne (Pickering & Byrne, 2014), was conducted to collect quantitative data on job creation in the wind power industry. The literature selection process comprised two phases. In the first phase, primary, secondary, and tertiary keywords were identified for retrieving relevant literature. Primary keywords included jobs, job creation, employment, employment creation, and employment factor. Secondary keywords focused on wind energy, wind power, and wind turbines, while tertiary keywords were specific to Europe and the EU. A Python script utilizing the Scopus Application Programming Interface (API) was employed for literature collection, generating bibliographies and abstracts from the database. To broaden the scope, the script was run separately on primary and secondary keywords to retrieve relevant literature beyond Europe. We expected that the later would contribute to increase the amount of data points to be retrieved for individual job types and stages.

The second phase involved reviewing and categorizing references based on relevance to the research questions. Abstracts were scrutinized, and references were considered pertinent if they provided information or data directly related to job creation in the wind power sector. Articles inaccessible to the author or not in English or Dutch were excluded. Included references underwent a full reading, and pertinent quantitative data on job creation were documented and organized in numerical tables.

In addition to scientific literature, grey literature was utilized to supplement data. The use of grey literature addressed data gaps and offered supplementary insights to determine an EF.

2.3.2 Semi-structured interviews about job creation

In addition to scientific literature, interviews were undertaken to augment data collection and enhance comprehension of wind energy job creation. The primary objectives of these interviews were to verify the accuracy of literature-retrieved data, gather specific quantitative insights into job creation, and identify factors influencing employment. Given the challenge of providing precise EF values, the interviews adopted a semi-structured approach. This format facilitated the inclusion of additional questions that could provide indications for an EF or yield data for deriving ones. The semi-structured interviews were conducted with organizations affiliated with

WIMBY, active participants in the wind power sector, offering valuable practical data. To maintain confidentiality, both interviewees and organizations were anonymized.

In total five interviews were conducted. Interviewee A, a self-employed consultant, specializes in small to large-scale wind energy parks, primarily engaged during the construction stage. Interviewee B, a sustainable energy manager at a major energy provider, contributes to wind project development. Interviewees C and D, both employed by the same large energy provider, hold roles as a renewable global project portfolio manager and a wind park decommissioning expert, respectively. Interviewee E is a representative of an European wind energy lobby institution.

2.3.3 Data analysis of job creation data from literature

The collected data underwent a systematic examination. Initially, all data were standardized to a common unit, with the prevalent unit of job-years/MW adopted for quantifying job creation, aligning with most EFs in the literature. This streamlined the conversion process between different units. The transformation from jobs/GWh to jobs/MW was contingent on the wind park's capacity factor and lifetime provided in the individual references. Values initially presented in jobs/MW were further converted to job-years/MW, with normalization achieved by multiplying by the technology's lifetime or an assigned typical duration if the literature lacked specific information.

The analysis of collected data employed a descriptive approach, utilizing statistical techniques such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, frequency distribution, and correlation (Siedlecki, 2020). Mean, median, and mode values were determined and utilized when multiple data points pertained to the same wind park. Of particular interest were the relationships among variables (e.g. turbine size, park size, whether the turbines are off-shore or on-shore, country it is located) influencing EFs identified in the literature. These relationships were explored through a multiple linear regression analysis, employing the general equation (1) adapted from Uyanik & Güler (2013).

$$\gamma = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \dots + \beta_nx_n + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Here, γ represents the dependent variable (EF in different job sectors), β_i denotes parameters, x_i signifies independent variables influencing the EF, and ε stands for error. Parameter values corresponding to independent variables

were derived using ANOVA statistics. A 5% significance level was applied to assess the regressions, considering a significance level at or below 5% indicative of likely determination of the dependent variable by the independent variables. This threshold aligns with common practice and minimizes the risk of deeming a significant regression as not determining the dependent variable (Fang & Yang, 2019).

2.3.4 Job creation model development

During this phase, a comprehensive model was formulated to quantify job creation across diverse wind parks, accounting for factors such as the number of turbines, turbine capacity, and whether they are onshore or offshore. The foundation of this model lies in the significant regressions identified for various job sectors in the preceding step. The holistic job creation function incorporates all the regressions of EFs for distinct job sectors, consolidating them into a unified job creation EF.

The total job creation EF (expressed in job-years/MW) is the summation of EFs from the development (*dv*), manufacturing (*m*), construction (*c*), operation and maintenance (*o&m*), and decommissioning (*dc*) job sectors. To determine total job creation for a specific wind park, the total EF is multiplied by the installed MW (see equation 2).

$$job\ creation = (EF_{dv} + EF_m + EF_c + EF_{o\&m} + EF_{dc}) \times MW \quad (2)$$

Here *EF* is the employment factor (job-years/MW) and the subscripts *dv*, *m*, *c*, *o&m* and *dc* represent the development, manufacturing, construction, operation and maintenance and decommissioning job sector, respectively.

To operationalize this job creation function, an Excel-based model was developed using all available data collected in step one. Ideally, the model would have been constructed based on 80% of the acquired data for subsequent validation against the remaining 20%. However, due to limited data availability, the entire dataset was utilized as model input. Consequently, model validation relies on comparing its results with alternative methods and discerning trends or relationships identified during the interviews.

3. REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR WIND POWER

This section provides an overview of the regulatory framework for wind power deployment in Austria, Portugal, Norway, and Italy. An overview of the national legislations including the respective link can be found in Annex A on page 118. This assessment will be extended to all partner countries in the final version of Deliverable 2.9 to be submitted in month 24.

3.1 Austria

Austria is a federal state with three levels of government: (i) the national level; (ii) nine federal states; and (iii) 2,100 municipalities (OECD, 2017).

3.1.1 Wind Energy Zones

Wind Energy Within Dedicated Zones

The nine federal states of Austria have the competence to define suitable and/or unsuitable areas for wind energy exploitation through so called state development concepts (*Landesentwicklungsprogramme*). So far, four states passed specific regulations and programmes on wind energy zoning: Burgenland (LGBl Nr 59/2019), Lower Austria (LRNI 2014049), Carinthia (LGBl Nr 46/2016), Styria (LGBl Nr 72/2013), Upper Austria (Land Oberösterreich, 2017) and Salzburg (Land Salzburg, 2022). Table 1 provides an overview of regulation at the level of federal states in Austria as of November 2023.

Table 1: Federal states' regulation on wind energy zoning in Austria as of November 2023

DEDICATED AREAS	Burgenland	Lower Austria	Carinthia	Styria	Upper Austria	Salzburg
special area	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
suitability zone	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
priority zone	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES
exclusion zone	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO
map indicating areas / zones	YES	YES	NO*	YES	YES	YES

* only abstract criteria / Source: Own elaboration.

In the states of Salzburg, Tyrol and Vorarlberg, no wind turbines are deployed as of November 2023 with the latter two states not having passed wind energy zoning plans yet. In December 2022, shortly after the state of Salzburg announced its first wind park project (salzburg.orf.at, 2022) it also published a Wind Energy Zoning Programme (Land Salzburg, 2022) containing suitability zones for wind energy in various locations.

The state of Upper Austria, despite its land surface of almost 20,000 km², only counts 31 wind turbines. Its wind energy zoning map contains exclusion

zones but does not define suitable or preferential areas for wind energy deployment. The construction of wind parks in Upper Austria on building land is only permitted if its nominal capacity lies below five kW; the construction on green land is prohibited, leaving wind park operators limited scope for action.

The state of Carinthia with a land surface of almost 10,000 km² merely counts ten wind turbines of which the last eight (ots.at, 2023) became operational in September 2023. The Carinthian wind energy zoning regulation contains strict visibility criteria indicating suitable areas for wind energy construction at an abstract level, without offering a map. In light of the national aim to accelerate the energy transition, the government of Carinthia has announced to facilitate the expansion of wind energy, among others by repealing the strict visibility criteria in the near future (kaernten.orf.at, 2023). Table 2 provides an overview of wind turbines deployed in Austria as of December 2022 (IG Windkraft, 2023).

Table 2: Wind turbine deployment in Austria as of December 2022

	AT11	AT12	AT13	AT21	AT22	AT31	AT32	AT33	AT34
WTs	445	762	9	10	114	31	0	0	0

All_Burgenland | A12_Lower Austria | A13_Vienna | A21_Carinthia | A22_Styria | A31_Upper Austria | A32_Salzburg | A33_Tyrol | A34_Vorarlberg
Source: IG Windkraft

Paragraph 4a of the Federal Environmental Impact Assessment Act or EIA-Act (BGBl Nr 697/1993) facilitates the expansion of wind energy; it has been introduced in March 2023. So far, the construction of wind energy required a dedicated area for wind energy manifested both, in the regional planning law of the federal states and the provincial planning law of the municipalities. The above amendment limited the competencies of municipalities as summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Limitations of municipal competencies in the Federal EIA-Act since March 2023

Amendment of the Federal EIA-Act	
If the state has defined dedicated areas for wind energy development	Construction within dedicated area According to §4a para 2, the municipalities have no veto-power.
	Construction outside dedicated area According to §4a para 2, the municipalities have no veto-power; however, construction only possible if the state permits the construction outside of its dedicated areas as well.
If the state has not defined dedicated ar-	- According to §4a para 3, the construction of wind farms is permitted if the selected site does not contradict EU law, public interests, and the interests of third parties. In this case, however, wind park operators need the approval of the municipality (veto-power).

measures for wind energy development

Source: Own elaboration.

Four federal states foresee special requirements that must be met within dedicated wind energy zones: The states of Lower Austria and Upper Austria require the minimum average wind power density at a height of 130m above the ground to reach at least 220 W/m²; the states of Burgenland and Styria require a minimum total capacity of the wind turbines to be 15 MW (the state of Styria only requires this limit to be reached in priority zones, not in suitability zones as well). The state of Upper Austria requires a minimum of three wind turbines to be constructed within a radius of one km. In addition, the state of Burgenland has very detailed rules on rotor diameter, blade tip height, nature and emission protection that must be met by developers who construct a wind park in its suitability zones. Table 4 summarises the requirements for the construction of wind turbines within dedicated wind energy zones in Austria as of November 2023.

Table 4: Construction requirements for wind turbines in Austria within dedicated wind energy zones as of November 2023

	Burgenland	Lower Austria	Styria	Upper Austria
min nominal capacity of WT	N/A	N/A	≥ 0.5MW (priority/suitability zones)	> 0.5 MW
min total capacity of WTs	> 15 MW	N/A	≥ 15 MW (only in priority zones)	N/A
min number of WTs	N/A	N/A	N/A	≥ 3 WTs (within 1 km radius)
min average wind power density	N/A	≥ 220 W/m ² (130m above ground)	N/A	≥ 220 W/m ² (130 m above ground)
Rotor diameter	130 – 175 m	N/A	N/A	N/A
Blade tip height	200 – 250 m	N/A	N/A	N/A
Rotor distance to ground	60 – 80 m	N/A	N/A	N/A
Nature protection	birds and bats, soil	N/A	N/A	N/A
Emission protection	light, ice, noise	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Own elaboration.

Wind Energy Outside Dedicated Areas

In the states of Burgenland (LGBl Nr 49/2019) and Carinthia (LGBl Nr 59/2921), the construction of wind parks outside dedicated areas is prohibited. In the states of Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Salzburg, it is permitted, however, only under special conditions: in Lower Austria (LGBl Nr 3/2015) the nominal capacity of the wind park must not exceed a bottleneck operation of 20 kW,

in Upper Austria (LGBI Nr 114/1993) the nominal capacity of the wind turbine in dedicated construction zones must not exceed the nominal capacity of five kW, in Salzburg (LGBI Nr 30/2009) the limit is 500 kW. In the state of Lower Austria, the construction of wind turbines on dedicated green zones is prohibited. Table 5 provides an overview of the requirements for the construction of wind turbines outside dedicated wind energy zones in Austria as of November 2023.

Table 5: Construction requirements for wind turbines in Austria outside dedicated wind energy zones as of November 2023

OUTSIDE OF DEDICATED AREAS	Burg.	Lowe Aus.	Carin.	Styria	Upper Aus.	Salzburg
WTs allowed outside	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES (not on green zone)	YES
max nominal/installed capacity of WT	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	< 5 kW nominal capacity (on construction zone)	< 500 kW installed capacity
max nominal capacity of wind park	N/A	< 20 kW bottleneck operation	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
min average power density of the wind	N/A	N/A	N/A	≥ 180 W per m2 (100 m above ground)	N/A	N/A

Source: Own elaboration.

Certain states rule that turbines within dedicated wind energy zones must respect distance rules. They are usually enshrined either in the regional planning laws (Burgenland: LGBI Nr 49/2019; Lower Austria: LGBI Nr 3/2015), the regional wind energy zoning plans (Carinthia: LGBI Nr 46/2016; Styria: LGBI Nr 72/2013) or the respective electricity codes (Upper Austria: LGBI Nr 1/2006). Table 6 provides an overview of the distance rules for the construction of wind turbines applicable outside dedicated wind energy zones in Austria as of November 2023.

Table 6: Distance rules for the construction of wind turbines outside wind energy zones in Austria as of November 2023

DISTANCE RULES	Burg.	Lower Au.	Carinthia	Styria	Upper Austria
(dedicated) residential or construction area	1200 m	1200 m	1500 m	1000 m	100 m (up to 30 kW) 500m (30 kW – 0.5 MW) 1000m (above 0.5 MW)
special building	N/A	1200 m	N/A	N/A	N/A
buildings in green land	N/A	750 m	N/A	700 m	100 m (up to 30 kW) 500m (30 kW – 0.5 MW) 1000m (above 0.5 MW)
dedicated residential buildings outside local community	2000 m	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
safety distance to roads and paths	yes	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
visibility rules	N/A	N/A	Yes	N/A	N/A

Source: Own elaboration.

Carinthia introduced complicated visibility rules for wind turbines with a hub height of more than 80 m: The surface area of a permanently inhabited settlement area within a radius of 10 km around a wind turbine from where it is visible must – except in special cases – not exceed 7 km²; mountains blocking the sight must be respected in the calculations.

3.1.2 Environmental Impact Assessment

The European EIA-Directive has been transposed in Austria with the EIA-Act (BGBl Nr 697/1993, *Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfungs-Gesetz, UVP-G*). EIA proceedings are concentrated at the federal level: The affected substantive laws at the state level such as the Electricity Law Codes, the Building Law Codes, the Nature Conservation Law Acts, as well as the Aviation Act on the federal level are automatically dealt with in the decision-making process of the EIA. With the state government being the responsible authority for conducting the EIA (§ 39 *ibid.*) Austria offers a one-stop-shop, simplifying the authorisation process for projects. Below the EIA thresholds, installations must be approved in individual procedures. Annex 1 to the EIA-Act lists 88 types of projects, including wind park projects, for which an EIA is mandatory if they are expected to have a substantially adverse impact on the environment.

If the total electrical output of a wind park does not exceed 30 MW or if the wind park does not count more than 20 converters (each with a nominal output of at least 0.5 MW), a simplified environmental impact assessment (Simplified EIA) suffices. In alpine regions (above an altitude of 1,000 m), the Simplified EIA must be conducted if the energy produced by the wind farm does not exceed a total electrical output of at least 15 MW or if the wind park does not have more than 10 converters (each with a nominal output of at least 0.5 MW). In areas that require special protection (e.g. areas that are vital for the protection of birds according to the European Bird Directive or flora, fauna, and habitat according to the European Habitat Directive), an individual case assessment must be conducted to decide whether a simplified EIA may be applied.

3.1.3 Electricity Law Permit

Below the EIA thresholds (see 3.1.2) the acquisition of an electricity law permit may be required. Several Austrian states require wind park operators to acquire an electricity permit according to the regional Electricity Law Codes

(Elektrizitätswesengesetz) if the bottleneck output of an electricity generating plant exceeds a certain limit (usually between 200 – 500 kW). Carinthia (LGBl Nr 10/2012) and Upper Austria (LGBl Nr 1/2006) have the strictest threshold, setting them at five kW. Several federal states offer the possibility of a simplified procedure which usually requires the public authority to act in an accelerated manner and does not foresee an oral proceeding. Other federal states only require a notification for plants if they do not exceed a special threshold (usually between 50 – 500 kW). Table 7 provides an overview of the requirements for electricity law permits for wind parks in Austria as of November 2023.

Table 7: Electricity law permit thresholds for wind parks in Austria as of November 2023

	AT11	AT12	AT13	AT21	AT22	AT31	AT32	AT33	AT34
no approval needed if bottleneck output of plant max	500 kW	200 kW	N/A	5 kW	500 kW	5 kW	500 kW	250 kW	100 kW
simplified procedure if bottleneck output of plants max	N/A	500 kW	250 kW	500 kW	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	500 kW
notification needed if bottleneck output of plant more than	50 kW	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	150 kW	50 kW	N/A
notification needed if bottleneck output of plant max	500 kW	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	500 kW	250 kW	N/A

AT1_Burgenland | AT12_Lower Austria | AT13_Vienna | AT21_Carinthia | AT22_Styria | AT31_Upper Austria | AT32_Salzburg | AT33_Tyrol | AT34_Vorarlberg
 Source: Own elaboration.

The relevant Electricity Law Codes for each state are the following: Burgenland (LGBl Nr 59/2006), Lower Austria (LGBl 7800-0), Vienna (LGBl Nr 46/2005), Carinthia (LGBl Nr 10/2012), Styria (LGBl Nr 70/2005), Upper Austria (LGBl Nr 1/2006), Salzburg (LGBl Nr 75/1999), Tyrol (LGBl Nr 134/2011 and Vorarlberg (LGBl Nr 52/2001).

3.1.4 Building Law

General Considerations

Below the EIA thresholds (see 3.1.2), the acquisition of a separate building law permit may be required. The states of Burgenland, Lower Austria, Carinthia, and Upper Austria address the construction of wind parks directly; according to the respective Building Law Codes, wind park operators only need a construction permit if the energy installation does not need to apply for an electricity permit; this typically applies only to micro wind turbines. Regarding the states of Vienna, Styria, Salzburg, Tyrol and Vorarlberg, the respective Build Law Codes do not address wind turbines directly. They contain general

requirements such as the protection of the urban and the natural landscape as well as the reduction of sound and other nuisances to levels that do not unreasonably bother neighbours and other people connected to the project site.

The relevant Building Law Codes for each state are the following: Burgenland (LGBl Nr 10/1998), Lower Austria (LGBl Nr 1/2015), Vienna (LGBl Nr 11/1930), Carinthia (LGBl Nr 62/1996), Styria (LGBl Nr 59/1995), Upper Austria (LGBl Nr 66/1994), Salzburg (LGBl Nr 1/2016), Tyrol (LGBl Nr 44/2022) and Vorarlberg (LGBl Nr 52/2001).

Aviation Law Considerations

The national aviation security act (BGBl Nr 253/1957) defines various civil and military aviation security zones. The civil aviation security zones are indicated on an interactive map⁴, whereas the military security zones have not been published online (bmk.gv.at, 2023). Within and outside these security zones, the construction of objects requires a permit (Art. 92 *ibid.*) if the obstacle exceeds certain size limits. Outside security zones, the construction of objects with a minimum height of 100 m requires a permit; if the object is constructed on an elevation with 100 m, the height limit is reduced to 30 m. Within security zones, all constructions above the ground, trees, cranes, antennas and similar are defined as obstacles and need a permit.

3.1.5 Nature and Cultural Heritage Law

Below the EIA thresholds (see 3.1.2), finally, a nature law permit may be required. In principle, the construction of a wind park within a nature protection park is possible, as long as the general requirements of nature protection are fulfilled. These typically include the need to protect the value of the landscape and to keep the balance of nature. Further, all Nature Law Codes have implemented the protection requirements drawn out in the Habitats Directive (EU) 92/43/EEC and the Birds Directive (EU) 2009/147/EC. However, several states have introduced stricter criteria with respect to the construction of wind farms in such areas.

The Nature Conservation Act (LGBl Nr 120/2001) of the state of Upper Austria explicitly mentions wind energy projects and requires that the construction of wind turbines with a height of more than 30 m requires a nature law per-

⁴ <https://maps.austrocontrol.at/mapstore/#/viewer/openlayers/121>.

mit and with a height of more than 10 m a notification. The Biosphere Conservation Act (LGBl Nr 65/2022) of the state of Styria explicitly states that the construction of wind turbines in the core zones of its biosphere parks is impossible, while a construction outside the core zones is possible as long as it does not significantly impair the value of the park, without explaining how this negative impact should be measured. The Wind Energy Zoning Plan (LGBl Nr 46/2005) of the state of Carinthia explicitly rules that the construction of wind turbines in nature and biosphere parks, in nature protection zones, in landscape protection zones, in nature parks, in European protection zones, in Natura-2000 zones and in special ecological sites is prohibited.

The relevant Nature Law Codes for each state are the following: Burgenland (LGBl Nr 27/1991), Lower Austria (LGBl 5500-0), Vienna (LGBl Nr 45/1998), Carinthia (LGBl Nr 79/2002), Styria (LGBl Nr 71/2017 and LGBl Nr 65/2022), Upper Austria (LGBl Nr 129/2001), Salzburg (LGBl Nr 73/1999), Tyrol (LGBl Nr 80/2020) and Vorarlberg (LGBl Nr 59/2003).

3.1.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance

In 2023, the state of Burgenland introduced a regulation (LGBl Nr 47/2023) that charges a levy on wind energy plants as compensation for the damage caused by wind turbines on the landscape. 50 percent of the levy revenue goes to the state and another 50 percent to the municipality on whose territory the wind park is being constructed. The amount of the levy must not exceed 3,000 EUR per megawatt. For wind turbines that were legally approved and completed before the Regulation entered into force, the annual levy is progressive starting with the first year of tax liability: in the first year, 800 EUR per MW; in the second year, 1,350 EUR per MW; in the third year 1,900 EUR per MW; in the fourth year 2,450 EUR per MW; in the fifth year 3,000 EUR per MW. The Regulation expires if the tariff support in accordance with the Green Electricity Act 2012, falls below 6.8 cents per MW for wind turbines.

3.2 Italy

Italy has four levels of government: (i) national; (ii) regional, with 19 regions and two autonomous provinces with regional powers; (iii) provincial, with 110 provinces, out of which ten acquired the status of metropolitan city in 2015; and (iv) local, with 8,047 municipalities. Although a unitary country, its land-use planning system follows a model generally observed in federal coun-

tries, with regional laws and regulations as the main source of legal provisions outlining the planning process. However, despite a high degree of regional autonomy, actual planning systems are similar across the country (OECD, 2017).

3.2.1 Wind Energy Zones

Onshore Wind Energy Within Dedicated Zones

The 21 regions of Italy constitute the first level of territorial subdivision of the Republic. According to a Ministerial Decree of 10 September 2010, they have the competence to define suitable and unsuitable areas for wind energy exploitation. According to a 2021 report of the GSE (Gestore dei Servizi Energetici, 2021), 13 regions have identified unsuitable areas for the development of wind energy and similar projects: Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Umbria, Marche, Abruzzo, Molise, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Sicily and Sardinia.

Transposing the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II, 2018) into national law, the Decree Law no. 199 of 8 November 2021 (DL 199/2021) foresees that the Minister of Ecological Transition in agreement with the Minister of Culture, and the Minister of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies have 18 months to adopt homogenous principles and criteria within the so-called Unified Conference that would help to identify suitable areas for wind energy development (Art. 20 *ibid.*). DL 199/2021 already offers a rough direction and considers the following areas to be suited for the production of renewable energy (Art. 20 para. 8 *ibid.*): sites where systems from the same source are already installed, possibly combined with storage system; quarries and mines that are closed, not recovered or abandoned; sites and plants available to the public railway and motorway companies. Further, the buffer distance wind turbines have to maintain around protected areas has been reduced from 7 km to 3 km (Art. 20 *ibid.*).

A first draft version of the criteria the Unified Conference is about to set up has been made public in July 2023 (Ressa, 2023). It expands the criteria enshrined in DL 199/2021. For example, property owned by the Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Justice and judicial offices must also be considered as suitable for RE production. Further, the Unified Conference aims to divide 80 GW of renewable energy capacity among the regions. Until 2030, the top three producers of renewable energy should be Sicily (10.3 GW); Lombardy (8.6

GW) and Puglia (7.2 GW); the region with the lowest burden is Valle d'Aosta (0.5 GW).

Offshore Wind Energy Within Dedicated Zones

With respect to offshore wind energy, Italy has not set up a zoning plan yet. However, the revised TEN-E Regulation (EU) 2022/869 (European Parliament & Council, 2022a) introduces key provisions to coordinate offshore wind energy development and grid planning in Europe. Together with the European Commission, Member States with access to the sea are asked to define and agree on the amount of offshore wind energy to be deployed within each sea basin by 2050, with intermediate steps in 2030 and 2040. In January 2023, Italy adopted two non-binding agreements together Greece, Spain, France, Malta, Croatia and Slovenia where the countries commit to connect up to 4 GW in the priority offshore grid corridors called "South and West Offshore Grids" (European Union, 2023c) and 4.5 GW in the priority offshore grid corridor called "South and East Offshore Grids" (European Union, 2023b) to the national grid by 2030.

Wind Energy Outside Dedicated Zones

Since the regulatory framework for dedicated zones (see above) is still pending, Ministerial Decree of 10 September 2010 (DM 2010) is central for onshore wind energy planning in Italy. It aims to ensure an efficient coordination between the state, the regions, and the local authorities and to enable a jointly coordinated development and monitoring of environmental and landscape plans in the public interest. The Decree has been drafted by the Minister of Economic Development, the Minister of Environment and the Protection of the Territory and the Sea and the Minister for Heritage and Culture and consists of five attachments focussing on the production of onshore wind energy:

- The general attachment (divided into two parts) offers a general guideline for Single Authorisation Procedures stipulating; that it is only the Regions and autonomous Provinces which can impose limitations and prohibitions in the field of electricity production.
- The first attachment (paragraph 13.2) contains an indicative list of nineteen (19) elements, naming all procedures that must be conducted and permits that must be acquired within the Single Authorisation Procedure.

- The second attachment (paragraphs 14.15 and 16.5) names the criteria for the possible establishment of compensatory measures in favour of the Regions and Autonomous Provinces.
- The third attachment (paragraph 17) sets out the criteria for the identification of unsuitable areas for the construction of wind power plants.
- The fourth attachment (paragraphs 14.9, 16.3 and 16.5) offers a guideline for the construction of onshore wind turbines with respect to the conservation of the landscape and the environment.

DM 2010 applies to wind power plants with a power capacity of more than 60 kW that should comply with the guidelines set out in annex four *ibid.* Annex four is divided into nine chapters, governing, above all, the impact of wind farms on flora, fauna, and ecosystems; its sound and electromagnetic interference; or its specific impacts on special locations. Although technically being merely a guideline (i.e., non-legally binding), in practice wind park developers will not be able to obtain an EIA without adhering to these guidelines.

According to DM 2010, the minimum distance of each wind turbine from residential areas should be at least 200 m or six times the height of the wind turbine (Annex 4 *ibid.*). To assess the visual impact, areas protected by Decree Law no. 42 of 22 January 2004 (DL 42/2004) within a distance of fifty times the height of the closest wind turbine should be photographically explored and the visual impact of the new turbines measured (Annex 4 *ibid.*). The decree offers several measures to minimize the visual impact. For example, could wind turbines be constructed close to existing large infrastructures such as power lines, highways, or industrial settlements. Further, a minimum distance of 5–7 times the diameter length between the wind turbines should be respected (Annex 4 *ibid.*).

With respect to noise, DM 2010 proposes wind park developers to carry out an acoustic measurement to verify the compliance with the limits indicated in the Prime Ministerial Decree of 14 November 1997 (DPCM 1997) and the compliance with the provisions on municipal zoning plans for acoustic noise pursuant to Law no. 447 of 26 October 1995 (L 447/1995, annex 4). In this respect DPCM 1997 differentiates various territory types that require different intensities of noise protection:

- Class I areas enjoy the highest level of protection (areas particularly protected); they include among others, hospitals, schools, rural residential areas, and public parks;
- Class II areas enjoy the second highest level of protection (areas mainly residential); they have a low population density and low presence of commercial or industrial activities;
- Class III areas enjoy the third highest level of protection (mixed areas); they define themselves through a medium-high population density and a high presence of commercial activities.

According to Law no. 447 of 16 October 1995 (L 447/1995), emission limit values are the maximum value of noise that can be emitted by a sound source, measured in the proximity to the source itself. Absolute limit values are determined with reference to the equivalent level of environmental noise; quality values are the noise values to be achieved in the short, medium and long term with the technologies and rehabilitation methods available, to achieve the protection objectives set by the law. Table 8 offers an overview of the various noise levels that must be respected in Italy.

Table 8: Compulsory noise thresholds in Italy as of November 2023

Emission limit values	Daytime (06:00 – 22:00)	Nighttime (22:00 – 06:00)
Class I: Protected areas	45	35
Class II: Residential areas	50	40
Class III: Mixed areas	55	45
Absolute input limit values	Daytime (06:00 – 22:00)	Nighttime (22:00 – 06:00)
Class I: Protected areas	50	40
Class II: Residential areas	55	45
Class III: Mixed areas	60	50
Quality values	Daytime (06:00 – 22:00)	Nighttime (22:00 – 06:00)
Class I: Protected areas	47	37
Class II: Residential areas	52	42
Class III: Mixed areas	57	47

Source: Own elaboration.

3.2.2 Environmental Impact Assessment

Decree Law no. 152 of 3 April 2006 (DL 152/2006) is the central regulation governing the procedures for the EIA, the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) and the Integration Environmental Authorizations (IPPC). The EIA applies to projects that may have significant and negative environmental impacts (Art. 7 para. 6 *ibid*). The respective regions or autonomous provinces verify whether an EIA is needed; wind farms with an installed power capacity of more than 1 MW must automatically undergo this check (Annex IV *ibid*).

Projects and modifications or extensions of these projects are listed in Annex II and III (Art. 7 para. 7 *ibid.*). Onshore wind farms exceeding a total power capacity of 1 MW are listed in Annex III; they are under the governing responsibility of the regions and the autonomous provinces of Trento and Bolzano. Onshore wind farms exceeding a total power capacity of 30 MW and offshore wind farms are listed on Annex II; they are under the governing responsibility of the State.

3.2.3 Electricity Law Permit

Legislative Decree no. 387 of 29 December 2003 (DL 387/2003) promotes RE production in Italy covering power plants with an installed capacity exceeding 20 kW (Art. 6 *ibid.*). Wind power installations on roofs with a total height of up to 1.5 meters and a diameter of up to 1 meter must merely notify the respective municipal administration of the start of the activity (*attività ad edilizia libera e sono realizzati previa comunicazione*); an electronic notification is sufficient (Attachment of DM 2010). This does not apply in cases covered by the Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape (Decree Law no. 42 of 22 January 2004). According to the Legislative Decree no. 28 of 3 March 2011 (DL 28/2011), the regions and autonomous provinces may extend these provisions to power plants with a nominal power capacity of up to 50 kW (Art. 6 para. 11 *ibid.*).

Wind power installations with a capacity of less than 60 kW require a certified notification with respect to the start of their activity (*segnalazione certificate di inizio di attività*), pursuant to Article 22 and 23 of the Presidential Decree no. 380 of 6 June 2001 (Art. 12 para. 5 PD 380/2001). The Regions and Autonomous Provinces may extend the provisions to power plants with a nominal power capacity of up to 1 MW (Art. 6 para. 9 *ibid.*).

For the construction of RE plants exceeding a production capacity of 60 kW, DL 387/2003 foresees a "Single Authorisation" (*autorizzazione unica*) to be issued by the region or provinces delegated by the region (Art. 12 para. 3 *ibid.*). The provinces of four Italian regions (Bolzano, Trento, Liguria, and Lazio) enjoy the power to govern the Single Authorisation procedure themselves, while the provinces in three Italian regions (Piemonte, Lombardy, and Marche) share the competence with the respective region. The Single Authorisation is a "one-stop-shop", simplifying the authorization process of RE plants. Within a so-called Unified Conference, all administrative institutions and authorities involved in the process participate in compliance with the

principles of simplification and the methods established in the Law of 7 August 1990 no. 241 (Art. 12 para. 4 *ibid.*).

For offshore plants, the authorization must be issued by the Ministry of Ecological Transition in agreement with the Ministry of Sustainable Infrastructure and Mobility and, for aspects related to maritime fishing activity, with the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry (Art. 12 para. 3, DL 387/2003). For systems with an installed capacity equal to or greater than 300 MW, the authorisation must be issued by the Ministry of Economic Development, in compliance with the regulations regarding the protection of the environment, the landscape and the cultural heritage of Italy (Art. 12 para. 3 *ibid.*). Table 9 offers an overview of the electricity permit in Italy as of November 2023.

Table 9: Electricity Permit Thresholds in Italy as of November 2023

	Permit-Free Construction Upon Notification	Certified Notification	Single Authorisation Procedure
General Thresholds	MD of 10.9.2010, attachment: Wind power installations on roofs with the following cumulative requirements and not falling into the scope of DL no. 42 of 22.1.2004: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - up to 1.5 m of height - up to 1.0 m of diameter 	DL no. 387 of 29.12.2003 Art. 12 para. 5: Wind power installations with a capacity of less than 60 kW pursuant to Arts 22 and 23 of PD no. 380 of 6.6.2001	DL no. 387 of 29.12.2003 Art. 12 para. 5: Wind power installations with a capacity of more than 60 kW pursuant to MD of 10.9.2010
Option of Threshold Adaptation by Regions and Autonomous Provinces	DL no. 28 of 3.3.2011 Art. 6 para. 11 to a nominal power capacity of up to 50 kW	DL no. 28 of 3.3.2001 Art. 6 para. 9 to a nominal power capacity of up to 1 MW	none

MD = Ministerial Decree; PD = Presidential Decree; DL = Decree Law Source: Own elaboration.

3.2.4 Building Law

As noted in section 3.2.3 above, wind farms with a capacity of less than 60 kW, do not require a Single Authorisation, but solely a certified notification with respect to the start of its activity (*segnalazione certificate di inizio di attività*), pursuant to Arts 22 and 23 of the Presidential Decree 380/2001 (Art. 12 para. 5 *ibid.*). The decree entails general principles and provisions with respect to construction activities. With respect to electromagnetic interference from wind turbines on telecommunication, a report pursuant to the Law no. 36 of 22 February 2001 should be created by the wind park developers (DM 2010). Possible mitigation measures are, above all, the use of low

speed and optimized airfoil generators to reduce the noise impact (which can be interpreted as a trade-off); the provision of adequate distances of the turbines to the source of radio signals; the use of existing transmission lines or of underground lines (Annex IV *ibid.*).

To minimize of the risk of accidents, the wind turbines should comply to IEC 61400 standards. Further, the distance of each wind turbine to roads should be higher than the maximum propeller height including the rotor and, in any case, not less than 150 m. If the wind park is close to a particular site or an installation, such as an apparatus of air navigation assistance or radio links of public interest, design solutions must be adopted to avoid any interference (Annex IV *ibid.*).

3.2.5 Nature and Cultural Heritage

Onshore Wind Energy

With respect to the end of service of the wind turbine, wind park operators should restore the used site to its previous condition. This might include, among others, reforestation, and afforestation measures. Further, the foundation structure made of concrete should be drowned for at least 1 m; power lines should be completely removed and treated according to the current legislation (Annex 4, DM 2010).

To protect flora, fauna and habitat, the analysis of impacts on the most sensitive and valuable species (in particular avifauna and bats) should be conducted. A cartographic identification of Natura 2000 sites and areas protected through nature conservation law should be conducted with a particular focus on the identification of sites of bird nesting. Some measures proposed are, among others, the use of wind turbines with tubular towers and low-speed blade rotation (Annex 4 *ibid.*).

Offshore Wind Energy

With respect to offshore wind development, Legislative Decree no. 290 of 13 October 2010 transposes Directive 2008/56/EC with the aim to developing strategies to maintain a good status of the marine environment. Projects that pose an impact on the marine environment are listed in the annex of the regulation; wind energy plants of wave motion and tides are included (Table 2 of Annex *ibid.*).

Cultural Heritage Considerations

Legislative Decree no. 42 of 22 January 2004 regulates the protection of Italy's cultural heritage and landscape assets. The Italian Cultural Heritage and Landscape Code stipulates that institutional consultation and the participation of interested parties and authorities must be ensured in the landscape approval procedures. To this end, the regions regulate landscape planning procedures, including forms of participation, information, and communication as to fulfil the requirements of this Law (Art. 144 *ibid.*). The Italian Cultural Heritage and Landscape defines specific areas protected by the law, among others coastal territories; rivers, streams, and waterways; mountains for the part exceeding 1,600 m above sea level for the Alpine chain and 1,200 m above sea level for the Apennine chain and for the islands; glaciers; national or regional parks and reserves and forests (Art. 142 *ibid.*). To be able to construct buildings, including wind parks, in these zones, special protection measures must be developed by the responsible authorities (Art. 142 *ibid.*).

3.2.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance

DM 2010 names the criteria for the possible establishment of compensatory measures in favour of the Regions and Autonomous Provinces (Annex III *ibid.*). It stipulates that compensations must not only be of financial nature. Further, compensation of economic nature must not exceed three percent of the proceeds obtained from the electricity produced.

3.3 Portugal

Portugal is a unitary state with two levels of government: (i) the national level; and (ii) the municipal level with 308 municipalities. Furthermore, two autonomous regions exist: The island of the Azores and Madeira. Portugal has a centralized system (OECD, 2017); a referendum to empower the eight regional divisions failed. It is thus mainly federal regulations governing wind energy in Portugal.

3.3.1 Wind Energy Zones

Wind Energy Within Dedicated Zones

Portugal has no zoning plans explicitly dedicated to onshore wind energy planning. However, the 2022 Report on the State of The Regional Planning (Direção-Geral do Território, 2023) in Portugal dedicates a chapter on RE and includes a map with areas in which the construction of wind park could

potentially enjoy simplified administrative procedures; this map is also available online (geoPortal, 2023).

Wind Energy Within Nature Protection Zones

In Portugal, Special Territory Planning Plans (*Planes de Ordenamento do Território*, PEOT) are regulating spatial planning policies at regional, inter-municipal and municipal level. They are legally binding for public entities and private individuals. The PEOT can be subdivided into various planning types: such as Protected Area Management Plans (*Planos de Ordenamento de Áreas Protegidas*, POAP); and Coastal Management Plans (*Planos de Ordenamento da Orla Costeira*, POOC). The five regions of continental Portugal (Norte, Centro, Lisboa Metropolitan Region, Alentejo and Algarve) propose maps with respect to nature protection. Table 10 contains an overview of POAP and POOC regulating the construction of wind turbines on their protected area (da Cruz Almeida, 2015).

Table 10: Rules on Wind Energy Construction Within Protected Areas

NUTS2	Area Protection Plans (POAP or POOC)	Paragraph	Content of the POAP / POOC
PT11	POAP of the Alvão Natural Park	8_1_ab	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the ICNF IP.
PT11	POAP of the Litoral Norte Natural Park	8_n	Wind turbine impossible.
PT11	POAP of the Montesinho Natural Park	9_1_f	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the ICNF IP
PT11	POOC of Caminha-Espinho	12_a	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the DRA or the ICN
PT11	POAP of the National Park Peneda Geres	7_d	Wind turbine construction impossible.
PT15	POOC of the Vilamoura_Vila Real de Santo Antonio	66_2	Wind turbine construction impossible on beaches of type IV and V.
PT15	POOC of Burgau_Vilamoura	annex_II	Wind turbine construction impossible on beaches of type IV and V.
PT15	POAP of the Ria Formosa Nature Park	8_1_l	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the DRA or the ICN.
PT15	POAP of the Sapel de Castro Marim and the Santo António Natural Reserve	8_c	Wind turbine construction Impossible.
PT16	POOC of Ovar-Marinha Grande	8_1_a	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the DRAOT Center or the ICN.
PT16	POAP of the Tejo Internacional Nature Park	9_m	Wind turbine construction impossible.
PT16	POAP of the Serra da Estrela Nature Park	12_1_b	Wind turbine construction impossible in type I partial protection areas.
PT16	POAP of the Serras de Aire e Candeeiros	NE_17_11	Wind turbine construction impossible with the exception of UPAC.
PT16	POOC of Alcobaca-Mafra	54_3	Wind turbine construction impossible on beaches of type IV and V.
PT17	POOC of Sintra-Sado	21_5_c and d	Wind turbine construction in protection areas subject to a binding opinion from the competent entity.
PT17	POOC of Sintra-Sado	22_4_f and h	Wind turbine construction in framing areas subject to a binding opinion from the competent entity.
PT17	POAP of the Estuario do Sado Natural Reserve	8_e	Wind turbine construction impossible.

PT18	POOC of Sado-Sines	annex_III	Wind turbine construction for domestic consumption if the public energy supply VALUE UNIT away.
PT18	POAP of the Sudoeste Alentejano e Costa Vicentina Natural Park	19_3_b	Wind turbine construction impossible except for domestic consumption.
PT18	POOC of Sines-Burgau	annex_I	Wind turbine construction on beaches of type II and III for domestic consumption if the public energy supply VALUE UNIT away.
PT18	POOC of Sines-Burgau	annex_I	Wind turbine construction impossible on beaches of type IV and V.
PT18	POAP of the Esturio do Tejo Natural Reserve	25_5_c	Wind turbine construction subject to a binding opinion from the ICNF IP.

PT11_Norte | PT15_Algarve | PT16_Centro | PT17_Área Metropolitana de Lisboa | PT18_Alentejo
 Source: Own elaboration.

Offshore Wind Energy Zones

With respect to offshore wind energy, an inter-ministerial working group has been set up in accordance to Order no. 11404/2022 of 23 September 2022. It has identified three areas in the North Atlantic Ocean, totalling 3.5 GW: Viana do Castelo (1 GW), Leixões (500 MW) and Figueira da Foz (2 GW). The inter-ministerial working group proposed to let wind park developers compete for these areas in tenders. The first tender was launched in November 2023; fifty bidders have expressed their interest (Durakovic, 2023). Prior to the proposition of the three areas, the cost of establishing the wind farms and power grid capacities and environmental impacts were assessed (Buljan, 2023). Further, a public hearing was conducted between January 30 to March 10, 2023 (see Order no. 1396-C/2023 of 27 January 2023). A report of the inter-ministerial working group indicating the selected areas and the offshore wind energy exploitation plan has been published in May 2023 (República Portuguesa, 2023).

The revised TEN-E Regulation (EU) 2022/869 (2022b) introduces key provisions to coordinate offshore wind energy development and grid planning in Europe. Together with the European Commission, Member States with access to the sea are asked to define and agree on the amount of offshore wind energy to be deployed within each sea basin by 2050, with intermediate steps in 2030 and 2040. In January 2023, Portugal adopted a non-binding agreement with Ireland, Spain, and France to produce a minimum amount of offshore wind energy in the North Atlantic Ocean waters; Portugal pledged to produce 30 GW of offshore wind energy by the end of 2050 (2023a).

Wind Energy Outside Dedicated Zones

This project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

In Portugal, noise pollution is regulated through Decree Law no. 9/2007. Municipal land use plans must ensure the quality of the sound environment, promoting the appropriate distribution of land uses, considering existing and expected noise sources. Municipalities are responsible for indicating the location of sensitive areas and mixed areas in municipal spatial planning plans (Art. 6 *ibid.*). Noise maps prepared by the municipal councils are to support the set-up of municipal spatial planning plans (Art. 7 *ibid.*).

The two noise indicators relevant for the construction of wind turbines are the indicator for day periods (L_{den}) and the indicator for night periods (L_{night}). The L_{den} is the noise indicator associated with the long-term overall annoyance experienced between daytime period from 7 am to 8 pm; the $L(n \text{ index})$ or $L(\text{night index})$ is the noise indicator associated with the long-term average sound level, determined during a series of night periods from 11 pm to 7 am, representing a year (Art. 3). Depending on whether an area is classified as mixed or sensitive, the following exposure limit values must be respected:

- (i) mixed areas must not be exposed to external ambient noise exceeding 65 dB(A) and greater than 55 dB(A), both expressed by the indicator L_{den} ;
- (ii) sensitive areas must not be exposed to external ambient noise exceeding 55 dB(A) and exceeding 45 dB(A), both expressed by the indicator L_{night} (Art. 11).

Mixed areas are zones whose occupation is affected by other uses, existing or planned, in addition to those defined as sensitive areas. Sensitive areas are areas used or intended to be used, above all, for housing, schools, hospitals, and leisure activities. Sensitive areas may contain small commercial and service units intended to serve the local population, such as cafes and other catering establishments, shops and other traditional establishments which are not open at night. According to a 2018 JRC Technical Report (2018) a threshold of 45 dB, which is the strictest threshold according to Law-Decree n 8/2007, is reached at a distance of around 120 m in case of small wind turbines (with a power output of 250 kW) and at around 500 m for large wind turbines (with a power output of around 3 MW). Turbine emission specifications (in dB levels) must comply with IEC 61400. The APA (Portuguese Environmental Agency) has published a practical guide for how environmental noise measurements must be conducted.

3.3.2 Environmental Impact Assessment

In Portugal, the Environmental Impact Assessment (*Avaliação de Impacte Ambiental*, AIA) was introduced by Decree Law no. 151-B/2013 (DL 151-B/2013) and amended by Decree Law No. 152-B/2017 (DL 152-B/2917). An EIA is, among others, mandatory for projects listed in Annex II of the EIA-Decree. It explicitly governs that an EIA is mandatory for wind turbines if they fulfill the following criteria:

- (i) If the wind park is located outside a sensitive or protected area and counts 20 or more wind turbines or if it is located near (< 2km) a similar wind park project.
- (ii) If the wind park is located inside a sensitive or protected area and counts ten or more wind turbines or if it is located near (< 2km) a similar wind park project (Annex II *ibid.*).

Sensitive areas are, among others, national parks, nature parks and nature reserves, protected landscape areas, natural monuments, Natura 2000 Network Sites, special conservation zones, special protection zones and protection zones for real estate (Art. 2 DL 151-B/2013). Wind energy projects that are not covered by the above thresholds but are located in sensitive areas must undergo an EIA if it is considered likely that they cause significant impacts on the environment pursuant to the criteria set out in annex III (Art. 1 *ibid.*). Wind energy projects that are neither covered by the above thresholds set out in annex II nor located in sensitive areas must undergo a case-by-case analysis if the distance between the wind turbines is less than 2 km (Art. 1 Decree Law no. 11/2023).

Projects that are not subject to an EIA but are planned within Natura 2000 Network sites must undergo an Environmental Incidence Assessment (*Procedimento de Avaliação de Incidências Ambientais, EinCA*) (Art. 10-A Decree Law no. 76/2019). The EinCA is carried out by the territorially competent Regional Coordination and Development Commission (CCDR), in accordance with the Nature Conversation Law (Decree Law no. 140/99). Before making a decision, the CCDR must consult the Institute for the Conservation of Nature and Forests (INCF).

3.3.3 Electricity Law Permit

The production of RE with plants that exceed a maximum installed capacity of 1 MW requires an electricity production and operation licence (*licença de produção e de exploração*); below that threshold, a notification is sufficient

(Art. 4 Decree Law no. 76/2019). Obtaining an electricity law permit depends on the grid capacities available. To start the electricity law procedure, it is required to obtain a prior attribution of a grid capacity reservation certificate (*Titulus de Reserve de Capacidade de rede, TRC*) for injecting electricity into the Public Service Electricity Network (*Rede Elétrica de Serviço Público, RESP*) (Art. 5 *ibid.*). The Directorate General for Energy and Geology (*Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia, DGEG*) is the responsible authority. TRCs are allocated pursuant to one of three modalities (e-redes, 2022) explained in Table 11.

Table 11: Three modalities of distributing grid capacity reserves certificated to energy producers in Portugal as of November 2023

General Access	Agreement	Competitive Procedure
A general access request is submitted to the DGEG, indicating the intended injection capacity, the connection substation, the voltage level and the respective grid operator used.	An agreement must be reached between the DGEG and the energy producer when there is not enough grid capacity left but the energy producer assumes the financial cost for constructing or reinforcing the grid. The maximum available capacity is defined by the government by January 15 of each year.	The government can determine that a competitive procedure must be carried out for the attribution of the TRC. This modality is intended for the attribution of TRC for electricity produced from renewable energy and may cover one or more production technologies and include storage facilities (batteries).

Source: Own elaboration.

The *holder* of the electricity production licence can only start the project after obtaining the respective operation licence (Art. 20-B Decree Law no. 76/2019). The request for the operation licence must be accompanied by a declaration signed by the technicians responsible for the project and supervising the construction, certifying, under oath, that the installation is completed and that the plant is ready to be used. Before issuing the licence, the DGEG carries out an inspection and may be accompanied by the representatives of the respective network operator (Art. 21 Decree Law no. 76/2019).

3.3.4 Building Law

The installation of renewable energy plants, storage facilities, self-consumption unit (*Unidade de Produção para Autoconsumo, UPAC*) with a power capacity of more than 1 MW is subject to prior control, through prior communication, pursuant to the Urbanization and Building Code (Decree Law no. 555/99 of 16 December). The project developer must submit all legally required opinions, authorization documents and approvals. Within

eight days after reception, the president of the municipal council may issue an order asking for further information or rejecting the project (Art. 4-A Decree Law no. 30-A/2022). The municipality may also reject the prior communication on the grounds of negative impact on the landscape, except if (i) the project has been subject of a favourable or conditional EIA or (ii) the municipal territory has an area of less than two percent of the total area allocated to renewable energy projects (Art. 4-A *ibid.*).

3.3.5 Nature and Culture Heritage

The issuance of an electricity production and operation license pursuant to Decree Law no. 76/2019 for electricity production plants that do not need to conduct an EIA but are planned in areas of the Natura 2000 Network is preceded by an environmental impact procedure pursuant to the Nature Conservation Act (Art. 10-A, Decree Law no. 140/99). The territorially competent Regional Coordination and Development Commission (CCDR) is the responsible authority for the procedure. It promotes a public consultation for the period of twenty days and making available on its website the study of environmental impacts (Art. 10-B Decree Law no. 76/2019). The CCDR must also consult the Institute for the Conservation of Nature and Forests (ICNF), before making a decision.

3.3.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance

Monetary Measures

According to Decree Law no. 15/2022 (Art. 49 para. 2 *ibid.*), the owners of RE plants or storage facilities with an assigned connection power exceeding 50 MWh must offer to the municipality where the project is located or, at the municipality's request, to the nearby population:

- (i) a self-consumption unit (*UPAC*) with an installed power equal to 0.3% of the power connected to the installed RE plant or storage facility; or
- (ii) electric vehicle charging stations for public use with an equivalent capacity as indicated under (i).

If the municipality already has installed *UPACs*, it can instead opt for a one-off payment of 1,500 EUR per MVA of allocated connection power.

Owners of RE plants or storage facilities with an assigned connection power between 1 and 50 MVA must offer a one-off payment of 1,500 EUR per MVA of allocated connection power.

Cash compensations are intended to be applied to promote energy efficiency of municipal buildings or equipment of collective use or of public housing buildings, by adopting the following measures (Art. 49 para. 3 *ibid.*):

- (i) replacing non-efficient windows with efficient windows that have an energy class equal to or higher than A+;
- (ii) installing or replacing thermal insulation on roofs, walls or floors, using natural-based materials or those that incorporate recycled materials as well as replacing entrance doors;
- (iii) offering space heating and/or cooling and/or domestic hot water systems that are run through renewable energy and have an energy class of A+ or higher (e.g., heat pumps, solar thermal systems; biomass boilers and recuperators with high efficiency; storage systems)

In addition to the above compensation measures, Decree Law no. 30-A/2022 governs that owners of renewable energy installations and storage facilities must offer municipalities a one-time compensation in the amount of 13,500 EUR per MVA of allocated connection power. This money is to be borne by the Environmental Fund and has been transferred to the municipalities since January 2023 (Art. 4-B *ibid.*).

Qualitative Measures

The so-called Simplex-Package (Decree-Law no. 30-A/2022) rules that RE projects with an installed power capacity of 20 MW or more or, in the case of wind energy, projects with ten or more turbines, must be accompanied by a proposition to involve the local community, for example through (Art. 6 *ibid.*):

- Offering the space used by the RE plants for other activities such as sheep and chicken farming, beekeeping, or urban gardening;
- the creation of local jobs, especially for the operation and maintenance of the local renewable energy production centre;
- the promotion of biodiversity with the involvement of local associations and population as well as schools located in proximity to the RE plant;
- the provision of electricity surplus to local communities and/or industry;
- granting the local population the option to co-invest into the energy plants.

3.4 Norway

Norway is a unitary state with three levels of government: (i) the national level; (ii) 19 counties and (iii) 428 municipalities (OECD, 2017). The land zone planning in Norway is divided into three levels pursuant to the Planning and Building Act (LOV-2008-06-27-71): municipality planning executed by the municipal board (Section 3-3 *ibid*); regional planning executed by the regional planning authority (Section 3-4 *ibid*) and national planning executed by the ministry whereby the King is responsible for its management (Section 3-5 *ibid*).

3.4.1 Wind Energy Zones

Wind Energy Within Dedicated Zones

Plans pursuant to the Planning and Building Act (LOV-2008-06-27-71) must set goals for the environmental, economic, social, and cultural development in municipalities and regions (Section 3.1 *ibid*). The plans must, among others, secure the value of the landscape, the natural basis for Sami culture and take climate considerations into account. Concerning the value of the landscape, the national reference system for landscape (Norwegian Institute of Land Inventory, NIJOS), serves as indicator revealing which parts of the country must be protected (Puschmann, 1998).

With respect to the energy sector, the Ministry of Local Government and Districts can decide in individual cases that final concessions for power production plants shall, without further ado, have effect as a state spatial plan. The ministry thus draws up and adopts certain land zoning plans by itself, overriding the competence of the municipality. Since June 2023, however, this competence does not apply to licenses for onshore wind power plants (Section 6-4, LOV-2008-06-27-71), making it impossible to build wind turbines contrary to the will of municipalities. The aim of this amendment was to reduce the level of conflict in wind power matters and to enhance the cooperation between wind park developers and municipalities (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2023). In 2019, wind park licencing has been put on a hold for a duration of three years, after the Norwegian Constitutional Court ruled that the construction of the Storheia and Roan wind farms were illegal, conflicting with the rights of reindeer herders, and needed to be torn down again (Buli, 2021).

In April 2019, the Norwegian Directorate of Water Resources and Energy (NVE) published a 239-page proposal (NVE, 2019) for a national framework for on-

shore wind power on behalf of the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy. The proposal includes an updated knowledge base on the effects of wind power and a map of thirteen areas the NVE believes are best suited for wind power development in Norway. The map (NVE Temakart, 2023) can be consulted on the official website of the NVE. During the process of public consultation, more than 5,000 responses (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2019) from ministries, municipalities, nature conservation associations and other interested parties have been collected. In view of massive criticism, the government has decided to disregard the 13 (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020b) areas chosen but will continue to update the knowledge base on the effects of wind power to guide wind park developers in their implementation (NVE, 2023b).

Wind Energy Outside Dedicated Zones

In March 2021, the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy commissioned the NVE to establish a permanent collaboration with state agencies to update the knowledge base on the effects of wind power plants on land on a regular basis. The knowledge base can be assessed on the NVE website (NVE, 2022a). Adhering to the knowledge base, which by itself has no legally binding effect, is crucial to successfully obtain a wind energy production license. It covers various topics along six pillars: (i) culture; (ii) natural diversity; (iii) climate, pollution, and natural hazards; (iv) infrastructure; (v) society and (vi) food and outdoor areas.

The knowledge base (NVE, 2022b) contains information on noise limits for wind energy and draws on limit values given in the Guidelines for the treatment of noise in spatial planning (T-1442) (Klima-og miljødepartementet, 2021). Recommended limits for noise emissions are Lden 45 dB in yellow zones and Lden 55 dB in red zones. Yellow zones are assessment zones, where good planning must be conducted to achieve satisfactory noise conditions; red zones are not suitable for the development of noise-sensitive buildings (e.g., hospitals) but leave a greater playing field for wind turbines. To respect the noise limits, the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy proposes a minimum distance of wind turbines to permanently inhabited residences and leisure facilities of four times the total turbine height or a minimum of 800 metres (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020b).

Offshore Wind Energy Zones

The Norwegian Offshore Energy Act (LOV-2010-06-04-21) regulates RE production at sea, typically wind power, as well as the transmission of electrical energy at sea. The right to exploit RES at sea belongs to the state (Section 1-3 *ibid.*). The King-in-Council (meetings of the King and the Cabinet) plays a vital role in offshore wind energy development; it can determine that an area for RE construction shall be opened to grant a licence, after a Strategic EIA has been conducted. Proposals for the opening of areas with completed EIA must be submitted for consultation and put out for public inspection (Section 2-2, LOV-2010-06-04-21).

In January 2013, a Strategic EIA (NVE, 2013) was carried out by the NVE and presented to the Ministry of Oil and Energy, analysing 15 areas in the Norwegian sea area. In June 2020, the Norwegian Government decided to open up the first two offshore wind energy zones Utsira Nord (with a capacity of 1,500 MW) and Sørilige Nordsjøen 2 (with a capacity of 3,000 MW) for applications (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020a). According to the media (Memija, 2023), Norway's first offshore auction attracted seven applications. In May 2022, the government presented a major initiative to accelerate offshore wind energy production (Office of the Minister, 2022). The national target is to open up areas for offshore wind power production that will generate 30,000 MW of power in Norway by 2040. In September 2023, the NVE recommended that the government should consider extending the already opened two areas with the areas Sørvest F and Vestavind F for the 2024 tender round. In addition, the government intends to conduct a Strategic EIA for a third area: Vestavind B to be concluded by the end of November 2024 (Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy, 2023).

3.4.2 Environmental Impact Assessment

Onshore Wind Energy

All wind power projects with an installed capacity of more than 10 MW require notification pursuant to the Impact Assessment Regulation (Appendix I nr. 28, FOR-2017-06-21-854). Such notification shall include a description of the project, as well as a provisional assessment of its potential environmental and societal impact (Section 14 *ibid.*). The notification is circulated for consultation to enable affected parties and other stakeholders to comment on the project at an early stage. After the notification process, the NVE shall compose an impact assessment programme which will be the leading

guideline for the project developer to assess the respective project (Section 16 and 17, FOR-2017-06-21-854).

Wind power projects with an installed capacity of less than 10 MW may be assessed pursuant to appendix II nr. 3h of the Impact Assessment Act (FOR-2017-06-21-854). The relevant regulations are the Water Resource Act (LOV-2000-11-24-82) and the Watercourses Regulation Act (LOV-1917-12-14-17). Such impact assessment must assess significant effects on the environment and society, including, among others: natural diversity, cultural monuments; landscape; pollution; soil resources; Sami natural and cultural basis and accident risk. The description must include positive, negative, direct, indirect, temporary, permanent, short-term, and long-term effects (Section 21, FOR-2017-06-21-854).

Offshore Wind Energy

With respect to offshore wind energy, whoever is allocated an area by the Ministry of Oil and Energy as responsible authority receives a time-limited and exclusive right to carry out a project-specific impact assessment to apply for a licence for a power plant within this area (Section 2-3, LOV-2010-06-04-21). The project developer must assess the impact of the energy plant on the environment and society focussing, among others, on the following elements: impact on birds and fish; impact on the fishing industry; impact on Sami nature and cultural basis and impact on the sea, the air, the ground, and noise (Section 6, FOR-2020-06-12-1192). The Norwegian Environment Agency as responsible authority under the Pollution Act (LOV-1981-03-13-6) can propose further measures that must be considered by project developers.

3.4.3 Electricity Law Permit

The Environmental Impact Assessment and the general licencing procedure for wind energy development are closely connected. The Energy Act (FOR-1990-12-07-959) contains the basic and centralized rules for granting wind energy permits. Since June 2023, no electricity permit application for onshore wind power plants can be processed until the municipality has proposed a suitable area for construction (Section 3.7, LOV-2008-06-27-71).

Onshore wind power plants do not need a licence when the installed power capacity of the plant does not exceed 1 MW or the plant does not count more than 5 turbines; these cases are processed by the municipalities according

to the Planning and Building Act (LOV-2008-06-27-71) (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020b). In cases of doubt, the NVE can decide whether there is a license obligation. The wind park developer without licence obligation must report to the NVE once the final permission pursuant to the Planning and Building Act has been issued (Section 3-1, FOR-1990-12-07-959). In all other cases, a licence pursuant to the Energy Act is necessary. The Energy Act (LOV-1990-06-29-50) ensures that the production, transformation, sale, distribution, and use of energy takes place in a socially rational way, considering public and private interests that might be affected (Section 1-2 *ibid.*). The same applies to the remodelling or expansion of existing facilities (Section 3-1 *ibid.*).

To ensure a more holistic assessment of wind park projects, the government, where possible, processes several license applications jointly in a county, possibly within regions across countries which are most appropriate for wind energy. A regional treatment will provide a better basis for assessing overall pressure, for example on bird migration and reindeer herding. It will also be easier to assess network capacity and regional effects on security of supply (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020b). In October 2023 NVE introduced criteria for prioritizing wind power cases, to better cope with the large amount of applications (NVE, 2023a). Indicators for prioritization are the energy producing capacity of the project (large power plants will be prioritized); the location of the project (projects in Finnmark will be prioritized since they are demanding cases because of the great natural and environmental values in the area and because of the strong and sometimes conflicting interests in these cases) and the documents handed in (projects with detailed and complete plans will be prioritized). Further, licence applications that contain documentation of involvement from reindeer husbandry in the studies and an agreement on mitigation and compensatory measures will be prioritized (NVE, 2023a).

3.4.4 Building Law

Offshore Wind Energy

The regulation on the marking of RE plants (FOR-2016-09-15-1066) applies to installations that are located above or below sea level possibly obstructing vessels. Measures wind park developers must ensure when constructing a wind park on sea include:

- (i) Bottom-fixed and floating wind energy installations must be specifically coloured to ensure their visibility when illuminated with searchlights in the dark (Section 4.1 *ibid.*).
- (ii) Offshore wind energy devices must be identified with letters and numbers (with a height of at least 0.7 m) that must be visible from any horizontal direction at distances of up to 1.5 nautical miles (Section 4.1 *ibid.*).
- (iii) Light signal should be placed at a height between 6 - 15 m above the highest astronomical tide (Section 4.2 *ibid.*).
- (iv) Offshore Wind Energy plants that constitute a particular navigational hazard, should be equipped with radar transponders to ensure seafarers can recognize and detect them (Section 6.2 *ibid.*).

Aviation Law

The regulation on aviation obstacles (FOR-2014-07-15-980), establishes minimum requirements on this topic to reduce the risk of aviation accidents. Measures wind park developers must ensure when constructing a wind park include:

- (i) Wind turbines must be marked with obstacle lights, located on the top of the nacelle (Art. 10 *ibid.*).
- (ii) Wind turbines need colour markings that must be visible in daylight at a distance of at least 1,500 meters from all relevant approach angles (Art. 2 *ibid.*).
- (iii) Wind turbines must be marked with a light colour, for example grey, off-white, or other shades of white; snow white colour must not be used.
- (iv) The marking requirement does not apply to the bottom third of the tower (Art. 15 *ibid.*).

3.4.5 Nature and Cultural Heritage

Nature Law

The Nature Diversity Act (LOV-2009-06-19-100) is crucial for the development of wind energy protecting, among others, areas on land and in the sea, contributing to the conservation of natural diversity and species (Section 33 *ibid.*). It defines several types of protected areas, such as national parks; landscape conservation areas; nature reserves; biotope protection areas; marine protected areas and protected areas with international status (Sections 35-40 *ibid.*). The conservation values in protected areas must be weighted when deciding whether to grant a wind park project permission or

not (Section 49 *ibid.*) The areas are determined by the King-in-Council (Section 34 *ibid.*). The Norwegian Environmental Agency (miljødirektoratet) published an online map, indicating the protected areas (Miljødepartementet, 2019).

Cultural Heritage Law

The Cultural Heritage Act (LOV-1978-06-09-50) is crucial for the development of wind energy in congruence with the national aim to protect archaeological and architectural monuments as part of Norway's cultural identity and the rights of the Sami indigenous people. Section four contains a list of monuments and sites from before 1537 AD that are automatically protected by the Act; the same level of protection applies to Sami monuments and sites that are more than 100-year-old.

3.4.6 Measures to Raise Acceptance

In October 2023 (Norwegian Ministry of Finance, 2023), the government presented a modified bill for the introduction of a resource rent tax on onshore wind power which will take effect from 1 January 2024. The resource rent tax will be automatically adjusted to the profits of the particular windfarm. The Government aims for an amount equivalent to NOK 0.002 per kWh of wind power production to be set aside for local purposes such as nature, reindeer husbandry and any other purposes directly affected by the land use. This arrangement needs to be examined in more detail. The proposal will ensure that a larger share of the value added in the wind power industry will accrue to society as a whole; at least half of the revenues will accrue to municipalities. The government is proposing an effective tax rate of 35 %, with the tax being structured as a cash flow tax with an immediate deduction of investment costs. Gross revenues from the proposed resource rent tax are projected to be about NOK 300 million accrued in 2024. Net revenues, after the deduction of production tax, are projected to be about NOK 150 million accrued in 2024 (Norwegian Ministry of Finance, 2023).

With respect to offshore energy, if the business in an area seizes a fishing field in whole or in part and makes fishing impossible or significantly more difficult, the state is obliged to compensate affected actors. Compensation can be set in whole or in part as a lump sum or as fixed annual sums. Losses that have occurred more than seven years after the seizure cannot normally be claimed. The state can demand recourse from the concessionaire if the

concessionaire should have averted the loss (Section 9-2, LOV-2010-06-04-21).

3.5 Synthesis of Regulatory Framework

Analysing the regulatory framework governing wind energy development in Austria, Italy, Portugal, and Norway, a heterogenous legal landscape unveils. While Austria presents a high level of regulatory density governing wind turbines siting using hard law, Italy, Portugal, and Norway lean on guidelines when proposing minimum distances, leaving wind park developers room for interpretation. The following Table 12 offers an overview of the national regulations governing wind turbine siting, defining the competence of municipalities to influence wind energy development and financial compensation measures to raise acceptance vis-à-vis wind energy.

Table 12: Summary of Regulatory Framework

	Austria	Italy	Portugal	Norway
Dedicated areas for wind energy development (onshore)	In several states (Burgenland, Lower Austria, Carinthia, Styria, Upper Austria, Salzburg) dedicated zones for wind energy development have been introduced (legally binding).	Suitable areas such as quarries and mines will be defined by the national government (not yet in force). Several regions have defined unsuitable areas.	The Portuguese General Directory of Territorial Planning published a map with areas in which the construction of wind parks could enjoy simplified administrative procedures (not legally binding).	In 2019, the attempt to define 13 suitable areas for wind energy development failed. A legally non-binding knowledge base helps wind park developers to choose suitable areas.
Distance of wind turbines to residential areas	Strict and legally-binding distance rules in various states: Burgenland (1.200m); Lower Austria (1.200 m); Carinthia (1.500 m); Styria (1.000 m); Upper Austria (100 – 1.000 m).	A minimum distance of 200 m or six times the height of the wind turbine has been proposed by the Ministerial Decree 2010. In general, noise limits (e.g. 45 dB Lden in protected areas) must be respected; this equals a minimum distance of	No explicit distance rules governing wind turbine construction. In general, noise limits must be respected (e.g. 45 dB Lnight in sensitive areas); this equals a minimum distance of 500 m. for large wind turbines.	A minimum distance of 800 m or four times the total turbine height has been proposed by the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy. In general, noise limits must be respected (45 dB Lden in sensitive areas); this equals a minimum distance of

<p>Dedicated areas for wind energy development (offshore)</p>		<p>500 m for large wind turbines.</p>	<p>No zoning plan for offshore wind energy presented yet.</p>	<p>500 m for large wind turbines.</p>	<p>Yes, offshore wind park developers must compete for the areas in public tenders.</p>
<p>Veto-right of municipalities to prevent construction of wind parks on land</p>	<p>Only if the state has not defined dedicated areas for wind energy development.</p>	<p>In certain regions that empower provinces to govern the authorization procedures for wind energy plants.</p>	<p>The municipality may in certain cases reject the construction of a wind park on the grounds of negative impact on the landscape.</p>	<p>Yes, in June 2023 and after a three-year moratorium, municipalities have regained their veto-power.</p>	<p>Yes, offshore wind park developers must compete for the areas in public tenders.</p>
<p>Mandatory financial compensation measures to raise acceptance</p>	<p>In 2023, the state of Burgenland, as only state, has introduced a windfall levy to xxx (50% state; 50% affected municipality).</p>	<p>Compensation of economic nature must not exceed three percent of the proceeds obtained from the electricity produced.</p>	<p>Since January 2023, owners of RE plants must offer municipalities a one-time compensation in the amount of 13,500 EUR per MVA through an Environmental Fund. Further, owners of RE plants must offer municipalities or the nearby population self-consumption units or electric vehicle charging stations. In certain cases, they can also opt for a one-off payment of 1,500 EUR per MVA.</p>	<p>In January 2024, a modified resource rent tax for onshore wind power will take effect; here, half of the revenues shall be accrued to municipalities.</p>	<p>If offshore wind energy negatively impedes the fishing industry, the state is obliged to compensate affected actors.</p>

Source: Own elaboration

Concluding, we observe a relatively high volatility regarding the formation of regulations governing the wind energy sector. Various rules, such as the windfall levy in Burgenland and the modified resource rent tax in Norway have only been introduced recently. This makes it difficult to understand the impact of regulations on real life, as long-term observational studies are made impossible.

4. GOVERNANCE MODELS

4.1 Overview of the EU Governance Framework for Wind Energy

4.1.1 Europeanization versus Member State Sovereignty

The multi-layered governance structure of the European Union allocates competencies between the EU and its Member States striking a balance between respecting national sovereignty and promoting European integration. While the EU has made a binding commitment at the supranational level to become the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050 through the European Green Deal, the governance of individual energy systems primarily remains within the domain of national governments. Each Member State exercises sovereign strategies, leading to notable variations in the adoption of renewable energy (RE). Complementing the detailed analysis of the regulatory framework for wind power deployment for each WIMBY partner country that has been presented in Chapter 3, this Chapter turns to the overarching EU policies, reigning the formation of governance models in wind energy projects in Europe.

4.1.2 The Energy Union and the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package

To advance the objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement, the European Commission initiated the Energy Union Strategy (COM/2015/080) in 2015 (European Commission, 2015a). With the goal of establishing "*an energy union that provides EU consumers – both households and businesses – with secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable energy,*" the Commission set forth a comprehensive set of measures aligning with the strategy of the Union (European Commission, 2015b).

Following negotiations between the European Commission, the Council and the Parliament in May 2019 (the institutional "trilogue") the *Clean Energy for All Europeans Package* (in short referred to as the Clean Energy Package, or CEP) was passed, signifying an important stride in realizing the objectives laid out in the 2015 Energy Union Strategy (European Commission, 2023f). Putting "*consumers at the heart of the Energy Union*", allowing them to actively take part in the clean energy transition, the CEP was celebrated as a "*game changer*" for community-based initiatives (FoE, 2018; Krug et al., 2022). Investigating how this affects wind power employment in Europe requires an analysis of the CEP's content regarding (1) regulations on energy

governance, (2) market design and (3) particular provisions in relation to the development of RE capacities.

Governance Regulation (2018/1999/EU)

The governance regulation has a pivotal place in the CEP, setting out provisions for a transparent governance of the Energy Union and *“the achievement of the 2030 and long-term objectives and targets of the Energy Union in line with the 2015 Paris Agreement”* (2018/1999/EU (1)). The regulation requires Member States to present National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs), based on *“common rules for planning, reporting and monitoring”* (European Commission, 2023g), setting a common template to be utilized by the MS. Nevertheless, actual application based on the common template strongly varies, especially regarding energy communities (Roberts & Gauthier, 2019).

Final NECPs for the period from 2021 to 2030 had to be submitted until the end of 2019. An updated draft of the plan was due by June 2023 with MS being given time until end of June 2024 to provide their final updated versions. An additional provision requires MS to develop long-term strategies to contribute to the goals of the Paris Agreement (2018/1999/EU (36)). While MS keep *“a wide scope of decision-making power, the regulation is seen as a compromise and compensation for the European Union’s lack of competences in the area of energy supply”* (Schlacke & Knodt, 2019). By obliging MS to react to any recommendation, the Commission introduced some ‘hardness’ to its otherwise soft governance on energy (Knodt et al., 2020). In summary, the Governance Regulation leaving room for national strategies to achieve set goals does not encompass explicit provisions on the deployment of wind energy.

Revised Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001/EU)

The revised Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001, commonly referred to as RED II, was enacted in December 2018 with its transposition deadline set for June 2021 although this process is still under way. The directive sets a binding target of 32% share of RE in the European Union's energy mix by the year 2030 and aims to safeguard the EU's *„global leadership on renewables”* (European Commission, 2023h).

This objective should be achieved with *“the lowest possible costs for consumers and taxpayers”* (RED II (19)). In this context, the directive includes RE

tenders as a means for the cost-effective implementation of projects. However, concerning wind energy, MS may exclude small-scale⁵ projects from these tendering procedures as a unilateral focus on competitive market principles could potentially impede the incorporation of broader aims, including social considerations. As a measure to enhance an inclusive transition the directive acknowledges the vital role of citizen participation. Regarding decentralized community ownership the RED II stipulates the right for consumers to become “renewable self-consumers” – ergo to become prosumers of renewable energy (Art 21 RED II) with the right to produce, store, consume and sell RE. They can do so either as prosumers acting individually or jointly or organised collectively as participants of a Renewable Energy Community (“REC”, RED II (52)). That table does not only include production and consumption but also the right to store and sell the produced energy. Actors eligible to be among the controlling shareholders of RECs are citizens, small and medium enterprises, and local authorities in the proximity of the installation.

Second Revision of the Renewable Energy Directive (2023/2413/EU)

In October 2023 the RED II was revised and amended to align with the updated EU goals set in the REPowerEU plan (European Commission, 2022a). Concerning wind energy, the preamble of the revised RED II stipulates the close cooperation of MS to facilitate more offshore RE capacities and opens the option for RECs to participate (amendment of Article 9 where paragraph 7a is added), stating that “*in order to enhance public acceptance, Member States may include renewable energy communities in joint offshore renewable energy projects*”. The amended Article 16a concerns the ‘permit-granting procedure in renewables acceleration areas’ and puts upper bounds to the time for permitting procedures for offshore wind energy projects to 12 months, with exceptional extensions of further six months.

Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU/2019/944) and Regulation (EU/2019/943)

⁵ “[The] thresholds are set at 1 MW (and 6 MW or 6 generation units for wind energy) and 500 kW (and 3 MW or 3 generation units for wind energy) in terms of exemptions from, respectively, tendering procedures and direct marketing.” (REDII (19))

The Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 (IEMD) and Regulation (EU) 2019/943 (IEMR) are intended to modernise Europe's electricity market at the supranational level to become *"more flexible, more market-based and better placed to integrate a greater share of renewables"* (European Commission, 2023d). The completion of the EU market integration being the priority, both the directive and regulation also envision the empowerment of consumers within the restructuring of the energy market (EU/2019/943 Article 1(b), EU/2019/944 Chapter III). To empower citizens to become participants rather than pure consumers the directive introduces the governance model of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) in Article 2 (11) as a counterpart of the RECs in the RED II. This marks a significant stride in expanding the scope for citizen engagement in the energy system. The governance model provides a wide range of possibilities for adaption to local prosumers' needs and interests, while at the same time providing a framework to facilitate citizen engagement especially in MS that so far lack national legislation on participatory governance structures in the energy sector.

In October 2023 a proposal (COM/2023/148) to amend the regulation and directive was tabled emphasizing the necessity of mitigating energy price spikes by decreasing the dependency of fossil fuel prices and with that protect the European consumers in the long run (European Commission, 2023c). It furthermore notes the importance of offshore installations in reaching climate neutrality until 2050 and foresees that MS should ensure access to hedging products explicitly for RECs and CECs (Article 18a (3)), therefore lowering the barriers for those players.

4.1.3 Fit for 55 Package

Conceptional basis for the Fit for 55 Package (in short also referred to as FF55) is the European Green Deal, presented in 2019. Reducing the EU's net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% until 2030 while ensuring a just and socially fair transition is the proclaimed goal of the package, that was adopted by the commission in July 2021 (European Council, 2023). The FF55 encompasses binding targets at the supranational level of the European Union, therefore making adoptions in existing regulations necessary, yet it lacks mandatory expansion targets for individual Member States. The efficacy of achieving the outlined goals under such conditions raises concerns. *WindEurope* anticipates annual wind installations to reach 15 GW per year between 2021 and 2025 ([WindEurope,2021](#)). However, the European Union

would need to achieve an annual capacity of 27 GW to meet the new target of a 55% reduction in emissions.

4.1.4 REPowerEU Plan

In May 2022, the REPowerEU Plan was presented as a response to the disruption of the global energy market triggered by Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine (European Commission, 2022a). Ending the dependence on Russian fossil fuels and expediting the transition to renewables, the plan involves streamlining the permitting process for RE projects and comprehensive measures to enhance energy efficiency. With its goal the REPower EU is strongly tied to the implementation of the FF55. To adhere to the principle of making RE an "*overriding public interest*" the plan acknowledges wind energy, especially offshore as a key technology and as fundamental in the energy transition. Therefore, it aims at strengthening supply chains and further accelerating permitting procedures⁶ throughout the EU.

4.1.5 European Wind Power Action Plan (COM/2023/669)

While wind stands as a main pillar for a successful energy transition, the aforementioned governance approaches concern the sector as such, without a focus on one RES. To focus on the acceleration of manufacturing and deployment of wind energy, the European Commission presented the European Wind Power Package in 2023. The Action Plan consists of six main pillars: (i) acceleration of deployment through faster permitting and increased predictability; (ii) improved auction design; (iii) access to finance; (iv) a fair and competitive international environment; (v) skills; and (vi) industry engagement and EU country's commitments (European Commission, 2023b). Explicitly focusing on strengthening European industry actors, the plan also calls for increasing wind power employment. While citizen-led projects might also profit from the aspired easier permitting processes it remains to be seen whether the focus of an accelerated expansion of wind farms "made in Europe" will leave room for small-scale projects.

4.2 Co-Investments and Financial Participation in Wind Energy

4.2.1 Renewable and Citizen Energy Communities

⁶ The REPower EU plan addresses the problem that the amount of time needed to obtain a permit can take up to 9 years (2022a, p. 11).

Research indicates that active involvement in and (co-)ownership of RES significantly enhances acceptance rates (Bauwens et al., 2016; Bauwens & Devine-Wright, 2018; Heldeweg & Saintier, 2020; Lowitzsch et al., 2020; Radtke & Ohlhorst, 2021). Empirical findings confirm that this trend is particularly prevalent in community-based wind energy (Baxter et al., 2020; Grashof, 2019). Accordingly, recital (70) of the RED II underscores the strong correlation between citizen-owned energy and social acceptance of renewables:

"The participation of local citizens and local authorities in renewable energy projects through renewable energy communities has resulted in substantial added value in terms of local acceptance of renewable energy and access to additional private capital which results in local investment, more choice for consumers and greater participation by citizens in the energy transition. Such local involvement is all the more crucial in a context of increasing renewable energy capacity. Measures to allow renewable energy communities to compete on an equal footing with other producers also aim to increase the participation of local citizens in renewable energy projects and therefore increase acceptance of renewable energy."

Emphasising their support of citizen involvement in the transition the European Commission provides the following definition for energy communities:

"Energy communities are legal entities that empower citizens, small businesses and local authorities to produce, manage and consume their own energy. They can cover various parts of the energy value chain, including production, distribution, supply, consumption, and aggregation." (European Commission, 2022b)

In pursuit of these objectives, the RED II and IEMD establish the Renewable Energy Community (REC) and Citizen Energy Community (CEC) as unified governance models for energy communities (Lowitzsch et al., 2020). They perform a step away from formerly highly diverse national regulatory barriers to the adoption of citizen energy initiatives, providing a framework to facilitate the widespread growth of citizen energy across Europe (Krug et al., 2022). Table 13 offers a concise overview of the characteristics of RECs and their delimitation to the more general CEC as defined in the IEMD.

Table 13: Governance models under RED II and IEMD

The new governance model for energy communities under RED II and IEMD.

Criteria	Renewable Energy Communities pursuant to RED II	Citizen Energy Communities as defined in IEMD
Eligibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • natural persons, • Small and medium sized enterprises, • local authorities, incl. municipalities; 	in principle open to all types of entities;
Primary Purpose	"environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders/members or for local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits";	voluntary participation open to all potential members based on non-discriminatory criteria;
Member-ship	voluntary participation open to all potential local members based on non-discriminatory criteria;	voluntary participation open to all potential members based on non-discriminatory criteria;
Ownership and control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the RE project; • is autonomous (no individual shareholder may own more than 33% of the stock). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • effectively controlled by shareholders or members of the project; • limitation for firms included in shareholders controlling entity to those of small/micro size (not medium); • shareholders engaged in large scale commercial activity and for which energy constitutes primary area of activity excluded from control.

Source: Lowitzsch et al., 2020

RECs and CECs encompass the concept of prosumership.⁷ Prosumers have the “right to consume, store or sell RE generated on their premises” (Lowitzsch et al., 2020). Both types of energy communities' primary purpose focusses on environmental, economic, or social community benefits rather than on profits. RECs do this by tying control to the criteria of locality and geographic proximity of their members or shareholders, while approaching with a broader base of eligible participants. This local proximity provision inhibits the search for particularly lucrative locations but usually facilities are built in the region where their members reside (Dröschel et al., 2021). CECs, on the other hand, limit control regarding enterprises by the size of the shareholders (only allowing small and micro enterprises) and their commercial activity and excludes those for which energy constitutes the primary area of activity. Any corporation bigger than small-sized (i.e., also medium sized) is excluded from being amongst the controlling shareholders of a CEC while for RECs medium sized enterprises are permissible in this respect conditional that they are local. These provisions aim to prevent big-scale players to profit from support schemes and the ‘enabling frameworks’ stipulated in the RED II.

The emphasis on local community benefits does not prohibit profit making but may turn out as a disadvantage when applying for financing or participating in an open bidding market with commercial actors. In such cases the

⁷ The artificial word probably first introduced by Alvin Toffler in his book *The Third Wave* (1980) stems from the Latin; as early as 1972 Marshall McLuhan and Barrington Nevitt suggested in their book *Take Today*, (p. 4) that technological progress would transform the consumer into a producer of electricity. They are termed “active consumers” in the IEMD and “renewable self-consumers” in the RED II respectively.

aim focusing on community benefits reflects a structural difference to the incumbent market actors *"in terms of size, ownership structure and the number of projects"* as recital 71 of the RED II puts it. Given the capital-intensive investment in wind energy relative to other renewable energy installations, such as rooftop PV, and the escalating competition within tender processes, pure citizen wind projects are at risk of being crowded out (Grashof, 2019). An additional complication for small-scale citizen projects was flagged within a report of the Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub (2023c): producers of wind turbines might refrain from selling individual turbines, as selling at scale promises to be more profitable.

To guarantee for community actors to play a significant part in wind energy production in the future the award decisions in the current tenders for new projects are of fundamental importance. To ensure not only a level playing field but to take into account this structural difference MS are called upon the RED II to ensure that they can compete *"on equal footing"* energy communities with concrete suggestions in recital 71 of the RED II:

"Measures to offset the disadvantages relating to the specific characteristics of local renewable energy communities in terms of size, ownership structure and the number of projects include enabling renewable energy communities to operate in the energy system and easing their market integration."

In summary, the European legislator identifies the co-investment of citizens as prosumers in general and the support of energy communities in particular as an important driver to increase public acceptance and to foster the energy transition.

4.2.2 RE Auctions – a determinant for community actors?

The transition from guaranteed feed-in tariffs to the implementation of tendering mechanisms has primarily been driven by the aim of reducing costs through competitive market mechanisms. The objective behind the shift was to reduce costs for end consumers (RED II, 2018, p. (19)). This commitment to foster financial efficiency in the RE sector implies significant changes for the competition among groups of energy producers. While Article 22 (7) RED II and Article 65 IEMD request MS to ensure fair competition for support on a level playing field, in their current form national tenders lead to a decrease of the share of citizen energy in onshore wind (Dröschel et al.,

2021; Grashof, 2019). Benefiting from economic advantages, such as professionalised business practices, better access to capital, economies of scale and market experience, large-scale producers have been argued to be systematically favoured in tenders for new wind projects (AURES II, 2020; Dröschel et al., 2021).

Figure 1: Typology of wind projects

Source: Grashof, 2019

Figure 1 illustrates that obtaining equity funding is fundamental for the risky stages of project development preceding the auction. This poses a significant challenge for actors with lower liquidity and limited access to finance (AURES II, 2020).

Figure 1 also shows that citizen wind initiatives can circumvent that issue by joining in at a later project stage, e.g., only in the operation of a plant. But this presents a trade-off between transferring risk and enhancing the potential for procedural and distributive justice through participatory planning procedures. To lower the risk that pure market incentives eradicate the thriving for social acceptance Article 4 (8) (d) and (f) RED II orders the European Commission to regularly report to the Parliament and the Council on safeguarding RE tenders against discriminating small actors (e.g., citizen-led projects) and to focus on ensuring local acceptability. As wind energy has been designated as a matter of "overriding public interest" within the EU, scholars caution that the efforts to streamline permitting processes may further enhance the advantages for commercial actors in auctions (Bucha and Lowitzsch, forthcoming). To mitigate this problem, business models like the CSOP (Lowitzsch, 2019), where commercial actors invest jointly with citizen and municipal actors might provide fertile prospects for facilitating wind power projects as they increase acceptance from the outset by actively involving local actors.

4.3 Possible Constellations of Wind Energy Projects Enhancing acceptance

Already in 2010, the Wind Barriers Report estimated that as many as 40% of wind energy projects in Europe were cancelled due to resistance of local populations filing lawsuits mostly during the EIA phase (EWEA, 2010). While conventional market actors might oppose the expansion of citizen projects as potential competition (Hoicka et al., 2021), they risk substantial cost increases in the project implementation when facing local resistance and NIMBY (Not In My Backyard) protests. Facilitating local ownership does not only enhance local acceptance of new wind projects, but the AURES II report highlights that: "*local engagement processes of RECs can facilitate the land acquisition process and thus ease the often-challenging pre-development of sites, particularly for new wind projects*" (2020, p. 26). Delays in the pre-development phase due to lengthy land acquisition procedures as well as lawsuits trying to prevent non-local investments are mitigated (Dröschel et al., 2021). According to the definitions of energy communities set by the IEMD and RED II these forms of governance open participation for commercial actor that are either micro, small or medium enterprises. Furthermore, within the REC no member is allowed to hold more than 33 % of the stocks. Not be-

ing able to hold a majority of shares and consequently not having the decision-making authority might inhibit the participation of commercial actors. Table 14 provides an overview of the organisational forms and legal structures open to Energy Communities.

Table 14: Legal Structures of Energy Communities

Legal Structure	Description
Energy cooperatives	The most common and fast-growing form of energy communities. This type of ownership primarily benefits its members. It is popular in countries where renewables and community energy are relatively advanced.
Limited partnerships	A partnership may allow individuals to distribute responsibilities and generate profits by participating in community energy. Governance is usually based on the value of each partner’s share, meaning they do not always provide for a one member – one vote.
Community trusts and foundations	Their objective is to generate social value and local development rather than profits for individual members. Profits are used for the community as a whole, even when citizens do not have the means to invest in projects (for-the-public-good companies).
Housing associations	Non-profit associations that can offer benefits to tenants in social housing, although they may not be directly involved in decision-making. These forms are ideal for addressing energy poverty.
Non-profit customer-owned enterprises	Legal structures used by communities that deal with the management of independent grid networks. Ideal for community district heating networks common in countries like Denmark.
Public-private partnerships	Local authorities can decide to enter into agreements with citizen groups and businesses in order to ensure energy provision and other benefits for a community.
Public utility company	Run by municipalities, who invest in and manage the utility on behalf of taxpayers and citizens. These forms are less common, but are particularly suited for rural or isolated areas

Source: European Commission, 2023i

As argued above, financial participation of local stakeholders, be it as co-investors and shareholders, through profit-sharing arrangements or via project related levies can significantly reduce public resistance and thus facilitate project implementation. Building on a data set of 76 best practice cases from 18 countries (Lowitzsch ed., 2019) this section maps possible actor constellations for wind power projects; in this mapping exercise we focus on the cases from the 10 EU Member States and Switzerland.

4.3.1 100% Citizen Projects

This project has received funding from the European Union’s research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author’s view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

While citizen initiatives were the driving forces at the beginning of wind power employment in Europe the distance between communities and wind power investors has been growing with the continuous upscaling of wind projects (Knauf & Wüstenhagen, 2023). As previously discussed in 4.2.2, investments in the wind sector meet significant hindrances for citizen projects. Inherent challenges, from raising sufficient investment capital to manoeuvring permitting procedures even pose challenges for highly professionalized actors. As indicated by the Energy Communities Repository (2023e) available on the European Commission's website, the predominant share of citizen energy projects excludes wind energy but centres around alternative technologies, particularly solar PV.

100% citizen energy communities in the wind sector are therefore mainly long-standing institutions. The example of the *Wildpoldsried Energy Community* in the South of Germany has installed their first citizen wind turbine in 2000, when projects still profited from guaranteed feed-in tariffs, “making the installation economically viable with feed-in tariffs despite the high initial cost” (2023b). For that endeavour and subsequent installations, the citizens of Wildpoldsried had the opportunity to invest capital in a limited partnership. Starting with 30 citizens as limited partners, more than 200 inhabitants invested in the newest wind project (Gemeinde Wildpoldsried, 2023). Within a cooperative governance model each member has one vote and membership is open for SMEs. While being primarily a citizen project the municipality as well as local businesses played a fundamental role in providing favourable conditions for the success of the initiative (The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub, 2023b).

4.3.2 Commercial Wind Project Developer and Majority Citizen Shareholding

Instead of a fully-fledged citizen-led approach from development to operation, citizen initiatives might also have the option to cooperate with a commercial wind developer. In the Netherlands the two largest cooperatives for wind energy generation – Zeeuwind and Deltawind, involving about 5,000 citizens – formed the *Windpark Kramer Limited Liability Company*. While 49% of the *Windpark Kramer BV* (operating 34 turbines with a total of 103 MW installed capacity) is owned by German wind turbine manufacturer Enercon 51% of the shares are held by the *Windpark Kramer LLC* (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

4.3.3 Commercial Wind Project Developer and Minority Citizen Shareholding

A prevalent business model in wind energy production involves commercial investors holding the majority shares, while offering different forms of financial participation to local communities and individuals. For instance, in the French region of Le Mené, inhabitants negotiated a 30% shareholding in a local wind farm constructed by the energy operator Idex. Approximately 140 people have invested in the park, in the form of investment clubs⁸. The rest of the windfarm is owned by the Caisse des Dépôts and Oxyan Energies (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

In Germany the energy provider EnBW offers financial participation in form of shareholding in a project company or as subordinated loans in RE projects. The first option is explicitly open to citizen energy cooperatives, but participation is limited to 49,9% of overall shares, keeping the effective decision-making power in the hands of EnBW (EnBW, 2017, p. 31). The second option is open to citizen in the vicinity of a project. They can participate after the project has been put into operation. Investments starting from 500 EUR run for a fixed term and interest rates (EnBW, 2023).

While those approaches effectively avoid the necessity for the citizens to invest in the risky development phase, active voting rights and democratic governance structures are not implemented. Furthermore, not all residents within the vicinity of a wind project have the financial means to invest. Vulnerable consumers such as low-income households (LIH) are effectively excluded.

This trend of exclusion is not only apparent in the participation in projects developed by commercial wind park operators but has also been scrutinized in community energy (Lowitzsch & Hanke, 2019; Radtke & Ohlhorst, 2021). It is therefore necessary to take inclusive measures as stipulated in RED II Article 21 6 (a) and Article 22 2 (f).

4.3.4 Commercial Actors and Citizen Project

Bringing together citizen and commercial actors promises to upscale available investment capital as well as enhancing the heterogeneity of actors and energy demand patterns. In the Catalonian county of Anoia the mem-

⁸ This new form of investment club is called CIGALES.

bership base of the rural Energy Community EOLPOP encompasses individuals, families and 30 companies and associations. One special feature of the LLC poses the possibility of joint ownership for families and friends. Through the bundling of funds this lowers the barriers for LIH to participate while not being a member of the community itself; here the municipality has also played a crucial role in facilitating the operations (The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub, 2023c).

4.3.5 Commercial Actor and Municipality

In the Netherlands four municipalities together with the energy company HVC Ltd. founded the LLC *Wind Alckmaer BV* as a subsidiary of HVC. The commercial actor holds the majority shares, while the municipalities made financial contributions proportional to their population size (Lowitzsch ed., 2019). Another example is the Italian municipality of Roseto Valfortore. Private investors intended to invest in 2 wind turbines while exiting majority shareholding after 3–4 years to “allow the municipality to become majority shareholder in a public/private ownership structure” (The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub, 2023a, p. 2). Despite those arrangements the municipality had to sell its shares in the end to the investor. After that the municipality pursued a new approach, leading to the establishment of the *Comunità Energetica Rinnovabile di Roseto Valfortore* in 2021. It is a joint venture between the municipality, a community facilitator and researchers from the University of Calabria. It is still in the planning phase of installations, which are envisioned to encompass PV, small-scale wind, microgrid structures and storage tanks.

4.3.6 Municipal Project

An example of a pure municipally financed project is the French *Parc éolien de la régie communale de Montdidier*. The wind farm has a nominal capacity of 8 MW and a production capacity of 19 GWh per year which covers 53 per cent of the annual energy consumption of the city of Montdidier. The project was financed with the help of the European Regional Development Fund, the Regional Council of Picardie, and the General Council of Somme (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

4.3.7 Citizen and Municipality Project

Denmark has been one of the countries where citizen wind pioneered in the 1990. The Middelgrunden Wind Farm poses a prominent example. In 1997 citizens set up the *Middelgrunden Windmill Cooperative* and together with the City of Copenhagen they owned the 20-turbine strong wind farm with each

of the two owning 10 turbines, respectively. While the City sold all its production capacity to the multinational energy company Ørsted half of the Wind Farm is still in the hands of the cooperative (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

4.3.8 SME, Citizen and Municipality

Given the governance provisions concerning eligibility are met (see Table 13) commercial, citizen and municipal actors can jointly form both RECs and CECs. The heterogeneous constituency of those three actor types holds the potential to be technically favourable, by exhibiting complementary demand patterns (Lowitzsch et al., 2020). The local consumption of self-produced energy not only cost-efficient but when employed as a RE cluster it also mitigates the need for an accelerated grid extension. Due to the highly variable local conditions and compositions the development of business models especially regarding value-sharing pose a challenge. While commercial actors and municipalities may not always be directly invested in the wind power installations, they are important facilitators of local wind power projects. Enhancing administrative measures and existing technical know-how is crucial in the establishment of local wind turbines.

An example of such a project, encompassing a diverse membership pool, is the Energy Community *Éolienne citoyenne de Chamole* (France). Participants are the municipality, a purpose-built citizen cooperative, a citizen territorial tool, a regional company, and a national fund. In 2016, the community bought one turbine constructed within a wind park encompassing six turbines from the commercial developer Intervent (Lowitzsch ed., 2019). Another example in France is the Community owned *Béganne wind farm*, an initiative of the local non-profit organization *Eoliennes en Pays de Vilaine*. While it brings together about 800 local citizens, solidarity-based enterprises, regional and national Investment Funds it does not fulfil the requirements of a REC, as the local energy company of Site à Watts obtained 35% of the voting rights, hence posing a blocking minority (Lowitzsch ed., 2019).

4.4 Synthesis of Governance Models

This chapter provided an overview of the governance structure reigning wind energy deployment on the European level, including the Energy Union and the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package, the Fit for 55 Package, the REPowerEU Plan, and the European Wind Power Action Plan. Within the overarching strategy, finding a balance between cost-efficient, rapid expansion

of wind energy and ensuring a socially just and inclusive transition poses as a pivotal challenge. As shown in chapter 4.2, the public interest of a rapid expansion of RE may indeed override local interests and acceptance of local populations. The subsequent chapter provided an overview of governance models already implemented in praxis within the MS. Even though the listing of community energy projects in the EU introduced in Chapter 4.3 does not claim completeness, the analysis of selected cases enhances our understanding of the options for participation in wind energy for European citizens. While these cases offer anecdotal evidence, showcasing the diverse possibilities for engaging local actors, we aim to gather more conclusive information in the future as data becomes more readily available.

5. FINANCING RESOURCES

The most existing financing resources were established around 2021 and there are no data about their impact and their financial support for wind energy. Impact and financial flows are also hard to determine because there is no wind energy-specific financing instrument. Instead, there are programmes which are intended to support economic development in general without information about shares of specific sectors. There are two funds for which there is a bit of specific information regarding wind energy for the period 2014 to 2020 is available: the European Structural and Investment Funds, but the data is (i) incomplete and (ii) outdated since the according regulations were amended for 2021 to 2027. This section does not draw any premature conclusions about the impact of the existing funding programs. Instead, the new instruments will be examined in terms of their institutional embedding, their financial scope, and the eligibility of wind energy projects for funding. To keep the chapter manageable, only those programs that promote wind energy are analysed in the text.

5.1 Institutional & Financial Framework

5.1.1 Institutional Embeddedness

All financing resources for wind energy are part of a larger institutional framework (s. Figure 2) They are all part of the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), the Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS), and NextGenerationEU (NGEU), of which MFF is by far the most important. It is the long-term budget plan of the EU and was set up for 2021 to 2027 (Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093 – MFF, 2020, art. 1).

The MFF's biggest share, financially spoken, is the New Cohesion Policy. It covers three wind energy financing instruments: (1) the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), (2) the Cohesion Fund (CF) and (3) the Just Transition Fund (JTF). The Cohesion Policy of the EU, renewed every several years, is intended to support the economic and social cohesion of territories in the EU by correcting imbalances between them. The New Cohesion Policy for 2021 to 2027 was established by the Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 that defines goals for the ERDF, the CF and the JTF. Next to making the EU more competitive, greener, and more connected, it also aims to make it more inclusive and closer to citizens (Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 – CPR, 2021, art. 5). The objective of becoming “greener” is defined more precisely as *“low-carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy [...] by promoting clean*

and fair energy transition". These goals are relevant because projects are only eligible if they contribute to them.

The JTF is not only part of the New Cohesion policy, but also part of the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM). It has the function to enable regions and people to address the "social, employment, economic and environmental impacts of the transition" (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021a, art. 5). The JTF is complemented by a Just Transition Programme under InvestEU to support private investments and a PSLF to support public investments. Altogether, they build the three pillars of the JTM. The JTM is part of the Green Deal, that is the EU's roadmap to make the European economy more sustainable. The superordinate goals of the Green Deal are becoming climate-neutral in 2050 and protecting the environment. The decarbonization of the energy sector is mentioned as a policy measure to achieve climate neutrality (European Commission, 2019). Despite the JTF is also part of the New Cohesion Policy, it is analysed in the subchapter about the JTM, since it is the mechanism's central pillar.

The budget for the LIFE programme is part of the MMF, too. The ETS Directive establishes the Innovation Fund and the Modernisation Fund. The EU sells allowance certificates to emit CO₂-equivalents in several covered economic sectors, for example, the energy industry. Shares of the revenue from the auctions, in which certificates are sold, are used to finance the Innovation Fund and the Modernisation Fund.

5.1.2 Financial Volumes

The whole budget for the ERDF and the CF is EUR 242 billion in 2018 prices⁹ (Regulation (EU) 2021/1057 - ESF+, 2021, art. 5). EUR 10 billion were transferred from the CF to the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), that is only supporting infrastructure to connect national grids with each other, but no wind energy projects. This reduces the potential funding for wind energy projects to EUR 232 billion with the managing authorities to select supported operations until the end of 2025 (Regulation (EU) 2021/1058 - ERDF and CF, 2021, art. 7 (4)).

⁹ In the contracts, the budget sums are specified at prices in certain years in order to compensate for losses in purchasing power after the regulation has been decided. Constant inflation causes the value of sum X to fall between year A and year B. In order to keep the purchasing power of the budget stable, the sums are given at prices in year A and the nominal budget is expanded by the inflation rate.

The JTF is partly financed by the MMF, that allocates EUR 7.5 billion in 2018 prices to the fund. Another EUR 10 billion for the JTF are part of NextGenerationEU, the pandemic recovery plan of the EU (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021a, art. 109). Thus, the JTF's whole budget is EUR 17.5 billion in 2018 prices. The EU budget for the whole InvestEU programme is EUR 26.2 billion at prices in 2021 for guarantees (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021, art. 4 (1)). There is no defined budget share of guarantees dedicated to the just transition scheme. The grant component of the PSLF is financed by the MMF with EUR 250 million. The European Commission expects to mobilise around EUR 55 billion between 2021 and 2027 under these three pillars.

Around 530 million allowances shall be auctioned to finance the Innovation Fund and the Modernisation Fund, which is only a share of the quantity of sold allowances. At an assumed carbon price of EUR 75 per tonne, the volume of the Innovation Fund is at EUR 40 billion for the period from 2020 to 2030. The budget for the calls for the Innovation Fund launched in 2023 was EUR 4 billion. The fund succeeded the NER300 programme, which was set up for the time between 2013 and 2020, but with a much lower budget of about EUR 2 billion for the whole period. According to the Directive, *"2 % of the total quantity of allowances between 2021 and 2030 shall be auctioned to establish"* the Modernisation Fund. At the assumed carbon price of EUR 75 per tonne, the budget is expected to be around EUR 48 billion.

Figure 2: Overview of the EU funding instruments relevant to the deployment of wind power across Europe

5.2 Eligibility of Wind Energy by Financing Resources

5.2.1 European Structural and Investment Funds

The ERDF and the CF are both based on Regulation (EU) 2021/158. According to Art. 3 of the Regulation, “promoting renewable energy in accordance with Directive (EU) 2018/2001” is one of the specific objectives of the ERDF. The Directive (RED II) defines renewable energy as “energy from renewable non-fossil sources, namely wind [...]” in Art. 2. The scope of the CF is, among others, to support “investments related to [...] energy presenting environmental benefits, with a particular focus on renewable energy” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021c, art. 6). Common outputs and result indicators for both funds regarding the cohesion policy’s goals are set out in the annex of the regulation. The two typical common outputs set out for promoting RE are “additional production capacity for renewable energy” and “renewable energy communities supported”. The success indicator is the “total renewable energy produced” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021c, app. Annex I).

Thus, promoting wind energy is generally eligible by the ERDF and the CF. According to the goal of strengthening cohesion between less and more developed regions, the CF only supports investments in countries with a gross national income (GNI) per inhabitant less than 90% of the EU average. Eligible countries for the period from 2021 to 2027 are Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia.

There is some data on how much money from cohesion policy from 2014 to 2020 have been earmarked by states for wind energy, how much of this has been approved by the EU and how much has been spent (Table 15). The larger share of the EU-wide planned budget for wind energy (~81%) were planned in by applications to the ERDF. The other ~19% were planned in by applications to the CF. The applications for the CF came exclusively from Poland and Slovenia.

Table 15: Cohesion Data regarding Wind Energy Projects, 2014 to 2020; Refresh Date: 14.09.2023; in EUR mil; Source: European Commission (Cohesion Data).

Country	Planned (100%)	Decided*	Spent
Spain	130	269 (207%)	11 (9%)

Poland	107	20 (19%)	10 (10%)
United Kingdom	51	6,1 (12%)	1,1 (2%)
France	18	6,3 (35%)	0
Interreg	16	2,5 (16%)	1,1 (7%)
Slovenia	2	5,7 (289%)	0
Italy	1,8	0	0
Czechia	1,7	3,2 (188%)	0
Sweden	1,4	0	0
Lithuania	1,2	0	0
Germany	0,85	0	0
Finland	0,75	0,33 (44%)	0,28 (37%)
Netherlands	0,56	0	0

* Some programmes award support to a volume of projects that exceeds the total planned cost of the programme. This explains why the sum under “decided” can be more than 100% of the sum under “planned”.

As of December 2023, the available information for the period from 2014 to 2020 is still incomplete and does not allow an evaluation of the contemporary funding policy of the EU as the data. Although this information was announced to be updated by September 2023 the figures in Table 15 are still not final; we will update them in the final version, i.e. deliverable 2.10. Concerning the cohesion data for the period from 2021 to 2027, no equivalent data on financial volumes flowing into wind energy investments are available yet. In contrast to the data from 2014 to 2020, there is no specific data category for wind energy. It is only possible to take insight into budget flowing into renewable energy in general.

A study from 2022 of RE projects in Poland funded by the EU’s cohesion policy (Florkowski and Rakowska, 2022, pp. 10–12) seems to have the same data problem. Although it was published in 2022, only data from 2007 to 2015 were used. About 13% (88 projects) of all supported RE projects involved wind installations. Regarding all types of RE projects, SMEs and local governments dominated the group of applicants to the programme. It is unclear whether the results can be generalized for the whole EU, but they could be an indicator that the funds are especially attractive for local projects.

5.2.2 Just Transition Mechanism

The mechanism's function, formulated by the Commission, is to support regions, sectors, and workers most affected by the transition. Three pillars were set up for this purpose: (a) the Just Transition Fund, (b) the Just Transition Scheme under InvestEU and (c) the Public Sector Loan Facility.

5.2.2.1 Just Transition Fund

Pursuant to Article 8, Par. 1 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/156, all sort of activities which are directly linked the specific objective of the fund can be supported. The specific objective of the fund, defined in Art. 2 of the regulation, is to enable *"regions and people to address the social, employment, economic and environmental impacts of the transition"* towards the Union's climate targets. MS can transfer national resources, allocated to them from those funds to investments supported by the Just Transition Fund in this way blending EU funding.

In accordance with this general goal, potentially support-worthy activities are further specified in Art. 8, Par. 2 of the Regulation. Some of the enumerated activities of the paragraph are highly relevant for the funding of local energy initiatives. Under letters (a) and (b), investments in and the creation of new firms are eligible for funding by the Just Transition Fund, if they lead to economic diversification and job creation. Letter (d) defines investments in the deployment of technology and infrastructures for affordable clean energy as eligible for funding. Energy storage technologies and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions are included. Under letter (e), investments in renewable energy and energy efficiency, including for the purposes of reducing energy poverty, are declared as eligible by the Just Transition Fund. Heating systems can be supported if they are supplied exclusively by renewable energy sources (g). Technical assistance (n) is also eligible by the Just Transition Fund.

Some other eligible activities are not directly linked to the building of RE installations but create a context in which it could be easier to found and maintain local energy projects. For example, the eligibility of investments for upskilling (k), job-search assistance (l) and active inclusion (m) of jobseekers can be used to tackle the problem of lacking qualified workers to install and maintain renewable energy plants by building a regional training centre

for mechanics. This would also address the superordinated goal of addressing job losses in regions with large fossil fuel industries. MS had to prepare Territorial Just Transition Plans (TJTPs) to implement resources of the Just Transition Fund (European Commission, 2021, art. 11). The mechanism is the same as with the other Cohesion Policy Funds: National governments develop programmes and submit their plans to the EU. There are unfortunately no reports of the EU or studies in the academic literature about the current outcome of the JTF. The JTF additionally lacks similar predecessors, as it is the first funding instrument of the EU that is dedicated to a Just Transition. A case study of the development of the JTF concludes that this it is the result of pressure by Eastern Europe countries, especially Poland (Kyriazi and Miró, 2023).

5.2.2.2 Just Transition Scheme under InvestEU

The programme InvestEU exists independently of the JTM in general but contains a just transition scheme. The programme's general goal is to boost private investments by providing guarantees in four different policy windows of which the first policy describes, among others, investments in sustainable infrastructure *"in energy, in particular renewable energy"* as scope of the programme (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021, art. 8 (1)). InvestEU is intertwined with the JTM. A just transition scheme shall be established across all four policy windows (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021d, art. 8 (2)). The just transition scheme shall declare guarantees for investments which are part of TJTPs. Therefore, wind energy projects, in general and specifically if supported by the JTF, are eligible for the programme.

5.2.2.3 Public Sector Loan Facility (PSLF)

The main function of the PSLF is to leverage public financing. Only legal entities which are a "public law body" or which are "established as a body governed by private law entrusted with a public service mission" are eligible (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 10). Eligible projects must contribute to the facility's objective set out in Article 3 of the Regulation (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 9), i.e., addressing *"social, economic and environmental challenges deriving from the transition towards the Union's 2030 climate and energy targets [...], for the benefit of the Union territories identified in the*

TJTPs” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 3). The main funding mechanism, as the title of the programme indicates, are loans. They are provided by the European Investment Bank (EIB) or other “financial partner, which are selected by the EIB according to specific criteria (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 15). The grant’s amount shall not exceed 15% (25% in less developed regions) of the loan provided by the EIB or selected financial partners (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 11).

5.2.3 Innovation Fund & Modernisation Fund (2021 - 2030)

The Innovation Fund and the Modernisation Fund are financed with revenue from the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS). The legal framework of both funds is the Directive (EU) 2003/87/EC, which establishes the ETS. The Innovation Fund is intended to decarbonize the sectors which are covered by the ETS. Next to others, emissions of energy industries are covered by the ETS. Renewable energy investments decarbonize the energy sector. Consequently, renewable energy generation can be supported by the Innovation Fund. The support can be provided in form of grants or technical assistance. Up to 60 % of the investment cost can be covered by grants from the Innovation Fund and up to 100 % in cases of competitive bidding or technical assistance. Support is only possible if the investors cannot implement their investment “under normal market conditions” (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003, art. 10a (8)).

Projects can be subsidized, if they support avoiding emissions and boost competitiveness in energy intensive industries, renewable energy production, energy storage, carbon capture or net-zero projects in the housing or mobility sector. An amendment of the operation of the Innovation fund renewed the mentioned projects size categories. From November 2023 on, the projects are categorized in the sizes small-, medium- and large-scale. All projects with a total capital expenditure up to EUR 20 mil are regarded as small-scale. Medium projects have a total capital expenditure from EUR 20 mil to 100 mil. All projects with a higher total capital expenditure than 100 mil are regarded as large-scale (European Commission, 2023h, art. 1).

The Innovation Fund Progress Report from August 2022 contains the results of the first two project calls, which were launched in 2020. Only one of seven awarded large-scale projects (total capital expenditure: > EUR 7.5 million) addressed renewable power generation (European Commission, 2022c, p. 14). Eleven of 30 awarded small-scale projects (total capital expenditure: <

EUR 7.5 million) addressed the production of renewable energy. In both categories, more projects applied than could be funded. In general, the EU assumes to mobilize four times the Innovation Fund's budget in a policy proposal from June 2023. According to the document, the assumption is based on the given experience under the fund (European Commission, 2023i).

Since the Innovation fund is primarily targeting industry companies, its usefulness for local community projects is limited. It could at most be used to financially support small- or medium-sized industry companies which aim to be part of a local energy communities. Specific calls for small-scale projects support the targeting for actors with limited access to finance. Nonetheless, the budget is small: If only 41 projects were awardable in the whole period from 2020 to 2021, the fund is obviously no broad-based supply of finance for small and/or local projects. As individual modern wind turbines cost two to four million euros, community projects would still have to finance large portions themselves.

The Modernisation Fund is intended to support MS with a GDP per capita below 60 % of the EU average in 2013. Eligible MS are Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Croatia, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003, art. 10). MS shall support small-scale investments to modernise energy systems and improve energy efficiency. The generation and use of renewable sources are mentioned explicitly. This also applies to support for low-income households to address energy poverty and a just transition in carbon-dependent regions (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003, art. 10d).

5.2.4 LIFE Clean Energy Transition Sub-Programme

The LIFE programme in general is intended to contribute to a more sustainable economy. Part of Art. 3, where the objectives of the programme are laid out, is the "transition to renewable energy" (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021f). All types of legal entities in the European Union are eligible (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021f, art. 12). The LIFE Programme is implemented for the period from 2021 to 2027. The whole budget is EUR 5.4 billion. The share of the subprogramme "Clean Energy Transition" is EUR 997 million in 2021 prices (European Parlia-

ment and Council of the European Union, 2021e, art. 5). The money is disbursed in the form of grants (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2021d, art. 6). There are no available reports of the effects and results of the LIFE programme.

Additionally, the Commission proposes to allocate additional 10 billion EUR to existing financing programmes, of which two are relevant for wind energy deployment: The InvestEU Fund is expected to be expanded with another 3 billion EUR and the Innovation Fund with 5 billion EUR. The Commission expects to crowd in 87 billion EUR for eligible projects by expanding both programmes (European Commission, 2023a). It is necessary to consider that wind energy deployment is only a share of the eligible projects of both instruments.

5.3 Conclusions

The lack of data does not allow any conclusions about the impact of the programmes. With more data becoming available we hope to be able to assess the how useful the financing resources are employed for wind energy (this is expected for D2.10 in M24). In principle, however, we note that there are a variety of ways to support wind energy investments in the form of grants, loans or guarantees. The next years will show whether the programs have an effect and which actors will use them.

There is also potential for updates of single instruments. At this moment, there is a proposal for the programme “Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform” (STEP) by the European Commission from June 2023. Next to boosting production capacities for renewable energy installations, the policy contains expansions of existing funds: Another EUR 3 billion will be allocated to InvestEU, resulting in an expected EUR 75 billion of private investments. Additionally EUR 5 billion will be allocated to the Innovation Fund, which could result in the mobilisation of EUR 20 billion given the experience to date (European Commission, 2023a).

6 Job Creation In The Wind Power Industry – Results

6.2 Results of the literature review

The proposed literature search resulted in 526 unique references. From these 162 references were considered pertinent and 67 were ultimately used for data collection in the literature review after a thorough assessment. Exclusions were made for various reasons: 8 articles were in a different language, 2 articles were inaccessible, and 85 articles lacked job creation data. During the review, it was observed that multiple articles presented identical job creation quantities. This redundancy arose from articles utilizing the same data from other sources, exemplified by Simas & Pacca (2014) and Vasconcellos & Caiado Couto (2021). The report by Rutovitz et al. (2015), although not retrieved from the literature search, was manually added due to being used in multiple references. Two additional articles suggested by organizations during interviews were also manually included. Consequently, the total literature review encompasses 165 references, with 70 providing useful data. Data from articles using employment factors from Simas & Pacca (2014) and Rutovitz et al. (2015) was documented but excluded from the regression analysis to prevent double counting. Similarly, data from articles by Okkonen & Lehtonen (2016), Greene & Geisken (2013) and Ejdemo & Söderholm (2015) was documented but not used in the regression analysis due to their focus on specific towns or regions.

Annex B offers a comprehensive overview of all collected data points, showcasing variations in job sectors, types, and quantification units. Some articles provided total values without specifying individual job sectors, while others focused solely on the construction phase, encompassing development, construction, and manufacturing. Job creation values for all three job types (direct, indirect, and induced) were limited, with some articles presenting total values without breakdowns. Quantification units varied, with jobs/MW and job-years/MW being the most common. All data was converted to job-years, adjusting for variations in job duration. The job duration per sector ranged from a few years to 5 years for development, half a year to 2.5 years for construction and manufacturing, 20 to 40 years for O&M, and 1 to 3 years for decommissioning. If jobs were quantified in jobs/MW, com-

monly used durations were applied, such as 1 year for construction, manufacturing, and decommissioning, 3 years for development, and 25 years for O&M. Figure 3 illustrates the duration ranges for different job sectors identified in the literature.

Figure 3: Job sectors and their duration range

In addition to variations in job sectors, types, and units, a limited number of articles provided detailed descriptions of wind parks. Some distinguished between onshore and offshore wind, while others only offered an EF for wind energy in general. Furthermore, not all articles included specifics about the wind farm, such as the number of turbines, turbine capacity, or total capacity. The reference year for the EF also lacked consistency, with the publishing year being used as a reference if no clear year was specified.

Beyond job creation quantities, attention was given to the local nature of job creation. The data revealed the proportion of jobs created locally and internationally, detailed in Appendix B. Additionally, two articles delved into the educational requirements of jobs in the wind power industry. Swift et al. (2019) found that 79.9% of the worker profile in the wind power industry had vocational training, and 27.1% held a university degree. Pegels & Lütkenhorst (2014) specified that manufacturing, construction, and operation and maintenance jobs required 14%, 6%, and 17% university degree workers, respectively.

6.3 Results from the statistic and regression analysis

This section presents the outcomes of distinct statistic and regression analyses conducted for each job sector. The independent variables considered in the regression analysis encompassed an Onshore/Offshore dummy (OS), locations per continent that could be Europe (EU), North America (NA), South

America (SA), Asia (AS), Africa (AF), turbine capacity (TC), number of turbines (Nr.T), and reference year (RY). In case no significant regression was found descriptive statistics were kept for the model development.

6.3.2 Statistics of the wind park development stage

Only five different data points were found in literature for the development stage of wind energy. The statistics for direct, indirect, induced and total jobs are presented in Table 15: Direct, indirect, induced & total EFs for the development stage. Values provided in job-years/MW The induced jobs are only based on two different values resulting in similar average and median values.

Table 15: Direct, indirect, induced & total EFs for the development stage. Values provided in job-years/MW

Development	Direct jobs	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	0.21	0.26	0.48	1.34
Max	1.41	1.09	0.70	2.37
Average	0.69	0.59	0.59	1.86
Median	0.58	0.41	0.59	1.58
St.dev	0.52	0.44	0.16	0.73

6.3.3 Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage

Table 16 summarizes significant regressions for direct, indirect, and induced jobs during the construction phase. While these are significant and have rather high R^2 constructing the model with them will lead to unrealistic (negative) EF when turbines are larger than 2.4 MW. Consequently, job creation for indirect and induced jobs in this study relies on minimum, maximum, and average values as shown in Table 17.

Table 16: Significant EF regressions for the construction stage

Dependent variable	Obs.	Int. coef	Int. P-value	Independent variable(s) coef	Independent variable(s) P-value	Regres. sig F	R ²	St.dev
Direct jobs run 1	48	11.281	8E-10	OS) -5.477 EU) -4.454 NA) -4.295	OS) 2E-06 EU) 0.0028 NA) 0.0006	9E-07	0.502	2.561
Direct jobs run 2	46	9.457	3E-11	OS) -3.653 EU) -4.072 NA) -4.372	OS) 2E-05 EU) 0.0002 NA) 3E-06	2E-07	0.551	1.801

Direct jobs run 3	18	13.560	0.0005	Nr.T) 0.000353 TC) -1.803 OS) -9.402 EU) 7.159	Nr.T) 0.0041 TC) 0.0070 OS) 0.0010 EU) 0.0176	9.6E-05	0.819	1.772
Indirect jobs run 1	8	20.769	0.00059	TC) -2.136 OS) -15.463	TC) 0.0247 OS) 0.0064	0.0106	0.838	1.681
Indirect jobs run 2	8	5.306	0.01275	TC) -2.136 EU) 15.463	TC) 0.0247 EU) 0.0064	0.0106	0.838	1.681
Induced jobs run 1	7	11.787	0.00508	TC) -1.026 OS) -9.125	TC) 0.0309 OS) 0.0046	0.0044	0.933	0.777
Induced jobs run 2	7	2.662	0.01768	TC) -1.026 EU) 9.125	TC) 0.0309 EU) 0.0046	0.0044	0.933	0.777

Table 17: Indirect, induced and total EFs for the construction stage. Values provided in job-years/MW

Construction	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	0.08	0.15	0.48
Max	11.10	14.40	44.30
Average	3.08	4.16	9.11
Median	2.11	1.50	3.32
St.dev	2.70	4.98	13.55

6.3.4 Statistics and regressions of the wind park manufacturing stage

Table 18 outlines three significant regressions for direct jobs in the manufacturing sector. Direct run 1 considers only the onshore/offshore dummy variable, yielding an EF of 13.37 job-years/MW for offshore wind and 3.87 job-years/MW for onshore wind. Direct run 2, involving turbine capacity, EU, and reference year, raises concerns due to high negative intercept values and is based on only 6 observations, two of which feature outdated and non-representative turbine capacities. Consequently, run 2 is not usable for job creation projection. The direct and indirect jobs combined regression, significant for the reference year and the location AS, exhibits a high negative intercept value, suggesting an undue influence of the reference year on the EF. This renders the regression unsuitable for projecting job creation. Therefore, only direct jobs run 1 is considered for projecting direct job creation, while indirect and induced jobs rely on their minimum, maximum, and average values, as depicted in Table 19.

Table 18: Significant EF regressions for the manufacturing stage

Dependent variable	Obs.	Int. coef	Int. P-value	Independent variable(s) coef	Independent variable(s) P-value	Regres. sig F	R ²	St.dev
Direct jobs run 1	24	13.366	9.8E-16	OS) -9.496	OS) 1E-05	1E-05	0.595	3.964
Direct jobs run 2	6	-826.4	0.00463	TC) -1.814 EU) 7.292 RY) 0.414	TC) 0.0066 EU) 0.0057 RY) 0.0046	0.0119	0.992	0.336
Direct jobs run 3	6	-282.5	0.0146	TC) -1.916 OS) -10.152 RY) 0.149	TC) 0.0078 OS) 0.0068 RY) 0.0134	0.0144	0.990	0.370
Direct + in-direct jobs	10	-2926	0.0132	RY) 1.456 AS) -47.689	RY) 0.0129 AS) 0.0202	0.0355	0.615	8.377

Table 19: Indirect, induced & total EFs for the manufacturing stage. Values provided in job-years/MW.

Manufacturing	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	2.26	3.20	1.25
Max	16.90	4.10	39.40
Average	5.68	3.65	14.77
Median	3.89	3.65	10.99
St.dev	4.55	0.64	13.09

6.3.5 Statistics and regressions of the wind park operation and maintenance stage

Five significant regressions emerged from the analysis of operation and maintenance jobs, with two focusing on direct jobs (run 1 and run 2 in Table 20). Both regressions considered turbine capacity, EU, NA, and AS as independent variables, with significant values for EU, NA, and AS in both runs. Run 2, which included a 25-year job duration for an outlier data point, exhibited a higher R² and lower standard deviation, indicating a better fit. While the P-value for turbine capacity is slightly above our significance boundary, run 2 was deemed the best fit and utilized in the model. Only one significant regression was identified for indirect jobs, emphasizing turbine capacity as a key variable. However, due to a non-significant intercept P-value, this regression was excluded from the model. Two significant regressions surfaced for induced jobs, but run 2 was omitted due to an implausible negative EF for wind parks commissioned before 2007. Consequently, induced jobs in the

model are based on the minimum, maximum, and average values presented in Table 21.

Table 20: Significant EF regression for the O&M stage

Dependent variable	Obs.	Int. coef	Int. P-value	Independent variable(s) coef	Independent variable(s) P-value	Regres. sig F	R ²	St.dev
Direct jobs run 1	25	18.835	0.0013	TC) 1.5598 EU) -19.05 NA) -19.34 AS) -19.29	TC) 0.0507 EU) 0.0128 NA) 0.0016 AS) 0.0073	0.0121	0.4588	5.0183
Direct jobs run 2	25	19.382	8E-06	TC) 0.91638 EU) -15.74 NA) -18.83 AS) -17.59	TC) 0.0722 EU) 0.0022 NA) 2.2E-05 AS) 0.0004	0.0002	0.6531	3.2291
Indirect jobs	10	-0.950	0.5526	TC) 1.7145	TC) 0.0031	0.0031	0.6855	2.7272
Induced jobs run 1	11	-1.544	0.2881	TC) 1.9645	TC) 0.00062	0.00062	0.7452	2.6659
Induced jobs run 2	15	-3554	0.0297	RY) 1.7703	RY) 0.0293	0.0293	0.3157	15.733

Table 21: Direct, indirect, induced and total EFs for the O&M stage. Values provided in job-years/MW.

O&M	Direct jobs	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	0.90	0.20	1.00	2.63
Max	52.50	63.50	71.50	46.30
Average	7.87	9.36	12.53	15.56
Median	5.00	5.00	4.94	9.81
St.dev	7.87	13.07	18.72	14.61

6.3.6 Statistics and regressions of the wind park decommissioning stage

For decommissioning, only six data points were available for regression analysis, limiting the variables to reference year, location, onshore/offshore designation, and total wind park capacity for direct jobs. Despite the small dataset, the regression was significant for direct decommissioning jobs based on whether the wind park was onshore or offshore, as indicated by the coefficients and P-values in Table 22. The high R² value (0.988) and low standard deviation stem from data points closely aligned, possibly due to adaptations of values from Rutovitz et al. (2015) in four out of six observations.

Table 22: Significant EF regression for the decommissioning stage

Dependent variable	Obs.	Int. coef	Int. P-value	Independent variable(s) coef	Independent variable(s) P-value	Regres. sig F	R ²	St.dev
Direct jobs	6	2.8225	8.1E-06	OS) -2.111	OS) 5.8E-05	5.8E-05	0.988	0.136

Due to limited data availability, regression analysis for indirect jobs (based on 2 data points) and induced and total jobs (based on 1 data point) was not feasible. Consequently, indirect jobs rely on the average value, while induced and total jobs are solely based on a single value. Refer to Table 23 for the minimum, maximum, and average values for indirect, induced, and total jobs.

Table 23: Indirect, induced & total EFs for the decommissioning stage. Values provided in job-years/MW

Decommissioning	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	0.615	1.005	4.275
Max	1.186	1.005	4.275
Average	0.901	1.005	4.275
Median	0.901	1.005	4.275
St.dev	0.404	-	-

6.3.7 Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage

Limited data clarity arose regarding the inclusion of the development stage in references providing job creation quantities for the construction phase. Some references broadly referred to job sectors such as development, construction, and manufacturing, while others specifically mentioned construction and manufacturing. This lack of consistency, combined with the amalgamation of these diverse job sectors, compromises the model's granularity. Consequently, the significant regressions derived from this combined approach have not been incorporated into the model. Table 24 provides the minimum, maximum, and average values for various job types, facilitating a comparison with aggregated development, construction, and manufacturing jobs.

Table 24: Direct, indirect, induced & total EFs construction phase. Values provided in job-years/MW

Construction phase	Direct jobs	Indirect jobs	Induced jobs	Total jobs
Min	2.24	2.79	2.80	16.92
Max	18.10	25.70	12.27	52.00
Average	8.35	12.53	7.22	31.89
Median	8.60	9.63	6.90	29.80
St.dev	4.22	9.38	4.03	12.67

6.3.8 Statistics and regressions of the wind park construction stage

Job creation in the wind energy sector exhibits variations across different project stages. The development and decommissioning phases primarily contribute to job creation at local and national levels. Construction and operation and maintenance (O&M) jobs are predominantly localized or national, often displaying a significant local share. For instance, studies such as Vasconcellos & Caiado Couto (2021) reported a 90% local job share for construction and O&M, with an overall national share of 95%. In the case of direct O&M jobs, the share can be as high as 100% locally (Slattery et al., 2011).

In contrast, manufacturing jobs have the potential to be created both nationally and internationally, depending on the presence of major manufacturing organizations. The distinction between national and international creation of manufacturing jobs hinges on the presence of large manufacturing organizations. In 2017, the global top 10 wind turbine manufacturers included five European companies (Vestas, SGRE, Enercon, Nordex, and Senvion) (Lacal-Arántegui, 2019). By 2019, only three European manufacturers remained in the top 10 – Vestas, SGRE, and Nordex – as Enercon lost market share, and Senvion declared bankruptcy (Gönül et al., 2021). Vestas, SGRE, and Nordex, located in Denmark, Spain, and Germany, respectively, are considered European manufacturers. Enercon, based in Germany, is also included. Hence, manufacturing jobs in these countries are deemed nationally created. If a wind park is established in another European country, manufacturing jobs are considered internationally created, with the possibility that some of these jobs originate in Germany, Denmark, or Spain.

Table 25 presents a detailed breakdown of where jobs are assumed to be created for each job sector.

Table 25: Location of the job creation per job sector

Job sectors	Locational nature
Development	Local/national
Construction	Local/national
Manufacturing	National/international
Operation and maintenance	Local/national
Decommissioning	Local/national

Source: Simas & Pacca, 2014

6.4 A model to estimate job creation

6.4.2 Job creation model input

The significant and applicable regressions identified in the regression analysis were incorporated into the job quantification model. In cases where no (significant) regression was found, the average value obtained from the literature was utilized. To establish a job creation range, the model includes the average value plus or minus one standard deviation, as presented in Table 26. If the average minus one standard deviation falls below the lowest value obtained from the data, the minimum value is employed instead. All utilized regressions in the model are expressed in equations 4 to 7. The international character of the data collection process would allow to estimate values in and outside of Europe. Since WIMBY only has European coverage equations 4 and 6 are simplified assuming that the wind parks are located in Europe.

$$EF_{con,dir} = 9.46 - (3.65 \times OS) - (4.01) \tag{4}$$

$$EF_{manu,dir} = 13.37 - (9.50 \times OS) \tag{5}$$

$$EF_{o\&m,dir} = 19.38 + (0.92 \times TC) - (15.74) \tag{6}$$

$$EF_{decom,dir} = 2.82 - (2.11 \times OS) \tag{7}$$

Where TC is the turbine capacity in MW, and OS is a dummy variable having a value of 1 or 0. As a result, job creation is projected based on whether the park is onshore or offshore and on the turbine capacity. Multiplying by the amount of MW to be installed will provide the total job creation for the park.

Table 26: EF model input (range) values (job-years/MW)

	-1 St.dev	Average	+1 St.dev
Development			

Direct	0.21	0.69	1.21
Indirect	0.26	0.59	1.03
Induced	0.48	0.59	0.70
Construction			
Indirect	0.38	3.08	5.78
Induced	0.15	4.16	9.14
Manufacturing			
Indirect	2.26	5.68	10.23
Induced	3.20	3.65	4.10
O&M			
Indirect	0.20	9.36	22.43
Induced	1.00	12.53	31.25
Decommissioning			
Indirect	0.62	0.90	1.19
Induced	1.01	1.01	1.01

6.4.3 Model based estimations

The model calculates the EF for various wind parks, and for comparison, results are displayed for 5 MW wind turbines, a capacity within the range of current onshore and offshore wind turbines (Enevoldsen & Xydis, 2019). Figure 4 illustrates the different EFs for all job types and sectors concerning a 5 MW offshore wind turbine in the EU. While maintaining the wind turbine capacity at 5 MW but considering different locations, onshore and offshore, leads to slight variations in EFs for direct job types and sectors. Nevertheless, the development sector EFs and all indirect and induced EFs for other job sectors remain consistent. Only the direct EFs for the construction, manufacturing, O&M, and decommissioning sectors undergo changes. The total EFs (range) for 5 MW wind turbines at onshore or offshore locations are summarized in Table 27.

Comparing a 5 MW onshore wind turbine with a 5 MW offshore wind turbine reveals a total difference of 15 job-years/MW (Table 27). This disparity is primarily driven by significantly more manufacturing job-years/MW for offshore wind turbines compared to onshore wind turbines. Additionally, direct construction and decommissioning EFs for offshore are more than three times that of direct onshore EFs, although the absolute difference is smaller than in manufacturing EFs.

Figure 4: Direct, indirect and induced EFs (job-years/MW) for a 5 MW offshore wind turbine in the EU

Table 27: Total EFs range (job-years/MW) for a 5 MW wind turbine at different locations

	Offshore EU	Onshore EU
Total – st.dev	30.46	16.25
Total	72.06	56.80
Total + st.dev	127.02	111.76

Historically, wind turbine capacities were considerably smaller, with onshore capacities starting at 1 MW and offshore capacities at 1.5 MW in 1998 (Enevoldsen & Xydis, 2019). Forecasts indicate that future wind turbine capacities will rise to 8 MW for onshore and 10 to 15 MW for offshore installations (Nejad et al., 2022). To illustrate the differences in job creation shares, Figure 5 (onshore) and Figure 6 (offshore) present comparisons for 2 MW, 8 MW, and 12 MW wind turbines in the EU.

A notable trend is the consistently higher O&M share of total jobs for onshore wind, regardless of turbine capacity. Conversely, offshore wind exhibits a higher manufacturing share of total jobs than onshore wind. Moreover, the figures demonstrate that larger turbines, both onshore and offshore, have a higher O&M job share in total jobs. This is attributed to the model's dependency of O&M jobs on turbine capacity, resulting in more job-years/MW for larger wind turbines in the O&M stage.

Figure 5: Total job sector shares for 2, 8 & 12 MW onshore wind turbines in the EU

Figure 6: Total job sector shares for 2, 8 & 12 MW offshore wind turbines in the EU

6.4.4 Model validation based on interviews

Job duration values, as obtained from interviews, align closely with those used in the model. The construction and manufacturing stage typically lasts 1 to 2 years, the development stage spans 5 to 7 years, and the O&M stage extends over 20 years with a life extension of a few years. While no specific value was gathered for the decommissioning stage during interviews, the model incorporates average values due to a scarcity of data in this sector.

The model's assumptions regarding the international creation of manufacturing jobs are confirmed by the interviews. Manufacturing jobs are likely to be created internationally. The regression analysis also supports this by finding no significant values for location variables, suggesting consistent job creation per MW, regardless of the turbine's location.

Interviews indicate that construction jobs are mostly created nationally, with some potential for international creation, especially for lower-skilled flex

jobs. However, finding highly skilled personnel locally is challenging, leading to more national than local job creation. O&M jobs, requiring highly skilled individuals, also see low local job creation, with most jobs being created nationally.

Induced jobs, such as those in restaurants, lodging, and car rentals, have a higher likelihood of being created locally. Development jobs are typically created locally, as developers prefer working with local stakeholders. Larger wind parks may exhibit some efficiency increase during construction, but the larger budget available for larger projects can offset this effect by hiring more employees.

Scaling effects during the construction stage, as indicated by interviews, are influenced by locational complexity and a larger budget for larger wind parks. For the development stage, limited scaling effects are expected, with more pronounced differences between onshore and offshore. Offshore wind, being more complex, requires a larger development team, as well as more highly skilled employees, consistent with the model's findings.

Regarding decommissioning, the model relies on average values due to a lack of data. Interviews suggest that the decommissioning sector is not yet mature, with no clear strategy for recycling wind turbines. Future developments and increased volumes may alter the job creation potential in the decommissioning sector.

6.4.5 Job creation model limitations

The research findings should be interpreted within the framework of certain model and research limitations. Firstly, the quantification of jobs is based on an employment factor measured in job-years/MW, capturing additional job creation over the entire lifetime of wind parks rather than offering an instantaneous total employee count. For example, decommissioning jobs are only generated at the end of a wind park's lifespan.

Secondly, the decommissioning sector's employment factor is subject to potential fluctuations as only a limited number of wind parks have been decommissioned to date. Future decommissioning activities may significantly alter this factor, though its impact on total jobs remains relatively small, comprising only a fraction of the overall employment.

The scarcity of data represents a primary constraint on the research. Limited information on decommissioning and development sectors, in particular,

hindered comprehensive regression analyses on multiple independent variables. Insufficient data points for various combinations made it impractical to conduct regression analyses.

Additionally, the model encompasses only the five principal job sectors, potentially underestimating actual job creation. For instance, other studies have considered transportation separately, but its contribution remains minimal. Data uncertainty is another limitation, addressed by providing a job creation range. Yet, assumptions regarding job duration homogeneity across locations might introduce a degree of uncertainty.

Finally, the model offers distinctions only for countries with large manufacturers and countries without manufacturers due to data constraints. Providing finer location differentiations is not feasible with data that is publicly available. Improving this will highly depend on manufacturers, project developers, O&M companies and decommissioning companies systematically making this information publicly available, which is beyond the scope of WIMBY.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The aspirations of European policymakers to move forward into a net-zero future has been enshrined in various legal acts, intended to accelerate RE development. In this light, the fast expansion of wind energy poses a fundamental factor in the success of this vision. Within the overarching strategy, striking a balance between a cost-efficient, rapid expansion of wind energy and ensuring a socially just and inclusive transition remains a critical challenge. While the complex regulatory frameworks across multiple levels of governance within the European Union provide facilitative approaches, implementation in practice encounters challenges. This concerns in particular the inclusion of local actors, and here especially vulnerable groups like low-income households. While broad enabling concepts and governance models have been set under the RED II and the IEMD, Chapter 4.2 highlights some major challenges for the inclusion of local actors in the wind sector, be it municipalities, their individual citizens or SMEs and micro enterprises. To address the difficulties faced by citizen- or community-led projects in competing with established market players, financial instruments tailored to the needs of citizen actors, especially in the pre-development phase, are essential. This is vital as antagonising even small local interest groups has the potential to effectively stall project implementation.

The examination of governance models in wind energy in Chapter 4.3 stresses that local municipalities play a crucial role in the facilitation of projects. Be it as aiding in administrative processes, financial support or creating favourable regulatory environments. At a deeper layer yet is the question of business models that can facilitate the inclusion of vulnerable consumers and low-income households, to alleviate the hardship of the energy poor in the EU. While business models building on participatory governance forms are developing, there is still a need for more inclusive financing models to facilitate an equitable transition for truly all Europeans. To approach the necessity for financing of projects and measures needed to reach a successful transition, Chapter 5 shed light into the funding instruments set up by the EU.

Since most of the cited EU financing programmes are very young, there is little information about their success. The only review of the success happened regarding the Innovation Fund, which indicates that only a handful of wind energy projects were funded. The intention of the EU to address JT is-

sues by implementing the JTM should be acknowledged. A study of the effect of a “Just Transition” strategy by the Spanish government concluded that the governing Socialist Party (PSOE) increased their electorate in affected municipalities by addressing social issues of the transition. The effect was strongest when trade union supported the issue in the concerned municipalities. This indicates how acceptance of climate policy could be increased, when political actors take social issues of the transition into account (Bolet et al., 2023). Sustained, long-term support – in the best case possible bipartisan – is important to ensure the effects of climate policies once they have been launched.

Most programmes are addressing private investments with the idea to de-risk them by assuming costs (grants) or providing loans or guarantees. Some instruments allow local governments or other public legal entities to apply, but the main focus lays on the mobilisation of private capital. In summary, regarding the financing wind power projects:

- The success of most of the existing financing instruments of the EU cannot be evaluated as of November 2023 as they are too recent to be already assessed.
- The overall amount of funding for wind energy is hard to estimate, since programmes are eligible for several kinds of projects.
- The implementation of the JTM is likely to ensure that the role of social issues of the transition is reflected.

More generally, the central criterion for eligibility of projects (from all possible economic sectors) is the usefulness of the project for the respective defined objectives of the regulations (e.g., decarbonisation of the energy sector). Regulations and eligibility criteria are kept in general terms without specifying rules for a specific energy sector. In this context, the expansion of wind power is eligible for funding as it serves the respective objectives.

The job creation potential of new wind energy projects can be estimated using three key variables, namely location, wind park type (onshore or offshore) and turbine capacity. Higher turbine capacities yield a greater employment factor, and offshore wind projects generate significantly more job-years/MW compared to onshore counterparts. National job shares en-

compass development, construction, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning, except for manufacturing jobs, which are created internationally. Notably, Germany, Denmark, and Spain, with large wind turbine manufacturing organizations, stand to benefit most from new wind energy deployment in Europe. Finally, while most jobs are on a national scale, the local impact is minor and limited to predominantly temporary development jobs.

REFERENCES

- AURES II. (2020). *Auctions and RECs*. AURES II.
- Bartik, T. J., & Sotherland, N. (2019). Realistic Local Job Multipliers. *Employment Research*, 26(2), 1–3. [https://doi.org/10.17848/1075-8445.26\(2\)-1](https://doi.org/10.17848/1075-8445.26(2)-1)
- Bauwens, T., & Devine-Wright, P. (2018). Positive energies? An empirical study of community energy participation and attitudes to renewable energy. *Energy Policy*, 118, 612–625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.03.062>
- Bauwens, T., Gotchev, B., & Holstenkamp, L. (2016). What drives the development of community energy in Europe? The case of wind power cooperatives. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 13, 136–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.12.016>
- Baxter, J., Walker, C., Ellis, G., Devine-Wright, P., Adams, M., & Fullerton, R. S. (2020). Scale, history and justice in community wind energy: An empirical review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101532>
- bmk.gv.at. (2023). *Was ist eine Sicherheitszone?* BMK. <https://www.bmk.gv.at/themen/verkehr/luftfahrt/sicherheit/luftfahrthindernisse/sicherheitszone.html>
- Bowen, A. (2016). 'Green' Growth, 'Green' Jobs and Labor Markets (SSRN Scholarly Paper 2018164). <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2018164>
- Breitschopf, B., Nathani, C., & Resch, G. (2013). Employment Impact Assessment Studies – Is There a Best Approach to Assess Employment Impacts of RET Deployment? *Renewable Energy Law and Policy Review*, 4(2), 93–104.
- Buli, N. (2021). Norway wind turbines should be torn down, reindeer herders say. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/environment/norway-wind-turbines-should-be-torn-down-reindeer-herders-say-2021-11-12/>

- Buljan, A. (2023, July 14). Portugal Zooms In on Three Offshore Wind Areas with 3.5 GW Capacity for Upcoming Auction. *Offshorewind.Biz*. <https://www.offshorewind.biz/2023/07/14/portugal-zooms-in-on-three-offshore-wind-areas-with-3-5-gw-capacity-for-upcoming-auction/>
- da Cruz Almeida, B. F. (2015). *Localização de parques eólicos e ordenamento do território*. https://sigarra.up.pt/feup/pt/pub_geral.pub_view?pi_pub_base_id=26365
- Direção-Geral do Território. (2023). *Relatório do estado do ordenamento do território*. https://www.dgterritorio.gov.pt/sites/default/files/ficheiros-ordenamento/REOT_2022_100MB.pdf
- Directorate-General for Energy (European Commission), Eclareon, Oeko-Institut, SolarPower Europe, WindEurope, Tallat-Kelpšaitė, J., Brückmann, R., Banasiak, J., Valach, B., Surdea-Hernea, V., Szabó, J., Kokkonen, S., Bauknecht, D., Seebach, D., Vogel, M., Willems, G., Potestio, S., Sokolov, D., Bonadio, J., & Chevillard, N. (2023). *Res Simplify: Technical support for RES policy development and implementation – simplification of permission and administrative procedures for RES installations*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2833/894296>
- Dröschel, B., Grashof, K., & Hauser, E. (2021). *Stand der Umsetzung der RED II-Richtlinie in Deutschland mit Blick auf die Bürgerenergie [Kurzstudie]*. IZES gGmbH.
- Durakovic, A. (2023, November 16). 50 Developers Express Interest to Build Wind Farms Offshore Portugal. *Offshorewind.Biz*. <https://www.offshorewind.biz/2023/11/16/50-developers-express-interest-to-develop-wind-farms-offshore-portugal/>
- Eckhoff, T. (1953). *Rettsvesen og rettsvitenskap i U.S.A.* Akademisk forlag.
- Ejdemo, T., & Söderholm, P. (2015). Wind power, regional development and benefit-sharing: The case of Northern Sweden. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 47, 476–485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.03.082>

EnBW. (2017, March). *Windpark „Silberberg“ Stadt Ober-Ramstadt.*

EnBW. (2023). *Bürgerbeteiligung am EnBW Windportfolio.* buergerbeteiligung.enbw.com.

<https://buergerbeteiligung.enbw.com/windportfolio>

e-redes. (2022). *Produção em regime ordinário.* <https://www.e-redes.pt/en/customers-and-partners/producers/production-licensing>

European Commission. (2015a). *COM/2015/080.* European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2015:80:FIN>

European Commission. (2015b). *Energy Union Package—A Framework Strategy for a Resilient Energy Union with a Forward-Looking Climate Change Policy.*

European Commission. (2022a). *REPowerEU Plan.* https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:fc930f14-d7ae-11ec-a95f-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

European Commission. (2023a). *EU budget: Commission proposes Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) to support European Leadership on critical technologies.* https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_3364

European Commission. (2023b). *European Wind Power Action Plan.* European Commission.

European Commission. (2023c). *Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL.* <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023PC0148>

European Commission. (2022b, December 13). *In focus: Energy communities to transform the EU's energy system.* Energy.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/news/focus-energy-communities-transform-eus-energy-system-2022-12-13_en

European Commission. (2023d). *Clean energy for all Europeans package.* Energy.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/clean-energy-all-europeans-package_en

European Commission. (2023e). *Energy Communities Repository*. Energy-Communities-Repository.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://energy-communities-repository.ec.europa.eu/energy-communities-repository-energy-communities/energy-communities-repository-map_en

European Commission. (2023f). *Energy Union*. Energy.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/energy-union_en

European Commission. (2023g). *Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action*. Climate.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/governance-energy-union-and-climate-action_en#:~:text=Under%20the%20Governance%20Regulation%20%2C%20EU,energy%20security

European Commission. (2023h). *Renewable Energy Directive*. Energy. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en

European Commission. (2023i). *Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub: Organisational form and legal structure*. Rural-Energy-Community-Hub.Ec.Europa.Eu. https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/energy-communities/organisational-form-and-legal-structure_en

European Commission. (2023j). *Fit for 55*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/green-deal/fit-for-55-the-eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/#what>

European Council. (2023). *Fit for 55*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/green-deal/fit-for-55-the-eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/#what>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022a). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022b). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022c). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022d). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022e). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022f). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022g). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022h). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

European Parliament, & Council. (2022b). *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

Regulation (EU) 2021/1057—ESF+, Pub. L. No. Regulation (EU) 2021/1057 (2021).

Regulation (EU) 2021/1058—ERDF and CF, Pub. L. No. Regulation (EU) 2021/1058 (2021).

Regulation (EU) 2021/1060—CPR, Pub. L. No. Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 (2021).

DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/ 2001—RED II, (EU) 2018/ 2001 (2018).

European Union. (2023a). *Non-binding agreement on goals for offshore renewable generation in 2050 with intermediate steps in 2040 and 2030 for priority offshore grid corridor Atlantic offshore grids pursuant to Article 14(1) of the TEN-E Regulation (EU) 2022/869*. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-01/Atlantic_non-binding_offshore_goals_final.pdf

European Union. (2023b). *Non-binding agreement on goals for offshore renewable generation in 2050 with intermediate steps in 2040 and 2030 for priority offshore grid corridor South and East offshore grids (SE offshore) pursuant to Article 14(1) of the TEN-E Regulation (EU) 2022/869*. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-01/SE_offshore_non-binding_offshore_goals_final.pdf

European Union. (2023c). *Non-binding agreement on goals for offshore renewable generation in 2050 with intermediate steps in 2040 and 2030 for priority offshore grid corridor South and West offshore grids (SW offshore) pursuant to Article 14(1) of the TEN-E Regulation (EU) 2022/869*. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-01/SW_offshore_non-binding_offshore_goals_final.pdf

- EWEA. (2010). *Wind Barriers: Administrative and grid access barriers to wind power*.
http://www.ewea.org/fileadmin/files/library/publications/reports/WindBarriers_report.pdf
- Fang, K., & Yang, M. (2019). A Practical Approach to Model Validation. In *Model Engineering for Simulation* (pp. 123–161). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813543-3.00007-X>
- FoE. (2018). *Unleashing the Power of Community Renewable Energy*. Friends of the Earth Europe. https://uploads.strikinglycdn.com/files/533bfab6-f6c3-48ab-bbb3-ca3793a88f11/Community_Energy_booklet_FINAL.pdf
- Fragkos, P., & Paroussos, L. (2018). Employment creation in EU related to renewables expansion. *Applied Energy*, 230, 935–945. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.09.032>
- Gemeinde Wildpoldsried. (2023). *Windkraft*. www.wildpoldsried.de.
<https://www.wildpoldsried.de/windkraft.html>
- geoPortal. (2023). *geoPortal of Energy and Geology* [Map]. <https://geoportal.ineg.pt/mapa/?Mapa=AreasCandidatasRenovaveis>
- Gestore dei Servizi Energetici. (2021). *Regolazione Regionale—Generazione Elettrica da Fonti Rinnovabili*. https://www.gse.it/documenti_site/Documenti%20GSE/Studi%20e%20scenari/GSE_Regolazione%20regionale_2021.pdf
- Grashof, K. (2019). Are auctions likely to deter community wind projects? And would this be problematic? *Energy Policy*, 125, 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.10.010>
- Greene, J. S., & Geisken, M. (2013). Socioeconomic impacts of wind farm development: A case study of Weatherford, Oklahoma. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 3(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-0567-3-2>
- Hanna, R., Heptonstall, P., & Gross, R. (2022). *Green job creation, quality, and skills: A review of the evidence on low carbon energy*. <https://doi.org/10.5286/UKERC.EDC.000953>

- Heldeweg, M. A., & Saintier, S. (2020). Renewable energy communities as ‘socio-legal institutions’: A normative frame for energy decentralization? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 119, 109518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109518>
- Hoicka, C. E., Lowitzsch, J., Brisbois, M. C., Kumar, A., & Ramirez Camargo, L. (2021). Implementing a just renewable energy transition: Policy advice for transposing the new European rules for renewable energy communities. *Energy Policy*, 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112435>
- HR-2021-1975-S, (Supreme Court of Norway 11 October 2021). <https://www.domstol.no/globalassets/upload/hret/decisions-in-english-translation/hr-2021-1975-s.pdf>
- IG Windkraft. (2023). *Regionle Verteilung der Windkraft in Österreich*. https://www.igwindkraft.at/fakten/?xmlval_ID_KEY%5B0%5D=1234
- IRENA. (2011). *Renewable Energy Jobs: Status, Prospects & Policies*. International Renewable Energy Agency. <https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2012/RenewableEnergyJobs.pdf>
- Joint Research Centre (European Commission), Tarvydas, D., Politis, S., Volker, P., Medarac, H., Dalla Longa, F., Badger, J., Kober, T., Nijs, W., Hoyer-Klick, C., Zucker, A., & Hidalgo Gonzalez, I. (2018). *Wind potentials for EU and neighbouring countries: Input datasets for the JRC EU TIMES model*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/041705>
- kaernten.orf.at. (2023, September 3). Windkraft: Sichtbarkeitsverordnung fällt. *kaernten.orf.at*. <https://kaernten.orf.at/stories/3222584/>
- Klima-og miljødepartementet. (2021, June 11). *Retningslinje for behandling av støy i arealplanlegging* [Retningslinjer]. Regjeringen.no; [regjeringen.no. https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/retningslinje-for-behandling-av-stoy-i-arealplanlegging/id2857574/](https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/retningslinje-for-behandling-av-stoy-i-arealplanlegging/id2857574/)

- Knauf, J., & Wüstenhagen, R. (2023). Crowdsourcing social acceptance: Why, when and how project developers offer citizens to co-invest in wind power. *Energy Policy*, *173*, 113340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113340>
- Knodt, M., Ringel, M., & Müller, R. (2020). ‘Harder’ soft governance in the European Energy Union. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, *22*(6), 787–800. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2020.1781604>
- Krug, M., Di Nucci, M. R., Caldera, M., & De Luca, E. (2022). Mainstreaming Community Energy: Is the Renewable Energy Directive a Driver for Renewable Energy Communities in Germany and Italy? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, *14*(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127181>
- Land Oberösterreich. (2017). *Oö. Windkraftmasterplan 2017*. https://www.land-oberoesterreich.gv.at/Mediendateien/Formulare/Dokumente%20UWD%20Abt_US/us_en_Windkraftmasterplan_2017_Kriterienkatalog.pdf
- Land Salzburg. (2022). *Salzburger Landesentwicklungs-programm 2022*. https://www.salzburg.gv.at/bauenwohnen_/Documents/230118V2-Landesentwicklungsprogr_2022_O_.pdf
- Llera, E., Scarpellini, S., Aranda, A., & Zabalza, I. (2013). Forecasting job creation from renewable energy deployment through a value-chain approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *21*, 262–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.12.053>
- Lowitzsch ed., J. (Ed.). (2019). *Energy Transition: Financing Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewables*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93518-8>
- Lowitzsch, J. (2019). Consumer Stock Ownership Plans (CSOPs)—The Prototype Business Model for Renewable Energy Communities. *Energies*, *13*(1), 118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13010118>

- Lowitzsch, J., Hoicka, C. E., & Van Tulder, F. J. (2020). Renewable energy communities under the 2019 European Clean Energy Package – Governance model for the energy clusters of the future? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 122, 109489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109489>
- Lowitzsch, J., Prof. Dr. iur., & Hanke, F. (2019). Consumer (Co-)ownership in Renewables, Energy Efficiency and the Fight Against Energy Poverty—A Dilemma of Energy Transitions. *RELP*, 9, 5–21.
- Memija, A. (2023, November 16). Norway’s Offshore Wind Tender Attracts Seven Applications. *Offshorewind.Biz*. <https://www.offshorewind.biz/2023/11/16/norways-offshore-wind-tender-attracts-seven-applications/>
- Miljødepartementet. (2019). *Norges verneområder—Miljødirektoratet*. Miljødirektoratet/Norwegian Environment Agency. <https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/ansvarsomrader/vernet-natur/norges-verneomrader/>
- Norwegian Ministry of Finance. (2023, October 6). *The Government will introduce a resource rent tax on onshore wind power from 2024* [Pressemelding]. Government.No; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/the-government-will-introduce-a-resource-rent-tax-on-onshore-wind-power-from-2024/id2997403/>
- Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy. (2023, September 14). *Three new offshore wind areas considered for opening and tender in 2025* [Pressemelding]. Government.No; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/tre-nye-havvindomrade-aktuelle-for-opning-og-utlysing-i-2025/id2993904/>
- NVE. (2019). *Nasjonal Ramme For Vindkraft*. https://publikasjoner.nve.no/rapport/2019/rapport2019_12.pdf

- NVE. (2013, January 1). *Offshore wind power in Norway—Strategic Environmental Assessment—English summary*. <https://publikasjoner.nve.no/diverse/2013/havvindsummary2013.pdf>
- NVE. (2022a). *Kunnskapsgrunnlag om virkninger av vindkraft på land—NVE*. <https://www.nve.no/energi/energisystem/vindkraft/kunnskapsgrunnlag-om-virkninger-av-vindkraft-paa-land/>
- NVE. (2022b). *Støy—NVE*. <https://www.nve.no/energi/energisystem/vindkraft/kunnskapsgrunnlag-om-virkninger-av-vindkraft-paa-land/stoey/>
- NVE. (2023a). *Konsesjonsbehandling av vindkraftverk på land—NVE*. <https://www.nve.no/konsesjon/konsesjonsbehandling-og-oppfoelging-av-vindkraft-paa-land/konsesjonsbehandling-av-vindkraftverk-paa-land/>
- NVE. (2023b). *Nasjonal ramme for vindkraft—NVE*. <https://www.nve.no/energi/energisystem/vindkraft/nasjonal-ramme-for-vindkraft/>
- NVE Temakart. (2023). *NVE Nasjonal ramme for vindkraft*. <https://temakart.nve.no/link/?link=nasjonalramme>
- OECD. (2017). *The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries: Policy Analysis and Recommendations*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/urban-rural-and-regional-development/the-governance-of-land-use-in-oecd-countries_9789264268609-en
- Office of the Minister. (2022, May 11). *Ambitious offshore wind initiative* [Pressemelding]. Government.No; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/ambitious-offshore-wind-power-initiative/id2912297/>
- Okkonen, L., & Lehtonen, O. (2016). Socio-economic impacts of community wind power projects in Northern Scotland. *Renewable Energy*, 85, 826–833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.07.047>

- Olje-og energidepartementet. (2019, April 1). *Høring – NVEs forslag til en nasjonal ramme for vindkraft på land* [Horing]. Regjeringen.no; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/horing--nves-forslag-til-en-nasjonal-ramme-for-vindkraft-pa-land/id2639213/>
- Olje-og energidepartementet. (2020a, June 12). *Opner områder for havvind i Noreg* [Pressemelding]. Regjeringa.no; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/nn/dokumentarkiv/regjeringa-solberg/aktuelt-regjeringen-solberg/aktuelt1/pressemeldingar/2020/opner-omrader/id2705986/>
- Olje-og energidepartementet. (2020b, June 19). *Meld. St. 28 (2019–2020)* [Stortingsmelding]. Regjeringen.no; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/meld.-st.-28-20192020/id2714775/>
- Olje-og energidepartementet. (2023, April 28). *Endringer i regelverket om vindkraft skal gi bedre lokal forankring* [Pressemelding]. Regjeringa.no; regjeringen.no. <https://www.regjeringen.no/nn/aktuelt/endringer-i-regelverket-om-vindkraft-skal-gi-betre-lokal-forankring/id2974637/>
- ots.at. (2023). *Erster Windpark in Kärnten feierlich eröffnet.* ots.at. https://www.ots.at/presseaussendung/OTS_20230904_OTS0087/erster-windpark-in-kaernten-feierlich-eroeffnet-bild
- Panos, E., Kleanthis, N., Tsopeles, I., Zhang, M., & Flamos, A. (2021). *Repository of co-identified policies and contextual factors for Switzerland and major European countries. Deliverable 1.2. Swiss decarbonisation pathways towards zero CO2 emissions (POLIZERO) project.* Swiss Federal Office of Energy. <https://www.polizero.ch/energy-and-climate-policy-inventory>

- Pickering, C., & Byrne, J. (2014). The benefits of publishing systematic quantitative literature reviews for PhD candidates and other early-career researchers. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 33(3), 534–548. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2013.841651>
- Puschmann, O. (1998). *The Norwegian landscape reference system*. https://nibio.brage.unit.no/nibio-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/2560260/NIJOS-Rapport-1998-12_en.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y
- Radtke, J., & Ohlhorst, D. (2021). Community Energy in Germany – Bowling Alone in Elite Clubs? *Utilities Policy*, 72, 101269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2021.101269>
- Ram, M., Osorio-Aravena, J. C., Aghahosseini, A., Bogdanov, D., & Breyer, C. (2022). Job creation during a climate compliant global energy transition across the power, heat, transport, and desalination sectors by 2050. *Energy*, 238, 121690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121690>
- República Portuguesa. (2023). *Grupo de Trabalho para o planeamento e operacionalização de centros eletroprodutores baseados em fontes de energias renováveis de origem ou localização oceânica*. https://www.lneg.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/20230531-GTOffshore_RelatorioFinal_vfinal.pdf
- RES Legal—Legal Sources on Renewable Energy. (2018). <http://www.res-legal.eu/home/>
- Ressa, F. (2023, July 20). Accelerazione rinnovabili: Arriva il decreto ‘aree idonee’. *BibLusnet*. <https://biblus.acca.it/decreto-aree-idonee-rinnovabili/>
- Roberts, J., & Gauthier, C. (2019). *Energy communities in the draft National Energy and Climate Plans: Encouraging but room for improvements* (p. 55). REScoop.EU. https://www.sero.se/sero_pdf/20190612_xxx1.pdf
- Rutovitz, J., Dominish, E., & Downes, J. (2015). *Calculating global energy sector jobs: 2015 methodology*. Prepared for Greenpeace International by the Institute for Sustainable

- Futures, University of Technology Sydney. <https://opus.lib.uts.edu.au/bitstream/10453/43718/1/Rutovitzetal2015Calculatingglobalenergysectorjobsmethodology.pdf>
- salzburg.orf.at. (2022, December 15). Erste Windräder in Salzburg beschlossen. *salzburg.orf.at*. <https://salzburg.orf.at/stories/3186427/>
- Schlacke, S., & Knodt, M. (2019). The Governance System of the European Energy Union and Climate Action. *Journal for European Environmental & Planning Law*, 16(4), 323–339. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18760104-01604002>
- Siedlecki, S. L. (2020). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493>
- Simas, M., & Pacca, S. (2014). Assessing employment in renewable energy technologies: A case study for wind power in Brazil. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 31, 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.11.046>
- The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub. (2023a). *Comunità Energetica Rinnovabile di Roseto Valfortore* (Rural Energy Community Best Practice). <https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/Rural%20Energy%20Community%20Best%20Practice%20-%20Roseto%20Valfortore.pdf>
- The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub. (2023b). *The Wildpoldsried Energy Community in the region of Allgäu, Bavaria, in Germany* (Rural Energy Community Best Practice). European Commission. <https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/Rural%20Energy%20Community%20Best%20Practice%20-%20Wildpoldsried.pdf>
- The Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub. (2023c). *Viure del l'aire – EOLPOP* (Rural Energy Community Best Practice). European Commission. <https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-11/EOLPOP.pdf>

Uyanık, G. K., & Güler, N. (2013). A Study on Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 106, 234–240.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.027>

Vasconcellos, H. A. S., & Caiado Couto, L. (2021). Estimation of socioeconomic impacts of wind power projects in Brazil's Northeast region using Interregional Input-Output Analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 149, 111376.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111376>

WindEurope. (2021, May 12). *Fit-for-55 Package: Higher targets alone will not make for more wind energy*. Windeurope.Org. <https://windeurope.org/newsroom/news/fit-for-55-package-higher-targets-alone-will-not-make-for-more-wind-energy/>

ANNEX

Annex A: Collected data on regulations

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT	Österreich	BGBl I Nr 150_2021	Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz	Renewable Energy Expansion Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20011619
AT	Österreich	BGBl Nr 697_1993	Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfungsgesetz 2000	Environmental Impact Assessment Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10010767
AT	Österreich	BGBl Nr 253_1957	Luftfahrtgesetz	Aviation Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10011306
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 49_2019	Burgenländisches Raumplanungsgesetz 2019	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrBgl&Gesetzesnummer=20001224
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 9_2023	Verordnung zur Zonierung für Windkraftanlagen im Burgenland	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/eli/lgbl/BU/2023/9/20230209?Abfrage=LgblAuth&Ti-

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
					tel=&Lgblnum=mer=9%2f2023&SucheNachGesetzzen=False&SucheNachKundmachungen=False&SucheNachVerordnungen=False&SucheNachSonstiges=False&VonDatum=01.01.2015&BisDatum=12.10.2023&BundeslandFilter=Burgenland&Bundesland=Burgenland&BundeslandDefault=Burgenland&ImRisSeitVonDatum=01.01.2015&ImRisSeitBisDatum=12.10.2023&ImRisSeit=Undefined&ImRisSeitForRemotion=Undefined&ResultPageSize=100&Suchworte=&Position=1&SkipToDocumentPage=true&ResultFunctionToKen=7f96ad27-905f-455c-a110-427e3d4e86ed

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 47_2023	Verordnung zur Bemessungsgrundlage für die Berechnung der Windkraft- und Photovoltaikabgabe	Wind Energy Levy Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrBgl&Gesetzesnummer=20001418
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 59_2006	Burgenländisches Elektrizitätswesengesetz 2006	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrBgl&Gesetzesnummer=20000597
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 10_1998	Burgenländisches Baugesetz 1997	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrBgl&Gesetzesnummer=10000504
AT11	Burgenland	LGBl Nr 27_1991	Burgenländisches Naturschutz- und Landschaftspflegegesetz	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrBgl&Gesetzesnummer=10000254
AT12	Niederösterreich	LGBl Nr 3_2015	NÖ Raumordnungsgesetz 2014	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrNO&Gesetzesnummer=20001080
AT12	Niederösterreich	LRNI_2014049	Sektorales Raumordnungsprogramm Windkraftnutzung in NÖ	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokument.wxe?Abfrage=LgblNO&Gliederungszahl=8001%2f1-0&FassungVom=&SkipToDocu-

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
					mentPage=True&Result-FunctionToken=1da7bbfe-4173-4c9a-878f-01b8d70de3ea&Dokumentnummer=LRNI_2014049
AT12	Niederösterreich	LGBl 7800-0	NÖ Elektrizitätswesengesetz 2005	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrNO&Gesetzesnummer=20001013
AT12	Niederösterreich	LGBl Nr 1_2015	NÖ Bauordnung 2014	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrNO&Gesetzesnummer=20001079
AT12	Niederösterreich	LGBl 5500-0	NÖ Naturschutzgesetz 2000	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrNO&Gesetzesnummer=20000814
AT13	Wien	LGBl Nr 46_2005	Wiener Elektrizitätswirtschaftsgesetz 2005	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrW&Gesetzesnummer=20000048
AT13	Wien	LGBl Nr 11_1930	Bauordnung für Wien	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrW&Gesetzesnummer=20000006

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT13	Wien	LGBl Nr 45_1998	Wiener Naturschutzgesetz	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrW&Gesetzesnummer=20000454
AT21	Kärnten	LGBl Nr 59_2021	Kärntner Raumordnungsgesetz 2021	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrK&Gesetzesnummer=20000386
AT21	Kärnten	LGBl Nr 46_2016	Windkraftstandorträumeverordnung	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/eli/lgbl/ka/2016/46/20160713?ResultFunctionToKen=87dfc5d6-&SkipToDocumentPage=True&Abfrage=LgblAuth&Titel=&Lgblnummer=&SucheNachGesetzen=False&SucheNachKundmachungen=False&SucheNachVerordnungen=False&SucheNachSonstiges=False&VonDatum=01.01.2014&BisDatum=12.10.2023&BundeslandFilter=Kaernen&Bundesland=K%c3%a4rnten&Bu

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
					ndeslandDe-fault=K%c3%a4rnten&Im-RisSeitVonDa-tum=01.01.2014&ImRisSeit-BisDatum=12.10.2023&Im-RisSeit=Undefined&Im-RisSeitForRemotion=Undefined&ResultPageSize=100&Suchworte=windkraft*
AT21	Kärnten	LGBI Nr 10_2012	Kärntner Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2011	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/ge/ltendefassung.wxe?abfrage=Lrk&gesetzesnummer=20000239
AT21	Kärnten	LGBI Nr 62_1996	Kärntner Bauordnung 1996	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrK&Gesetzesnummer=10000201
AT21	Kärnten	LGBI Nr 79_2002	Kärntner Naturschutzgesetz 2002	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrK&Gesetzesnummer=20000118
AT22	Steiermark	LGBI Nr 49_2010	Steiermärkisches Raumordnungsgesetz	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20000069

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT22	Steiermark	LGBl Nr 72_2013	Entwicklungsprogramm für den Sachbereich Windenergie	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20000361
AT22	Steiermark	LGBl Nr 70_2005	Steiermärkisches Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2005	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20000343
AT22	Steiermark	LGBl Nr 59_1995	Steiermärkisches Baugesetz	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20000070
AT22	Steiermark	LGBl Nr 65_2022	Steiermärkisches Biosphärenparkgesetz 2022	Biosphere Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20001707
AT22	Steiermark	LGBl Nr 71_2017	Steiermärkisches Naturschutzgesetz 2017	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrStmk&Gesetzesnummer=20001381
AT31	Oberösterreich	LGBl Nr 114_1993	Oö. Raumordnungsgesetz 1994	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrOO&Gesetzesnummer=10000370
AT31	Oberösterreich	not available	Oö. Windkraftmasterplan 2017	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.land-oberoesterreich.gv.at/Medien-

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
					dateien/Formulare/Dokumente%20UWD%20Abt_US/us_en_Windkraftmasterplan_2017_Kriterienkatalog.pdf
AT31	Oberösterreich	LGBl Nr 1_2006	Oö. Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2006	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrOO&Gesetzesnummer=20000397
AT31	Oberösterreich	LGBl Nr 66_1994	Oö. Bauordnung 1994	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrOO&Gesetzesnummer=10000411
AT31	Oberösterreich	LGBl Nr 129_2001	Oö. Natur- und Landschaftsschutzgesetz 2001	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrOO&Gesetzesnummer=20000147
AT32	Salzburg	LGBl Nr 30_2009	Salzburger Raumordnungsgesetz 2009	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrSbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000615
AT32	Salzburg	not available	Salzburger Landesentwicklungsprogramm 2022	Wind Energy Zoning Act	https://www.salzburg.gv.at/bauen-wohnen/Docs/230118V2-Landesentwicklung-sprogr_2022_O_.pdf

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT32	Salzburg	LGBl Nr 75_1999	Salzburger Landeselektrizitätsgesetz 1999	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrSbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000005
AT32	Salzburg	LGBl Nr 1_2016	Salzburger Bautechnikgesetz 2015	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrSbg&Gesetzesnummer=20001000
AT32	Salzburg	LGBl Nr 73_1999	Salzburger Naturschutzgesetz 1999	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrSbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000003
AT33	Tirol	LGBl Nr 43_2022	Tiroler Raumordnungsgesetz 2022	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/NormDokument.wxe?Abfrage=LrT&Gesetzesnummer=20000910&Artikel=&Paragraf=0&Anlage=&Uebergangsrecht=
AT33	Tirol	LGBl Nr 134_2011	Tiroler Elektrizitätsgesetz	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrT&Gesetzesnummer=20000491
AT33	Tirol	LGBl Nr 44_2022	Tiroler Bauordnung	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrT&Gesetzesnummer=20000911

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
AT33	Tirol	LGBl Nr 80_2020	Naturschutzgesetz 2005	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrT&Gesetzesnummer=20000252
AT34	Vorarlberg	LGBl Nr 39_1996	Vorarlberger Raumplanungsgesetz	Regional Land Use Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrVbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000653
AT34	Vorarlberg	LGBl Nr 52_2001	Gesetz über die Erzeugung, Übertragung und Verteilung von elektrischer Energie	Electricity Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrVbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000617
AT34	Vorarlberg	LGBl Nr 52_2001	Vorarlberger Baugesetz	Building Law Code	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrVbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000734
AT34	Vorarlberg	LGBl Nr 59_2003	Gesetz über Naturschutz und Landschaftsentwicklung	Nature Conservation Law Act	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=LrVbg&Gesetzesnummer=20000466
IT	Italy	DL n 199 8_11_2021	Attuazione della direttiva (UE) 2018/2001 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, dell'11 dicembre 2018, sulla promozione dell'uso dell'energia da fonti rinnovabili	Renewable Energy Expansion Act II	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2021-11-08;199

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
IT	Italy	DL n 28 3_3_2011	Attuazione della direttiva 2009/28/CE sulla promozione dell'uso dell'energia da fonti rinnovabili, recante modifica e successiva abrogazione delle direttive 2001/77/CE e 2003/30/CE	Renewable Energy Expansion Act	https://www.nor-mattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28!vig=2023-11-20
IT	Italy	DL n 152 3_4_2006	Norme in materia ambientale	Environmental Impact Assessment Act	https://www.nor-mattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2006-04-03;152!vig=2023-11-20
IT	Italy	DL n 387 29_12_2003	Promozione dell'energia elettrica prodotta da fonti energetiche rinnovabili nel mercato interno dell'elettricità	Electricity Law Code	https://www.nor-mattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2003-12-29;387!vig=2023-11-20
IT	Italy	L n 241 7_8_1990	Nuove norme in materia di procedimento amministrativo e di diritto di accesso ai documenti amministrativi.	Administrative Simplification Act	https://www.nor-mattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:1990-08-07;241
IT	Italy	DP n 380 6_6_2001	Testo unico delle disposizioni legislative e regolamentari in materia edilizia	Building Law Code	https://www.nor-mattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:presidente.repubblica:decreto:2001-06-06;380

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
IT	Italy	DPCM 14_11_1997	Determinazione dei valori limite delle sorgenti sonore	Noise Regulation Act II	https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/1997/12/01/097A9602/sg
IT	Italy	L n. 447 26_10_1995	Legge quadro sull'inquinamento acustico.	Noise Regulation Act	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:1995-10-26;447
IT	Italy	DL n 190 13_10_2010	Attuazione della direttiva 2008/56/CE che istituisce un quadro per l'azione comunitaria nel campo della politica per l'ambiente marino	Marine Environment Act	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2010-10-13;190!vig=2023-11-20
IT	Italy	DL n 42 22_1_2004	Codice dei beni culturali e del paesaggio	Landscape and Cultural Heritage Conservation Act	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2004-01-22;42!vig=2023-11-20
IT	Italy	DM 10_09_2010	Linee guida per l'autorizzazione degli impianti alimentati da fonti rinnovabili	National Wind Energy Plan	www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2010/09/18/10A11230/sg
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei n 30_A_2022	Aprova Medidas Excecionais que Visam Assegurar a Simplificação dos Procedimentos de Produção de Energia a Partir de Fontes Renováveis	Simplification of Renewable Energy Expansion	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2022-182491268

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 151_B_2013	n Regime Jurídico da Avaliação de Impacte Ambiental_AIA	Environmental Impact Assessment	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2013-70122774
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 76_2019	n Altera o Regime Jurídico Aplicável ao Exercício das Atividades de Produção, Transporte, Distribuição e Comercialização de Electricidade e à Organização dos Mercados de Electricidade	Amends the legal regime applicable to the exercise of electricity production, transport, distribution and commercialization activities and the organization of electricity markets	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2019-122465066
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 15_2022	n Estabelece a organização e o funcionamento do Sistema Elétrico Nacional, transpondo a Diretiva (UE) 2019/944 e a Diretiva (UE) 2018/2001	Establishes the Organization and Functioning of the National Electricity System, transposing the RED II and IEMD	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2022-177634029
PT	Portugal	Decree_Lei 555_99	n Regime Jurídico da Urbanização e Edificação_RJUE	Legal Regime for Urbanization and Building	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/555-1999-655682
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 9_2007	n Regulamento Geral do Ruído_RGR	Noise Regulation Act	https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2007-34526375

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 11_2023	Reforma e Simplificação dos Licenciamentos Am- bientais	Simplification of Environmen- tal Licensing	https://diariodarepub-lica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/2023-207577654
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 31_2014	Lei de Bases Gerais da Polí- tica Pública de Solos, de Or- denamento do Território e de Urbanismo	Soil, Land Use and Urban Plan- ning	https://diariodarepub-lica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/lei/2014-57377208
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 140_99	Rede Natura 2000	Natura 2000 Network	https://diariodarepub-lica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/decreto-lei/1999-34527675
PT	Portugal	Decreto_Lei 72_2022	Altera as medidas excecio- nais para a implemen- tação de projetos e iniciati- vas de produção e ar- mazenação de energia de fontes renováveis	Amends exceptional measures for the implemen- tation of renewable energy plants	https://diariodarepub-lica.pt/dr/en/detail/de-crete-law/72-2022-202357817
NO	Norge	FOR-1990-12-07- 959	energilovforskriften	Energy Act Regulation	https://lovdata.no/doku-ment/SF/forskrift/1990-12-07-959?q=vindkraft
NO	Norge	LOV-2008-06- 27-71	plan- og bygningsloven	Planning and Building Act	https://lovdata.no/doku-ment/NL/lov/2008-06-27-71
NO	Norge	LOV-2009-06-19- 100	naturmangfoldloven	Natural Diversity Act	https://lovdata.no/doku-ment/NL/lov/2009-06-19-100/kapv#kapv

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
NO	Norge	FOR-2014-07-15-980	Forskrift om rapportering, registrering og merking av luftfartshinder	Aviation Obstacles Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2014-07-15-980?q=vindkraft
NO	Norge	LOV-1990-06-29-50	energiloven	Energy Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/1990-06-29-50
NO	Norge	LOV-1981-03-13-6	forurensningsloven	Pollution Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/1981-03-13-6?q=Forurensningsloven
NO	Norge	FOR-2017-06-21-854	Forskrift om konsekvensutredninger	Regulation in Impact Assessment	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2017-06-21-854?q=vindkraft
NO	Norge	FOR-2016-09-15-1066	Forskrift om merking av og etablering av sikkerhetssoner tilknyttet innretning for fornybar energiproduksjon	Regulations on Labeling of Equipment for Renewable Energy Production	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2016-09-15-1066?q=vindenergi
NO	Norge	LOV-2010-06-04-21	havenergilova	Marine Energy Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2010-06-04-21?q=Havenergilova
NO	Norge	FOR-2020-06-12-1192	havenergilovforskrifta	Marine Energy Act Regulations	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2020-06-12-1192?q=Havenergilova
NO	Norge	LOV-2009-06-19-100	naturmangfoldloven	Nature Diversity Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2009-06-19-100?q=Naturmangfoldloven

NUTS	COUNTRY NAME	LAW ID	LAW NAME ORIGINAL	LAW NAME ENGLISH	LINK
NO	Norge	LOV-1978-06-09-50	lov om kulturminner	Cultural Heritage Act	https://lovdata.no/dokument/NLE/lov/1978-06-09-50

Annex B: Collected data on job creation

B1: development data

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					scale			Onshore / offshore	Location	Reference year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
Schallenberg-Rodriguez & Inchaustisintes, 2021)	1.41	0.26	1.67	0.7	2.37	40	5	200	Offshore	Gran Canaria	2021
(Kalinina et al., 2020)	0.69	1.09	1.78					798.8	Onshore	Ukraine	2019
(Kahouli & Martin, 2018)	0.46	0.41	0.87	0.48	1.34	62	8	496	Offshore	France	2020
Varela-Vázquez & Sánchez-Carreira, 2017)			3			99	5	495	Offshore	Spain	2030
(Dedrick et al., 2014)	0.21					50	2	100	Onshore	US	2014
(Okkonen & Lehtonen, 2016)			0.6	0.15	0.75	31	0.9	27.6	Onshore	Northern Scotland	2009 **

** = only regional impact/job creation/part of job creation, * = values based on Rutovitz et al (2015).

B2: construction data

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	in-duced	total	Nr. tur-bines	Turbine capac-ity (MW)	Total ca-pacity (MW)			
(Ortega-Izquierdo & Río, 2020)	2.217	1.667	3.884						onshore	EU-28	2016
(Ortega-Izquierdo & Río, 2020)	3.128	2.346	5.474						offshore	EU-28	2016
(Sharma et al., 2022)	1.83							65000	onshore	US	2019
(Janikowska & Jebreel, 2022)			11.4						onshore	Poland	2022
(Sohrab et al., 2019)	1.97	4.93	6.9						onshore	Iran	2050
(Schallenberg-Rodriguez & Inchausti-Sintes, 2021)	15	11.1	26.1	7.1	44.3	40	5	200	offshore floating	Gran Cana-ria	2021
(Kalinina et al., 2020)	3.057	4.861	7.918					798.8	onshore	Ukraine	2019
(Kahouli & Martin, 2018)	3.04	2.67	5.71	3.13	8.84	62	8	496	offshore	France	2020
(Varela-Vázquez & Sánchez-Carreira, 2017)			1.5			99	5	495	offshore floating	Spain	2030
(Ortega et al., 2015)	2.5	1.88	4.38						onshore	Global	2012
(Ortega et al., 2015)	4.28	3.28	7.56						offshore	Global	2012
(Simas & Pacca, 2014)	6.75	0.84	7.59						onshore	Brazil	2017
(Williams et al., 2008)	1.71							10.5	onshore	US, northern Arizona	2008
(Williams et al., 2008)	1.67							60	onshore	US, northern Arizona	2008

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	in-duced	total	Nr. tur-bines	Turbine capac-ity (MW)	Total ca-pacity (MW)			
(Williams et al., 2008)	1.67							180	onshore	US, northern Arizona	2008
(Vieira et al., 2019)	4.3	3.2	7.5		7.5				offshore	Portugal	2030
(Fragkos & Paroussos, 2018)	3.2								onshore	EU-28	2015*
(Coon et al., 2015)	1.28							147	onshore	US, Okla-homa	2012
(Brown et al., 2012)	1.35								onshore	US	2008
(Grover, 2002)	0.244	0.077	0.321	0.154	0.475	260	1.5	390	onshore	US, Wash-ington	2002
(Twidell, 1986)	4								onshore	Denmark	1985
(Koasidis et al., 2022)	2.894								onshore	EU	2025
(Koasidis et al., 2022)	6.575								offshore	EU	2025
(Buchmayr et al., 2022)	2.48						3		onshore	Belgium	2022
(Buchmayr et al., 2022)	6.09						5		offshore	Belgium	2022
(Osorio-Aravena et al., 2022)	3.2					303	2	606	onshore	Spain	2022*
(Ram et al., 2020)	3.2								onshore	global	2015*

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	in-duced	total	Nr. tur-bines	Turbine capac-ity (MW)	Total ca-pacity (MW)			
(Ram et al., 2020)	8								offshore	global	2015 *
(Aldieri et al., 2020)	13								nc	Spain	2010
(Aldieri et al., 2020)	2.1	6.13	8.23						nc	Japan	2017
(Aldieri et al., 2020)	1.48	0.95	2.43					3500	offshore	France	2040
(Aldieri et al., 2020)	6	8	14						nc	USA, Mon-tana	2014
(Jacobson et al., 2017)			7.06	9.1					onshore	US	2012
(Jacobson et al., 2017)			9.3	14.4					offshore	US	2012
(Loomis et al., 2016)	0.72	3.49	4.21	1.5	9.2	2223	1.5	3335	onshore	US, Illinois	2012
(Hartley et al., 2015)	0.67							100	onshore	US, Texas	2011
(Jacobson et al., 2014)	4.05					24720	5	123600	onshore	US, Califor-nia	2014
(Jacobson et al., 2014)	7.3					7800	5	39000	offshore	US, Califor-nia	2014
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.81	0.92	1.73	0.52	3.17	33	3	100	onshore	Canada	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.99					44	2.3	101.2	onshore	Canada, ON	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.91					73	1.5	109.5	onshore	Canada, Qc	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.73					32	3	96	onshore	Canada, NB	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.81							100	onshore	Canada, NB	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	1.49					126	1.5	189	onshore	Canada, ON	2013

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	in-duced	total	Nr. tur-bines	Turbine capac-ity (MW)	Total ca-pacity (MW)			
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.61					73	1.5	109.5	onshore	Canada, Qc	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.42					10	3	30	onshore	Canada, PEI	2013
(Landry et al., 2013)	0.67					67	1.5	100.5	onshore	Canada, Qc	2013
(Van der Zwaan et al., 2013)	1.5	1.125	2.625		2.625				onshore	Middle East	2050
(Jacobson et al., 2013)	3.05								onshore	New York	2030
(Jacobson et al., 2013)	5.04								offshore	New York	2030
(Simas & Pacca, 2013b)	7.605								onshore	Brazil	2016
(Brown, 2011)	10.3							520	onshore	Brazil, Ceara	2007
(Slattery et al., 2011)	0.37	1.55	1.92	0.66	2.58	421	1.75	735.5	onshore	US, texas	2011
(Slattery et al., 2011)	0.62	1.86	2.48	0.85	3.32	407	1.63	662.5	onshore	US, texas	2011
(Larry Leistriz & Coon, 2009)	0.85	0.7	1.55			106	1.5	159	onshore	Great plains	2009
(Rose et al., 2022)	14.6							10000	offshore	US, califor-nia	2040
(Dedrick et al., 2014)	0.99					50	2	100	onshore	US	2014
(Shoeib et al., 2022)	1.31							100	onshore	US	2015
Kabayo et al., 2019)	3.2					2599	2	5046	onshore	Portugal	2015*

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	in-duced	total	Nr. tur-bines	Turbine capac-ity (MW)	Total ca-pacity (MW)			
(Okkonen & Lehtonen, 2016)			1.34	0.33	1.67	31	0.9	27.6	onshore	Northern Scotland	2009**
(Ejdemo & Söderholm, 2015)	0.852	0.19	1.042		1.042			4000	onshore	Northern Sweden	2019**
(Hanna et al., 2022)	4.2								onshore	global	2022
(Hanna et al., 2022)	7.2								offshore	global	2022
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	3.2								onshore	global	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	8								offshore	global	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	6.7								onshore	Latin America	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	8.9								offshore	North America	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	7.1								offshore	EU	2015

** = only regional impact/job creation/part of job creation, * = values based on Rutovitz et al (2015).

B3: manufacturing data

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	induced	total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(Ortega-Izquierdo & Río, 2020)	5.466	3.889	9.355						onshore	EU-28	2016
(Ortega-Izquierdo & Río, 2020)	9.216	6.912	16.128						offshore	EU-28	2016
(Sharma et al., 2022)					1.25			65000	onshore	US	2019
(Schallenberg-Rodríguez & Inchausti-Sintes, 2021)	9.05	3.835	12.885	4.1	16.985	40	5	200	offshore floating	Gran Canaria	2021
(Kalinina et al., 2020)	1.68	2.67	4.35					798.8	onshore	Ukraine	2019
(Kahouli & Martin, 2018)	3.11	2.72	5.83	3.2	9.02	62	8	496	offshore	France, Brittany	2020
(Varela-Vázquez & Sánchez-Carreira, 2017)			33			99	5	495	offshore floating	Spain	2030
(Ortega et al., 2015)	7.5	5	12.5						onshore	global	2012
(Ortega et al., 2015)	29.61	20.7	50.31						offshore	global	2012
(Simas & Pacca, 2014)	3.4	2.26	5.66						onshore	Brazil	2017
(Vieira et al., 2019)	22.5	16.9	39.4		39.4				offshore	Portugal	2030
(Fragkos & Paroussos, 2018)	4.7								onshore	EU-28	2015*

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	induced	total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(Twidell, 1986)	2.92					1500	0.08	120	onshore	Denmark	1985
(Twidell, 1986)	3.07					700	0.0605	42.35	onshore	Denmark	1985
(Koasidis et al., 2022)	4.25								onshore	EU	2025
(Koasidis et al., 2022)	12.821								offshore	EU	2025
(Ram et al., 2020)	4.7								onshore	global	2015*
(Ram et al., 2020)	15.6								offshore	global	2015*
(Hartley et al., 2015)	3.13							100	onshore	global	2011
(Van der Zwaan et al., 2013)	6.6	4.95	11.55		11.55				onshore	Middle east	2050
(Moldvay et al., 2013)	0.625								onshore	South Africa	2013
(Simas & Pacca, 2013b)	3.51								onshore	Brazil	2016
(Larry Leistriz & Coon, 2009)	3.4	7.02	10.42		10.42	106	1.5	159	onshore	Great plains	2009
(Dedrick et al., 2014)	3.91					50	2	100	onshore	US	2014
(Kabayo et al., 2019)	4.7					2599	2	5046	onshore	Portugal	2015*
(Okkonen & Lehtonen, 2016)			0.12	0.04	0.16	31	0.9	27.6	onshore	Northern Scotland	2009**

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			On-shore/ offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	induced	total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(Ejdemo & Söderholm, 2015)					1.442			4000	onshore	Northern Sweden	2019**
(Hanna et al., 2022)	8								onshore	global	2022
(Hanna et al., 2022)	16.8								offshore	global	2022
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	4.7								onshore	global	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	15.6								offshore	global	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	3.4								onshore	Latin America	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	20.5								offshore	North America	2015
(Rutovitz et al., 2015)	10.7								offshore	EU	2015

** = only regional impact/job creation/part of job creation, * = values based on Rutovitz et al (2015).

B4: operation and maintenance data

This project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(ORTEGA-IZQUIERDO & RÍO, 2020)	8.868	6.651	15.519						onshore	EU-28	2016
(ORTEGA-IZQUIERDO & RÍO, 2020)	4.895	3.671	8.566						offshore	EU-28	2016
(SOHRAB ET AL., 2019)	7.857	19.643	27.5					50	onshore	Iran	2050
(SCHALLENBERG-RODRIGUEZ & INCHAUSTI-SINTES, 2021)	14.125	2.375	16.5	6.375	22.9	40	5	200	offshore floating	Gran Canaria	2021
(KALININA ET AL., 2020)	5.915	9.405	15.32						onshore	Ukraine	2019
(SCHILLING ET AL., 2018)	20.161					365	0.85	310	onshore	Northern Kenya	2018
(KAHOULI & MARTIN, 2018)	8.065	14.8395	22.9	18.105	41.0	62	8	496	offshore	France, Brittany	2020
(VARELA-VÁZQUEZ & SÁNCHEZ-CARREIRA, 2017)	5.25					99	5	495	offshore floating	Spain	2030
(ORTEGA ET AL., 2015)	10	7.5	17.5						onshore	Global	2012
(ORTEGA ET AL., 2015)	22.5	17	39.5						offshore	Global	2012
(CORSATEA, 2014)	10								onshore	EU	2010
(SIMAS & PACCA, 2014)	14.75								onshore	Brazil	2014
(COLLINS ET AL., 2012)	3.81					164	2	328	onshore	US, Appalachia	2010

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(WILLIAMS ET AL., 2008)	11.9							10.5	onshore	Northern Arizona, US	2008
(WILLIAMS ET AL., 2008)	12.5							60	onshore	Northern Arizona, US	2008
(WILLIAMS ET AL., 2008)	12.5							180	onshore	Northern Arizona, US	2008
(VIEIRA ET AL., 2019)	18	13.6	31.6		31.6				offshore	Portugal	2030
(FRAGKOS & PAROUSSOS, 2018)	7.5								onshore	EU	2015*
(FRAGKOS & PAROUSSOS, 2018)	6								onshore	EU	2011
(FRAGKOS & PAROUSSOS, 2018)	1.25								onshore	EU	2017
(FRAGKOS & PAROUSSOS, 2018)	2								onshore	EU	2008
(FRAGKOS & PAROUSSOS, 2018)	7.5								onshore	EU	2015
(COON ET AL., 2015)	2.21							147	onshore	Oklahoma	2012
(BROWN ET AL., 2012)	8.75								onshore	US	2008

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. tur- bines	Turbine capac- ity (MW)	Total capac- ity (MW)			
(GROVER, 2002)	1.41	0.199	1.609	1.81	3.419	260	1.5	390	onshore	US, Wash- ington	2002
(TWIDELL, 1986)	25								onshore	Denmark	1985
(KOASIDIS ET AL., 2022)	6.95								onshore	EU	2025
(KOASIDIS ET AL., 2022)	4.575								offshore	EU	2025
(BUCHMAYR ET AL., 2022)	4.647 5								onshore	Belgium	2022
(BUCHMAYR ET AL., 2022)	3.04								offshore	Belgium	2022
(OSORIO-ARAVENA ET AL., 2022)	7.5					303	2	606	onshore	Spain	2022 *
(VASCONCELLOS & CAI- ADO COUTO, 2021)	12.937	14.765	27.702	18.598	46.3				onshore	Brazil	2023
(VASCONCELLOS & CAI- ADO COUTO, 2021)	14.75								onshore	Brazil	2014 *
(VASCONCELLOS & CAI- ADO COUTO, 2021)	52.5	63.5	116	71.5					onshore	Italy	2023
(RAM ET AL., 2020)	7.5								onshore	Global	2015 *
(RAM ET AL., 2020)	5								offshore	Global	2015 *
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	5								nc	Spain	2010
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	9.375								nc	Greece	2020
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	6.75								nc	Italy	2014

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	4.38	3.94	8.32						nc	Japan	2017
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	2.857	3.643	6.5						offshore	France	2040
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	7.5							63.1	nc	Germany	2023
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	2.5								nc	Canada	2020
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	5								nc	Middle east	2050
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	10	7.5	17.5						nc	US, Montana	2014
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2017)			11.1	14.319					onshore	US	2012
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2017)			18.9	25.515					offshore	US	2012
(CHILD ET AL., 2017)	5							70	onshore	Aland island	2030
(CHILD ET AL., 2017)	5							100	offshore	Aland island	2030
(LOOMIS ET AL., 2016)	1.582	2.279	3.861	2.256	6.117	2223	1.5	3335	onshore	US, Illinois	2012
(HARTLEY ET AL., 2015)	23.75							100	onshore	US, Texas	2011
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2014)	6.18					24720	5	123600	onshore	US, California	2014
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2014)	26.36					7800	5	39000	offshore	US, California	2014
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.25	1	3.25	1	4.25	33	3	100	onshore	Canada	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	1.5					44	2.3	101.2	nc	Canada, ON	2013

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. tur- bines	Turbine capac- ity (MW)	Total capac- ity (MW)			
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.25					73	1.5	109.5	nc	Canada, Qc	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	1.75					32	3	96	nc	Canada, NB	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	3					33	3	99	nc	Canada, NB	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.25							100	nc	Canada, NB	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.25					126	1.5	189	nc	Canada, ON	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.25					73	1.5	109.5	nc	Canada, Qc	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.5					10	3	30	nc	Canada, PEI	2013
(LANDRY ET AL., 2013)	2.5					67	1.5	100.5	nc	Canada, Qc	2013
(Van der Zwaan et al., 2013)	1.5	1.125	2.625		2.625				nc	Middle East	2050
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2013)	2.82					4020	5	20100	onshore	New York	2030
(JACOBSON ET AL., 2013)	2.81					12700	5	63500	offshore	New York	2030
(SIMAS & PACCA, 2013B)	11.7								nc	Brazil	2016

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. tur- bines	Turbine capac- ity (MW)	Total capac- ity (MW)			
(GREENE & GEISKEN, 2013)	2.585 03401 4	8.29931 9728	10.88435 374	9.251700 68	20.1360 5442	98	1.5	147	onshore	Weather- ford, Texas, US	2013 **
(BROWN, 2011)	12							520	onshore	Brazil, Ceara	2007
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	0.897	2.203	3.100	1.768	4.867	421	1.747	735.5	onshore	Texas, US	2011
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	0.906	2.234	3.140	1.992	5.132	407	1.628	662.5	onshore	Texas, US	2011
(ESTEBAN ET AL., 2011)	12								offshore	Britain	2009
(LARRY LEISTRITZ & COON, 2009)	1.572	3.302	4.874	4.874	9.748	106	1.5	159	onshore	Great plains	2009
(ROSE ET AL., 2022)	10.625							10000	offshore	California	2040
(DEDRICK ET AL., 2014)	2.4					50	2	100	onshore	US	2014
(SHOEIB ET AL., 2022)	14.44							100	onshore	US	2015
(KIM & KIM, 2021)	5	5	10	0	10	5	2	10	onshore	Korea	2015
(KIM & KIM, 2021)	5	10	15	5	20	24	5	120	offshore	Korea	2015
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	7.5					2599	2	5046	onshore	Portugal	2015 *
(OKKONEN & LEHTONEN, 2016)			7.61	2.26	9.87	31	0.9	27.6	onshore	Northern Scotland	2009
(EJDEMO & SÖDERHOLM, 2015)	0.3125	0.125	0.4375		0.4375			4000	onshore	Northern Sweden	2019 **
(HANNA ET AL., 2022)	7.5								onshore	global	2022
(HANNA ET AL., 2022)	12.5								offshore	global	2022

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					Scale			Onshore/ offshore	location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. tur- bines	Turbine capac- ity (MW)	Total capac- ity (MW)			
(RUTOVITZ ET AL., 2015)	7.5								onshore	global	2015
(RUTOVITZ ET AL., 2015)	5								offshore	global	2015
(RUTOVITZ ET AL., 2015)	15								onshore	Latin America	2015
(RUTOVITZ ET AL., 2015)	2.25								offshore	North America	2015
(RUTOVITZ ET AL., 2015)	5								offshore	EU	2015
(SHARMA ET AL., 2022)	1.97								onshore	US	2019
(JANIKOWSKA & JEBREEL, 2022)			11.4						onshore	Poland	2022

** = only regional impact/job creation/part of job creation, * = values based on Rutovitz et al (2015).

B5: decommissioning data

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					scale			Onshore / offshore	Location	Reference year
	Direct	Indi- rect	Direct + indirect	In- duced	To- tal	Nr. tur- bines	Turbine capac- ity (MW)	Total capac- ity (MW)			
(SCHALLENBERG-RODRIGUEZ & INCHAUSTI-SINTES, 2021)	2.655	0.615	3.27	1.005	4.27 5	40	5	200	Offshore	Gran Canaria	2021
(KALININA ET AL., 2020)	0.746	1.186	1.932					798.8	Onshore	Ukraine	2019
(TRYPOLSKA ET AL., 2022)	0.78							3600	Onshore	Ukraine	2050

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					scale			Onshore / offshore	Location	Reference year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(RAM ET AL., 2020)	0.72								Onshore	Global	2015
(RAM ET AL., 2020)	2.99								Offshore	Global	2015
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	0.6					2599	2	5046	Onshore	Portugal	2015
(OKKONEN & LEHTONEN, 2016)			0.1	0.02	0.12	31	0.9	27.6	Onshore	Northern Scotland	2009 **

** = only regional impact/job creation/part of job creation, * = values based on Rutovitz et al (2015).

B6: construction phase data

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					scale			Onshore / offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(SCHILLING ET AL., 2018)			24.2			365	0.85	310	onshore	northern Kenya	2018
(CORSATEA, 2014)	1.25								onshore	EU	2010
(COLLINS ET AL., 2012)	2.24					164	2	328	onshore	US, Appalachia	2010
(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	10.03	9.63	19.66	12.27	31.93				onshore	Brazil	2023
(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	10.74	2.79	13.53						onshore	Brazil	2023 **

Source	Jobs (job-years/MW)					scale			Onshore / offshore	Location	Ref. year
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total	Nr. turbines	Turbine capacity (MW)	Total capacity (MW)			
(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	5.18	6.14	11.32	5.6	16.92				onshore	Italy	2023
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	8.8								nc	Greece	2020
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	10.74	2.79	13.53						onshore	Brazil	2017 **
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	9.9								nc	Italy	2014
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	3.92								nc	Canada	2020
(ALDIERI ET AL., 2020)	8.1								nc	Middle east	2050
(CHILD ET AL., 2017)	8.6							70	onshore	Aland islands	2030 *
(CHILD ET AL., 2017)	18.1							100	offshore	Aland islands	2030 *
(GREENE & GEISKEN, 2013)	0.014	0.286	0.3	0.34	0.639	98	1.5	147	onshore	USA, texas	2013 ***
(ESTEBAN ET AL., 2011)					28.8				offshore	Britain	2009
(KIM & KIM, 2021)	8.6	18.4	27	2.8	29.8	5	2	10	onshore	Korea	2015 *
(KIM & KIM, 2021)	18.1	25.7	43.8	8.2	52	24	5	120	offshore	Korea	2015 *

*** = only regional impact/regional job creation, ** = data from IRENA, * = data from Simas and Pacca, 2015.

B7: other data

Source	jobs					Onshore / offshore	location	Ref. year	Unit
	Direct	Indirect	Direct + indirect	Induced	Total				
(DUARTE ET AL., 2022)					0.96	n.d.	Spain	2005	jobs/MW
(EL KINANI ET AL., 2023)					1.2	n.d.	France	2010	jobs/MW
(EL KINANI ET AL., 2023)					13.2	n.d.	Spain	2010	job-years/MW
(HERAS & MARTÍN, 2020)	9.0					onshore	Spain	2011	jobs/MW
(KANDROT ET AL., 2020)					6.418	offshore	Ireland	2030	job-years/MW
(MU ET AL., 2018)			26.4			onshore	China	2018	jobs/MW
(BEHRENS ET AL., 2016)					1.15	n.d.	Portugal	2010	jobs/MW
(ŞENGÜL ET AL., 2015)					0.335	n.d.	Turkey	2015	average and person/MW
(ROY ET AL., 2022)					1.1	n.d.	India	2022	jobs/MW

(DELOITTE, 2021)	0.1	3.7	3.8		3.7	n.d.	Portugal	2021	jobs/MW
(CHEN & LI, 2021)	15.8	19.3	35.1			n.d.	global south	2021	jobs/US\$1 million invested
(ZHOU ET AL., 2020)					30% reduction potential	n.d.	China	2020	30% labor reduction new maintenance schedule
(LEE & CHANG, 2018)					0.17	n.d.	Taiwan	2018	jobs/kWh
(KEČEK ET AL., 2019)	6	3	9	5	14	onshore	Croatia	2019	FTE/million invested
(KEČEK ET AL., 2019)	1	7	8	4	11	onshore	Croatia	2019	FTE/million value produced
(MIKULI ET AL., 2018)	6.1	3.2	9.3	5	14.3	onshore	Croatia	2018	FTE/million invested
(MIKULI ET AL., 2018)	0.6	6.5	7.1	3.6	10.7	Onshore	Croatia	2018	FTE/million value produced

B8: local share data

	job sector	(share) local	(share) national	total national	location	on/offshore	year
(GÖNÜL ET AL., 2021)	Manu	0%	0%		Turkey	onshore	2019
(GÖNÜL ET AL., 2021)	Manu	0%	0%		Turkey	offshore	2019
(CHARLES RAJESH KUMAR ET AL., 2019)	Manu		40%	40%	India		2018
(SCHILLING ET AL., 2018)	O&M		81%	81%	Northern Kenya		2018
(GARSOUS & WORACK, 2022)	Manu		75%	75%	China		2016
(GARSOUS & WORACK, 2022)	Manu		70%	70%	Spain		2016
(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	O&M	90%	5%	95%	Brazil	onshore	2023
(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	Manu	50%	30%	80%	Brazil	onshore	2023

(VASCONCELLOS & CAIADO COUTO, 2021)	Con	90%	5%	95%	Brazil	onshore	2023
(KANDROT ET AL., 2020)	Con	local			Ireland	offshore	2030
(KANDROT ET AL., 2020)	O&M	local			Ireland	offshore	2030
(KANDROT ET AL., 2020)	Plan	local			Ireland	offshore	2030
(KANDROT ET AL., 2020)	Manu		0%		Ireland	offshore	2030
(MOLDVAY ET AL., 2013)	Manu		66-80%		South Africa	onshore	2013
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	Con	24%			US, Texas	onshore	2011
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	O&M	72%			US, Texas	onshore	2011
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	Con	20%			US, Texas	onshore	2011
(SLATTERY ET AL., 2011)	O&M	57%			US, Texas	onshore	2011
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	Manu		0%		Portugal	onshore	2015
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	O&M	local			Portugal	onshore	2015
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	Con	local			Portugal	onshore	2015
(KABAYO ET AL., 2019)	decom	local			Portugal	onshore	2019

